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Refugee Protection in Europe and Beyond

Comparative Report

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List of Abbreviations

AFM	Tax Registration Number (Greece)
AMKA	Social Security Number (Greece)
AnKER	Arrival, Decision and Return Centres Ankunfts-, Entscheidungs-, und Rückführungszentrum (Germany)
ASAM	Association for Solidarity with Migrants (Turkey)
BAMF	Federal Office for Migration and Refugees (<i>Bundesamt für Migration und Flüchtlinge</i> , Germany)
BG	Border Guard (Poland)
CEAS	Common European Asylum System
CPR	Pre-removal Detention Centres (Italy)
CRRF	Comprehensive Refugee Response Framework
DFT	Detained Fast Track (the UK)
DGMM	Directorate-General for Migration Management (Turkey)
EASO	European Asylum Support Office
ECHR	European Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
EURODAC	European Dactyloscopy
FRONTEX	European Border and Coast Guard Agency
GSO	General Directorate of General Security (Lebanon)
ICRC	International Committee of the Red Cross
IDP	Internally Displaced Persons
IHL	International Humanitarian Law
IHRL	International Human Rights Law
INGOS	International Non-governmental Organizations
IOM	International Organization for Migration
IR	Implementation Regulation (Turkey)
KEELPNO	Centre for Disease Control and Prevention (Greece)
KR-I	Kurdistan Region of Iraq
LFIP	Law on Foreigners and International Protection (Turkey)
LGBTIs	Lesbian Gay Bisexual Transgender Intersex
MoU	Memorandum of Understanding
MSs	Member States
OIC	Organization of Islamic Cooperation
PDMM	Provincial Directorate of Migration Management (Turkey)
RESPOND	Multilevel Governance of Migration in Europe and Beyond
RIS	Reception and Identification Service
RSD	Refugee Status Determination
SMA	Swedish Migration Agency (Sweden)
SPRAR	The National System for the Protection for Asylum Seekers and Refugees
TPR	Temporary Protection Regulation (Turkey)
UN	United Nations
UNHCR	United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees
WPs	Work packages
WP3	Work package on International /Refugee Protection
VCRS	The Vulnerable Children's Resettlement Scheme (the UK)
VPRS	the Syrian Vulnerable Person Resettlement Scheme (the UK)

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About the RESPOND Project

RESPOND: Multilevel Governance of Mass Migration in Europe and Beyond Project (*hereafter* RESPOND) is a three-year project (2017-2020) that is funded by the European Commission (EC) under the Horizon2020 Programme with the goal of enhancing the governance capacity and policy coherence of the European Union (EU), its Member States and neighbours. RESPOND is a comprehensive study of migration governance in the wake of the 2015 refugee crisis, one of the biggest challenges that the Union has faced since its establishment. The crisis foregrounded the vulnerability of European borders, the tenuous jurisdiction of the Schengen system and broad problems in the multilevel governance of migration and integration. One of the most visible impacts of the refugee crisis has been the polarisation of politics within EU Member States (MSs) and the (in)coherence in the response policies of Member States to the crisis.

Bringing together 14 partners from 7 disciplines, RESPOND aims to:

- provide an in-depth understanding of the governance of recent mass migration at macro, meso and micro levels through cross-country comparative research;
- critically analyse governance practices with the aim of enhancing the migration governance capacity and policy coherence of the EU, its member states and third countries.

RESPOND is a comprehensive study of migration governance in the wake of the 2015 refugee crisis. The project probes policy-making processes and policy (in)coherence through comparative research in source, transit, and destination countries.

RESPOND addresses how policy (in)coherence between the EU and its MSs, as well as between states differentially positioned as transit, hosting and source countries, affects migration governance. Specifically, we will analyse the reasons behind the apparent policy incoherence by delineating interactions and outcomes between national refugee systems and the EU.

RESPOND studies migration governance through a narrative which is constructed along five thematic fields: (1) Border management and security, (2) Refugee protection regimes, (3) Reception policies, (4) Integration policies, and (5) Conflicting Europeanization. Each thematic field reflects a juncture in the migration journey of refugees and is designed to provide a holistic view of policies, their impact and the responses of affected actors.

The work plan is organized around 11 work packages (WPs) – of which 8 have research tasks. The project also includes two WPs to organise impact-related activities targeting different audiences, including the scientific community, policy actors and the general public.

Executive Summary

This comparative report is based on the RESPOND country reports [deliverable D3.1] that discusses the developments regarding legislation, policy measures and practices on refugee protection, but most importantly the implementation aspect in ten countries covered by the project (Austria, Germany, Greece, Iraq, Italy, Lebanon, Poland, Sweden, Turkey and the United Kingdom) for the 2011-2019 period. As a continuation of the RESPOND *Comparative Report: Legal & Policy Framework of Migration Governance* (Pannia et al., 2018) [D1.3], this report aims to provide a comparative analysis of refugee protection, emphasising the implementation aspect as drawn from the experiences and perceptions of meso and micro level actors. In doing so, the report offers analytical insights for evaluating the implications of the dynamics of refugee protection, which has undergone many changes since 2011.

In terms of the common international legal framework, all RESPOND countries are signatories of the 1951 Geneva Convention and the 1967 Protocol Relating to the Status of Refugees, except Iraq and Lebanon. Also, Turkey has ratified the Protocol with a geographic limitation. The majority of the countries (7 out of 10) are EU MSs, and therefore, bound by the relevant EU *acquis*, to create the Common European Asylum System (CEAS). The United Kingdom has repeatedly displayed opt-outs, exceptions and uncertainties in the field of refugee protection. As a common consensus on refugee protection and the sharing of responsibilities, the Global Compact on Refugees (2018) is also signed by a number of countries covered in this project, except Austria, Hungary¹, Italy and Poland.

Despite the largely shared regional, international and supranational obligations regarding refugee protection, the overarching pattern in the field of refugee protection is characterized by a restrictive approach.

The main tendencies in international protection regimes can be summarised as following:

- As of 2015, almost all countries have faced pressure and a lack of administrative capacity to process the increasing number of applications. Many countries have introduced a more state-centred (in terms of governance, thus more centralised) asylum system and restrictive policies to reduce the number of asylum seekers reaching their territory, and claiming asylum. This restrictive policy also aimed at increasing the number of deportations and returns.
- Although some countries were relatively more welcoming at the beginning Syrian displacement in 2011, such as Turkey (open-doors policy) and Lebanon, restricted access to national/federal territories, additional physical measures such as security walls and other actions such as push backs have become common, hindering the asylum procedure, particularly after 2015.
- Many RESPOND countries have introduced additional procedural measures to prevent and restrain access to international protection as well as to speed up asylum assessments, such as accelerated procedures, fast-track-procedures, border procedures. Increased rejections and long waiting periods have become policies in themselves.
- Anti-immigrant narratives and negative representations of refugee arrivals, even in some of the most welcoming countries, have become common.
- Almost all countries tended to downgrade the rights of applicants and beneficiaries of protection. In general, all newly introduced amendments or regulations impose new restrictions or limitations to existing standards of rights. However, at the same time, some countries developed policies and practices to respond to the humanitarian crisis and welcomed refugees only from certain nationalities on the grounds of humanitarian or national reasons, through residence permits and family reunification. As for the RESPOND countries who are EU Member States, the observance of the so-called minimum EU-level standards, or even lower, has become common.

¹ Hungary is one of the RESPOND countries, but it is not a part of the Work package 3: Refugee Protection.

- All countries display an extremely complex and continually changing legal framework on refugee protection. The newly introduced additional procedures result in the fragmentation of the examination of claims through the categorisation of asylum seekers. This also resulted in stratified legal statuses with different procedures and specified rights, adding up to the traceable nationality-based discrimination against certain asylum seekers (e.g. Afghans), creating 'desirable' and 'undesirable' migrants/refugees.
- In general, compliance with the rule of law is seen as an impediment. In particular, the secondary law has become more restrictive, and some new provisions and practices have clashed with constitutionally provided individual rights or international human rights. Temporary protection measures become more relevant through the extension of their coverage.
- The legal and political framework of refugee law has become quite fragmented and stratified, difficult even for experts to understand and interpret. The fragmented, complex structure is accompanied by a lack of consistent and standardized implementation.
- In terms of governance, the actors involved in refugee protection are numerous and operate at different levels (local, national, regional, supranational); there is a coexistence of centralisation and de-centralisation, localisation and re-nationalisation. In almost all countries, the role of 'care-taker' is undertaken by an increasing number of non-state actors, although state actors are still in control. In all countries, civil society movements monitor and criticise legal disparities, problems in the implementation of policies, and arbitrary practices.
- A problematic policy is the adoption and implementation of the Hotspot approach in Greece and Italy –a joint application of policies from national and EU agencies – which has resulted in further rights violation of asylum seekers, increasing pushbacks at the borders and returns, normalizing inhuman treatment.
- One of the main findings of the national reports is a strong tendency towards return policies as a mechanism to reduce the number of asylum applications. In this line, the list of third safe countries is updated in a way that legitimizes deportations and returns, blurring the lines between forced and voluntary returns.
- The categorization of states in terms of safe countries or first asylum, transit, destination or origin countries leads to a given specialization of states; as a result, some countries operate as "safety valves" and "buffer zones".
- Vulnerability continues to play a crucial role in the examination of the asylum applications, as many EU countries, such as Greece, Italy and Poland provide that asylum applications by persons with special needs are to be examined by way of priority.
- Although the Global Impact on Refugees is not included in the national reports, it should also be emphasized that seven RESPOND countries have signed the Compact, while Austria and Italy abstained. Poland, as well as four other countries (the United States, Hungary, Israel and Czech Republic) voted against the Compact. This Compact is not binding but provides common ground for both EU and non-EU RESPOND countries. On the one hand, as a global response to mass migration with fair responsibility sharing and better protection, the Compact can be seen as a more systematic collaboration of states in refugee and international protection. On the other hand, the rejections and their justification reaffirm the existence of renationalization, the emphasis on the sovereignty of nation-states and increasing securitization of migration policies. Last but not least, one of the two key objectives of the Compact are "to expand access to third-country solutions" and "to support conditions in countries of origin for return in safety and dignity" (UNHCR, 2020).

1. Introduction

This comparative report is part of the third Work Package of RESPOND (WP3) and deals with the issues of refugee protection and asylum procedures in RESPOND countries (Austria, Germany, Greece, Iraq, Italy, Lebanon, Poland, Sweden, Turkey, and the United Kingdom) during the period of 2011-2018.

The main goal of this report is to present and discuss the legal framework and different implementations thereof, drawing from the country reports on asylum and refugee protection prepared for the RESPOND project. These country reports are built on both desk research on legislation and policy and on first-hand data collected on implementations, perceptions and experiences through fieldwork and qualitative interviews with actors such as officials from government, non-governmental, international and local organizations, asylum seekers and refugees. This report can also be seen as an updated version of the “Comparative Report: Legal & Policy Framework of Migration Governance” (*hereafter* WP1 Comparative Report/ Pannia et al., 2018), specifically focused on refugee protection regimes.

The report highlights the recent developments in the legal and institutional framework of refugee protection in the RESPOND countries. A comprehensive definition of protection comprises an extensive approach that encompasses actors as well, defines it as “the ensemble of legislation, policies, implementation practices, institutions and actors involved in the definition, conceptualization and implementation of asylum procedures and refugee protection” (Leivaditi et al., 2020, p.9). From legal perspective it refers to “all activities aimed at obtaining full respect for the rights of the individual in accordance with the letter and also spirit of the relevant bodies of law, namely human rights law, international humanitarian law and refugee law” (Ibrido and Terlizzi, 2019, p. 11). As it is discussed in the conceptualisation part below, rather than solely the “refugee protection” or “protection”, the term “protection regime” which encompasses both legal, political framework, institutional organization and practices is adopted and reflected with the meso and micro level analysis by the RESPOND country reports. The concept of protection regimes helps to provide a full board definition encompasses different institutionalized forms of protection, such international protection regimes, and different forms of national protection regimes.

Given this conceptual background, the report examines the multilevel governance architecture regarding migration and asylum policies. It also focuses on examining the practical implementation problems through the perceptions and experiences of relevant ‘meso-level’ actors, political stakeholders such as municipal administrations and non-state actors such as NGOs, as well as of ‘micro-level’ actors, including migrants, refugees and asylum seekers in different countries.

1.1. Methodology

Using a qualitative research, this report addresses the legal and institutional framework regarding international protection in particular refugee protection at macro level in 10 RESPOND countries. It also reflects the views, perceptions, experiences and sense-making of refugees at micro level and reflects the experience of perceptions of the meso-level service providers, policy implementers regarding protection in those countries.

This report is based on ten country reports.² More than 200 stakeholder interviews and 540 interviews with asylum seekers and refugees were conducted in those countries during the 2018-2019 period. In the country reports, the interview material is analysed through a common

² The national reports cover reception policies and practices between 2011 and 2018 in the following countries: Austria, Germany, Greece, Iraq, Italy, Lebanon, Poland, Sweden, Turkey and the United Kingdom. They were referenced within the report and listed in the Reference section.

coding scheme and qualitative analysis software programmes (e.g.Nvivo, Atlas.ti). The interview material in each country report was supported by secondary sources and careful investigation of legal and policy documents on refugee protection. In order to compare results, certain themes were identified in advance as guiding the reports, and additional themes were derived from the completed country reports, particularly from the participant quotations so as to build a more comprehensive theme list. Nvivo is used to code the themes in each country reports, paying attention to the level of analysis. The findings of the comparative report are the result of a combination of major themes, informed to draw similarities, and minor themes which assisted in the discussion of differences. Both for meso and micro level analysis, the following themes are traced in transcriptions: first registration; legal aid, interpretation, consultancy and interview process; asylum related procedures; reception, identification and accommodation; vulnerabilities; relocation; Dublin procedure and admissibility; hotspots; relocation; detention; deportation, return and readmission; appeal procedure; and family unification. Since the report mainly focus on the refugee protection from the first application to the final decision including the appeal procedure, the other aspects of the protection were excluded and covered with the other WPs of the RESPOND project.

The report is divided into four sections, namely, Introduction (including methodology), Conceptualising Refugee Protection, Comparative Findings from the National Reports, Analysis of Findings and Conclusion.

2. Conceptualising International Protection

It is commonly shared that refugee and international protection are products of specific historical and geographical circumstances and they are not taken for granted concepts. These are few questions addressed in the literature. Our comparative report may provide some food for thoughts for the following questions:

- How does international protection appear as the part of migration governance?
- How is protection discussed within theoretical and disciplinary frameworks?
- What are the historical foundations and current manifestation of protection?
- Could a unified institutional structure for protection, regionally or internationally, guarantee a more efficient system of protection?

The concept of 'protection' is highly blurred and contested. Protection is often conceived as a right. Its broad definition refers to "all activities aimed at obtaining full respect for the rights of the individual in accordance with the letter and spirit of the relevant bodies of law, namely human rights law, international humanitarian law and refugee law" (UNHCR, 2011, p. 5). Protection is also approached as an objective and an activity. As an objective, protection implies full and equal respect for the rights of all individuals without discrimination, as enshrined in national and international law and as a legal responsibility (principally of the state and its agents, as well as of other agents, such as the United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees – UNHCR). Protection has also an activity dimension, which has four aspects: 1) responsive (to prevent or stop violations of rights); 2) remedial (to ensure a remedy to violations, including through access to justice and reparations); 3) environmental building (to promote respect for rights and the rule of law) and 4) empowering (Ibid.)

Protection cannot be reduced **to survival and physical security**. It requires the provision of the full range of rights, including civil, political, economic, social and cultural.

When states and other authorities are unable or unwilling to fulfil their protection obligations, humanitarian and development actors play a role in protection provision, bringing **the concept of "humanitarian protection."** The notion of humanitarian protection is strongly connected with the Geneva Conventions, thus the notion of humanitarian protection has been conceived at supranational level in order to respond to the needs of all those who, while in need of protection, were not covered by the strict application of the status provided for by the Conventions. More recently, the notion has been used in the framework of the EU law. Humanitarian protection, as defined by the European Commission, is provided under the conditions of "violence, coercion, deliberate deprivation and abuse for persons, groups and communities in the context of humanitarian crises. It is in compliance with the humanitarian principles of humanity, neutrality, impartiality and independence and within the framework of international law and in particular international human rights law, international humanitarian law and refugee law." (European Commission, 2016).

In general, 'international protection' and 'refugee protection' have been used interchangeably, which is the case for the analysed country reports. The concept of 'refugee protection' generally refers to 'international protection' and, despite its wide use, the meaning of protection remains open to interpretations. According to Puggioni (2016, p. 1), the lack of clarity in reference to protection is due to the fact that it is often conflated with the concept of assistance; thus, refugee protection tends to refer to any policies regarding refugees. The UNHCR Statute uses it as "international protection" (UNHCR, 2001, p. 30) in relation to the lack of protection in the country of citizenship. 'International' protection refers to situations where the country of origin cannot provide protection, and the international community fills the gap by providing "diplomatic protection" or, in other words, international protection (Fortion, 2011 cited in Puggioni, 2016, p. 7).

Refugees have a long history, and maybe limited and not structured but still as international recognized first refugee protection initiative as well as the awareness regarding the responsibility of the international community to provide protection and find solutions for

refugees dates back to the 1921, when the League of Nations and the election of Dr. Nansen as the first High Commissioner for Russian refugees (Feller, 2011, p. 130). The more global and structured regime is founded on clear norms relating to protection and solutions for refugees with the Convention Relating to the Status of Refugees (1951) and its Protocol (1967). The 1951 Convention was the first, and still remains as the only binding refugee protection instrument with a universal character despite its lacking points (Ibid., p. 131). It has never been able to provide solutions and rather than individuals' rights, mainly addressed the states' responsibilities, but put in place a global definition of refugee "a person who flees their country because of a well-founded fear of persecution on the grounds of race, religion, nationality, membership in a particular social group, or political opinion" (Article 1) along with the common principles such as the principle of nonrefoulement, providing protection to all refugees without discrimination.

In institutional terms, the United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees (UNHCR) appears as the significant turning point that mandated to work with states to comply with these norms. The UNCHR was established in 1951 as the successor the International Refugee Organization (IRO, 1947-1950) for providing international protection for refugees and to seek permanent solutions to their problems by assisting governments (Feller, 2011, p. 131). As pointed in Feller's genealogy of the international refugee regime, the 1950s is marked as the period for development of the international refugee protection regime with the 1951 Convention and the establishment of the UNHCR. During 1960s and 70s, the regime expands its borders and we observe some attempts to avoid the Eurocentric approach. While in terms of institutional structure, the mandate of the UNHCR reached beyond Europe, in particular to the African continent. In parallel, we come across with the 1967 Protocol which expands UNHCR's mandate to protect and assist groups of refugees falling outside the definition and geographic ambit of the 1951 Convention as including a broader category of persons. Thus, in a sense very narrow geographic and temporal terms of the Convention was partially overcome with the 1967 Protocol. In addition, during 1970s, this international refugee regime have been also adopted within different regions as being also updated through a combination of interpretation by particular states and by supplementary regional agreements in Africa, Europe and Latin America although the Convention has not been signed by all the countries, in particular in Asia. The regional refugee protection regimes were supported with the new instruments such as the 1969 OAU Convention on the Specific Aspects of Refugee Problems in Africa (OAU Convention, 1974). It should also be noted that some of them were providing further protection as mentioning the further aspects. For example, the OAU Convention defines refugees as also recognition of generalized conflict and violence and its victims as refugees:

Every person who, owing to external aggression, occupation, foreign domination or events seriously disturbing public order in either part or the whole of his country of origin or nationality, is compelled to leave his place of habitual residence in order to seek refuge in another place outside his country of origin or nationality (Article I(2)).

During the 1970s and 1990s political changes caused by decolonization and the Cold War reformed policies and movements of people. Due to emergency violent events and the unwillingness of more powerful states to take responsibility or to recognize the responsible state for protection on international level, large numbers of people become displaced without protection. Under these conditions, the priority became the humanitarian assistance in order to cover urgent needs and the UNHCR and other international organizations as well as local and international Non-Governmental Organizations undertaken this action. Since then, main features of these situations have been the increasing the numbers of internally displaced persons and the increasing number of camps within the country, closures of the borders by neighbouring countries (Loescher et al, 2003). Concerning the international protection- the refugee protection is not applicable in the cases of not crossing borders - has been marginalized, while the humanitarian assistance prevails.

Concerning Europe and the EU policies, the ideological basis for the reception of refugees after the end of the Cold War ceased to exist and fears arose within the EU for the increase of

immigrants from these countries to the Member States. As Lavenex (2001) observes, some countries in the EU managed to shift the issue of asylum from their borders to the European Union, which is in danger of becoming a haven for refugees due to their liberal policies. In this way, they put pressure on the other Member States, third states as well as on the refugees and asylum seekers themselves, adopting restrictive measures in order to control movements in their territories and the constructing European one (Petracou, 2004). The aims of these policies were: constraining access to European territory (carriers' liability, etc.); reduction of stay in the EU (detention, deportation, restriction of social benefits, temporary protection); exclusion from asylum procedures (safe countries, country of origin, nationality). Helton argued that since 1990s "a new strategy of containment is emerging, this time championing migration control and not ideology" (Helton, 2001, p. 10).

Moreover, it is important to mention that the asylum "crisis", an overloaded system and bogus refugees constitute basic elements in the formulation of the EU and member states of refugee policies (Loescher, 2001). Additionally, the implementation of temporary protection rather than the refugee one in the member states of the EU in the beginning of 1990s considered as a compromise between the provision of protection and non-burden on the asylum system (Koser and Black, 1999) raising the issue of burden sharing for the asylum system among member states (Petracou, 2004).

Since the establishment of the international protection regime, we have been observing the development and the growth of the regime's primary organization with additional actors. However, principles relating to the protection of refugees predate the modern state system is not limited with the last 60 years but have evolved alongside the state system over the past 350 years (Goodwin-Gill and McAdam 2007 cited in Betts and Milner, 2019, p. 1). But the main developments as well as the majority of the norms were codified in particular aftermath of World War II as the response to the over 55 million displaced people after the War (Ibid.). First, the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (1948) provided a common ground for the states to recognize the right of asylum as one of the fundamental rights with the Article 14:

Everyone has the right to seek and to enjoy in other countries asylum from persecution"), negative protection or the first generation of rights refers to the protection of the individual from excesses of the state such as the right to life, equality before the law, freedom of speech, the right to a fair trial, freedom of religion, and voting rights.

The establishment of the UNHCR provided the institutional core of the new regime with the main two aims: "to ensure the international protection of refugees" and "to cooperate with governments to find permanent solutions for refugees" (Ibid., p. 2). But, the 1951 Convention relating to the Status of Refugees, which initially defined the obligations of signatory states "in very narrow geographic and temporal terms" (Ibid.), which was partially overcome with the 1967 Protocol and this international refugee regime have been also adopted within different regions as being also updated through a combination of interpretation by particular states and by supplementary regional agreements in Africa, Europe and Latin America but it is a fact that even the Geneva Convention has not been signed by all the countries, in particular in Asia. Also, despite the common norms and the UNHCR's coordination, "states sought to retain ultimate authority over refugee affairs and did not include any decision-making mechanisms for the regime itself (Ibid., p. 5).

The regime's evolution continued in terms of its scope and practice after forming the core set of norms regarding refugee protection, organizations and decision-making process. However, Betts and Wilner (2019) argue that despite the evolution of the regime into more global one, "states retain ultimate control over the quantity and quality of asylum they grant to refugees on their territory" (p. 4). Number of case studies across the globe illustrate that countries engage in international refugee protection regime in various ways, they often fail to comply with provisions and spirit of the Convention and its Protocol (Dhavan 2005; Scheel and Rattfish,

2014; Song, 2018). The states' autonomy to carry out policies limiting access to territory poses a threat to international refugee protection regime (Morris, 2003).

An important issue of refugee protection is that “a range of international institutions have proliferated, many of which overlap in scope and purpose with the refugee regime”, which appears as a “complex” one because of these overlapping institutions (Betts and Wilner, 2019, p. 4).). The complexity of this regime is displayed with the following figure:

Figure 1: The Global Refugee Complex

Source: Alexander Betts and James Milner (2019). “Governance of the Global Refugee Regime”, World Refugee Council Research Paper No. 13, p. 5.

The concept of international protection has been the subject of the discipline of international relations, which traditionally focuses on state sovereignty and admission policies or the interpretation of international law, cooperation during refugee crises, global governance and international refugee regimes (Puggioni, 2016, p. 8). However, protection itself as a concept has not been adequately questioned and theorised.

The response to the question of who holds primary responsibility for refugee protection is highly controversial. The answers range from the international community to the representative of the refugee regime, UNHCR, host states, prospective asylum countries or all or none of the above. The leading actor in the asylum regime is the governments with reference to the common norm that it is “the duty and responsibility of states to respect, protect and fulfil the human rights of refugees within their borders” (Purkey, 2013, p. 693). However, the legal uncertainties allow states to avoid protection responsibilities as, in fact, international law is dominated by the “state sovereignty-oriented approach” and states are only bound by contest (Jubilut et al., 2018). In the current asylum systems, states are able to exploit legal ambiguity to distance themselves from asylum seekers. Powerful governments show particular decisiveness in what refers to legal structures. The offshoring and outsourcing of protection (also known as extraterritorialization) is also used for distancing purposes, as well as (temporary or permanent) control mechanisms that prevent refugees from arriving to national territory, given that asylum claims can be made only when the person enters the prospective asylum country. As for less developed countries with poor human rights records, the situation displays other sets of ambiguities because it is difficult to monitor compliance with international law (Gammeltoft-Hansen, 2011). In general, a “precariousness of protection” emerges when states

seek to limit and restrict their obligations as much as possible (McAdam, 2017). Also, states avoid cooperation for responsibility-sharing in protection. All these generate a “responsibility deficit in the international protection regime.” (Ibid.).

Apart from states, there are also other international, supranational, sub-national and local actors such as the United Nations (UN), the EU, international non-governmental organizations (INGOs) and others such as sub-national and local actors (municipalities, local NGOs etc.). The UNHCR plays a substantial role as the norm diffuser in international protection and assistance. Particularly in the less developed countries of the Global South where most refugee situations happen, protection responsibilities have been carried out in neighbouring or first destination countries in the Global South by the UNHCR. However, the UN Agency is criticised for not conducting effective monitoring and enforcing protection, acting rather as a mere aid provider in protracted refugee situations. It is defined as “international protection as provided by countries of asylum in cooperation with the UNHCR is an effort to compensate for the protection that refugees should have received in their own countries and its objective is not fulfilled until refugees once again enjoy protection as full-fledged members of a national community (UN General Assembly, 1993, para 1.3, p. 2). The UN and UNHCR reaffirm the state-centric approach. Also, the EU is the major player for Europe as well as and the UNHCR for non-European and North American regions (Global South). In addition, INGOs and NGOs attempt to influence the agenda and become global stakeholders in what refers to asylum (beyond North-South divide) (Joly, 2002, p.8).

It can be said that refugee protection is a matter of governance, in particular multi-governance that refers to “systems of governance where there is a dispersion of authority upwards, downwards and sideways between levels of government – local, regional, national and supranational – as well as across spheres and sectors, including states, markets and civil society.” (Daniell and Kay, 2017, p. 3). Mainly a field where state agencies play a central role but also international (intergovernmental and transnational) bodies are mainly acting in a soft governance mode, where they impose the international refugee protection law on countries, but countries always find a leeway to apply or not the international law, either instrumentalize it for their foreign policy goals or develop ad hoc legislations and protections regimes; local authorities – limited roles (e.g. service provider) due to the nature of the issue – admission criteria and civil society – more filling in the gap in practice, providing service and legal assistance in this process; and more proactive forms of activism and monitoring functions. Thus, beside states and IOs, local authorities, civil society partners (NGOs, faith-based organisations, academia), courts, the media and refugees are also part of the protection regime. INGOs contribute to the system as implementing partners and instruments for change regarding refugee protection. Therefore, the RESPOND project country reports have also considered said non-state actors, given that they contribute to the system as implementing partners and instruments for change in what refers to refugee protection.

Not only the question of ‘who’ is important, but also of ‘what’: ‘what will the protection look like’. This question can be addressed by referencing the 1951 Geneva Convention, as well as the 2011 EU Members Qualification Directive³ and 2013 Asylum Procedures Directive⁴. These documents are important insofar as refugee law pertains to human rights and is closely linked to international humanitarian law. The signatory states hold obligations of the refugee status and, therefore, must respect fundamental individual rights.

Some scholars argue that, decades after its signing, the Refugee Convention can still provide an adequate framework for protection as an instrument of law (Kneebone, 2018). The Convention is seen as the key regulating component of the protection regime and a blueprint for positive action as it sets out the minimum standards and conditions within which states must operate (McAdam, 2017). It is argued that the interpretation of the rules in the Convention are dynamic, allowing for its adaption to evolving conceptions of human rights law (Goodwin-

³ Directive 2011/95/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 December 2011 <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=OJ:L:2011:337:0009:0026:en:PDF>

⁴ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32013L0032&from=en>

Gill, 2013). On the other hand, many criticise the Convention in terms of its effectiveness regarding international protection regime. Critics of the Refugee Convention mainly focus on two diverging perspectives. The first perspective contends that the refugee definition enshrined in the 1951 Convention is both limiting and outdated, as it was originally influenced by the historical context of the Second World War (McAdam, 2017). For instance, it does not deal with current environmental displacement or gender-based persecution as a ground for refugee status. The second perspective considers that the Convention itself is responsible for the displacement crises because it is too generous (McAdam, 2017). Non-refoulement is the cornerstone of the Convention and it is among the vital rights that must be respected by states. However, the real situation is more complex, as there are critical areas of legal ambiguity in refugee law (Gammeltoft-Hansen, 2011; Menjivar and Kanstroom, 2013).

A recent attempt in the field of refugee protection is the Global Compact on Refugees, adopted in 2018 as one of two foreseen separate compacts by the New York Declaration (2016). The Compact provides the Comprehensive Refugee Response Framework (CRRF), as agreed by Member States. The CRRF focuses on sharing burdens and responsibilities, national and regional arrangements for specific situations, and tools for funding, partnerships, and data gathering and sharing. The specific emphasis of the Compact is on the responsibility-sharing in the absence of agreement about concrete rules with more detailed modalities. However, it remains quite limited in that it makes no reference to how states can contribute and how to achieve fair sharing in terms of financial burden or the sharing of refugees. It reinforces the role of the state in protection as well as refugee law. Thus, as a non-binding but mainly normative consensus, the Global Compact on Refugees seems unable to fix the shortcomings of the 1951 Convention; however, it can be seen as a positive effort to address 'how' questions by providing a framework for collaboration and challenging the implementation problems facing refugee protection.

Neither the Convention nor the recently adopted Global Compact on Refugees regulate the procedures for granting refugee status; this space is left to the discretion of institutions and agents (state bureaucracies) that translate the Convention into the national asylum regimes along with national and regional asylum laws. Countries adopt implementing legislations to bring their law into conformity with domestic obligations under the international treaties (Farbenblum, 2011). They track the language of the treaties, particularly regarding fundamental prohibitions such as non-refoulement or the definition of refugees. They interpret, adapt and contest the technical and administrative dimension of legislations.

Asylum procedures and the highly intense related bureaucracies play a substantial role in implementing and giving meaning to legislations as they interact with the asylum applicants, interpreters, and medical and linguistic experts who play a role in asylum regimes. Therefore, asylum bureaucracies involved in protection require scrutiny. It is quite important to address the role of officials (migration officers, case workers), lawyers and judges in the asylum procedures, how the asylum system is organised, how the different actors conceive and perform their roles, how the applications are assessed, discussed and decided on in bureaus and courts. The answer to these questions requires an ethnographically informed analysis of national asylum systems with emphasis on the legal, administration and organisational dimension.⁶ Existing studies show that practices are a vital part of the asylum bureaucracy often characterised by their organisational practices rather than their formal structures. For example, "the social practices of decision-making officials in determining refugee status go beyond labelling and categorization, and include the construction of facts, artefacts and (in)credibility" (Dahlvik, 2017, p. 369). Thus, the contingency and volatility of the (asylum)

⁵ For the full text https://www.unhcr.org/gcr/GCR_English.pdf [last access 23 May 2020].

⁶ For further information see UK, Austria, Hungary, Switzerland examples see Campbell, J. R. (2016). *Bureaucracy, law and dystopia in the United Kingdom's asylum system*. Taylor & Francis. Dahlvik, J. (2018). *Inside Asylum Bureaucracy: Organizing Refugee Status Determination in Austria*. Springer Open. For Hungary example, see Rajaram, P. K., & Arendas, Z. (2013). 10 Exceeding categories: law, bureaucracy and acts of citizenship by asylum seekers in Hungary. In *Enacting European Citizenship*, eds. Engin Isin and Michael Sward. Cambridge (pp. 195-220). Miaz, J. (2017). From the law to the decision: The social and legal conditions of asylum adjudication in Switzerland. *European Policy Analysis*, 3(2), 372-396

regime 'at work' has implications, as it is necessarily reproduced and reinvented by bureaucrats in the process of determining refugee status" (Ibid.). Furthermore, this is a relational and interactive process between agency and micro organisational structure, and the practices of caseworkers are bound by social and legal constraints which force them to perform an interpretation of the law when implementing it. The tendency to strictness may be a result of "the controls of superiors and peers, as well as [of] the secondary implementation rules created within the office to orient caseworkers' practices" (Miaz, 2017, p. 372).

In addition to the Convention and practices of national asylum bureaucracies and given that the majority of countries under consideration are EU Member States, the Comparative Report also consults with the normative framework of the EU to respond to the "what" question. And this is so for two reasons: firstly, following the so called "European Refugee Crisis", the Common European Asylum System (CEAS) became relevant in the implementation and introduction of several national regulations on refugee protection. Secondly, the country reports show that the EU's legal and institutional framework is of utmost importance. In this framework, 'refugee protection' refers to the ensemble of EU legislation, policies, implementation practices, institutions, and actors concerned with defining, conceptualising, and implementing asylum and refugee protection in the Member States. This structure reflects mainly the EU legal and institutional framework, along with its policy measures. For non-EU countries, in particular Lebanon and Iraq, the focus was on both national and international frameworks.

Within the EU framework, the term "protection" is in line with the definition provided by the current Qualification Directive of 2011 that amends Council Directive 2004/83/EC of 29 April 2004 on minimum standards for the qualification and status of third country nationals or stateless persons as refugees or as persons who otherwise need international protection, and the content of the protection granted. The Qualification Directive sets out the criteria for the qualification of applicants for refugee status or subsidiary protection and defines the rights afforded to the beneficiaries of these statuses, hence provisions on protection from refoulement, residence permits and travel documents. Although access to employment, education, social welfare, healthcare, accommodation, integration facilities, as well as specific provisions for children and vulnerable persons are contained in the legislative instrument, the country reports of the RESPOND on refugee protection, including this comparative one, focus on protection on its most specific meaning, leaving aside all other aspects, that pertain more to reception and integration. In addition to the Qualification Directive, the Asylum Procedures Directive is taken as a main reference for WP3 country reports. This directive sets common procedures for the granting and withdrawal of international protection. It allows people fleeing persecution or serious harm to apply for international protection. The Council Directive on Temporary Protection⁷ must also be considered.

Protection should also be understood in the context of human rights beyond being refugee. The right to asylum refers to the previously mentioned "responsive-immediate actions" of the country that provides asylum so as to prevent or stop violations of human rights or alleviate their immediate effects. If persecuted people enter their territories, states are expected to guarantee the right to life. Thus, it can be seen as a part of the first generation of rights that refers to the protection of the individual from excesses of the state such as the right to life, then come second and third-generation rights, which refer to Puggioni's 'positive protection'. Second-generation rights are linked to beyond formal equality and are of a fundamentally economic, social, and cultural nature. In a sense, they guarantee different members of the citizenry equal conditions and treatment. Thus, in the case of asylum, they have a "remedial" effect and aim to ensure a remedy to violations: the right to be employed under just and favourable conditions, the rights to food, housing and health care, as well as the provision of social security. Third-generation rights cover an extremely broad spectrum of rights such as

⁷ COUNCIL DIRECTIVE 2001/55/EC of 20 July 2001 on minimum standards for giving temporary protection in the event of a mass influx of displaced persons and on measures promoting a balance of efforts between Member States in receiving such persons and bearing the consequences thereof <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32001L0055&from=EN>.

numerous collective rights or the right to a healthy environment. Thus, they refer to the mentioned “environment-building – action” that aims to create an environment conducive to respect for human rights and the rule of law, including the reduction of exposure or vulnerability to protection risks. Briefly, the first-generation rights were more fundamental response and led to protection regimes which were formulated in the immediate aftermath of WWII. Second generation rights in the second half of 1960s are more in line with socio-cultural rights which constitute a paradigm shift in the approach towards refugees/migrants. It opened a new space for people to think beyond assimilation and an immediate response/protection mechanism. Third generation rights – 1970s and 80s – introduced rights in line with more radical forms of democracy: gender equality, environmental rights mainstreamed.

Although the RESPOND Project approaches refugee protection from a rights-based, broad perspective, it draws certain limits in order to limit overlaps with the other work packages. It focuses on international protection from the moment that asylum seekers and refugees apply for asylum until the final decision. This may include all kinds of protection – formal and informal, refugee protection, temporary protection and national forms of protection. The aforementioned conceptual discussions – in particular the ‘who and why’ dimensions – have been refocused after 2011, in particular following the 2015 “European Refugee Crisis”.

2.1. The Background of (International and European) Legal Framework on Protection

Despite their differences, the majority of RESPOND countries are part of the international and EU legal and institutional framework that will be overviewed below.

2.1.1. International Conventions and Treaties on Refugee Protection

The UN 1951 Geneva Convention⁸ (“Convention relating to the status of Refugees”) defines the term “refugee” and outlines the rights of the displaced, as well as the legal obligations of States to protect them. The cornerstone of the 1951 Convention is the “principle of non-refoulement” contained in Article 33. According to this principle, a refugee should not be returned to a country where he or she faces serious threats to his or her life or freedom. The **1967 Protocol** of the Convention broadens the applicability of the Convention by removing the geographical and time limits that initially restricted the Convention to persons who became refugees due to events occurring in Europe before 1 January 1951⁹.

Other **international human rights agreements and treaties** which refer to human and refugee rights include: the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights and its protocol, the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights, the Convention against Torture and other cruel, inhuman or degrading treatment or punishment, the Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women, the Convention on the Rights of the Child, the Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities, etc. Article 14 of the **Universal Declaration of Human Rights**¹⁰ states: “(1) Everyone has the right to seek and to enjoy in other countries asylum from persecution. (2) This right may not be invoked in the case of prosecutions genuinely arising from non-political crimes or from acts contrary to the purposes and principles of the United Nations”.

The **UN Convention against Torture**¹¹ upholds the principle of non-refoulement, which is an essential principle under international human rights, refugee, humanitarian and customary law.

⁸ United Nations Convention Relating to the Status of Refugees, UN Treaty Series vol. 189, 137.

⁹ UNHCR, The 1951 Refugee Convention and 1967 Protocol, <https://www.unhcr.org/about-us/background/4ec262df9/1951-convention-relating-status-refugees-its-1967-protocol.html>

¹⁰ Universal Declaration of Human Rights, UN, <https://www.un.org/en/universal-declaration-human-rights/>

¹¹ Convention against Torture and Other Cruel, Inhuman or Degrading Treatment or Punishment, Adopted and opened for signature, ratification and accession by General Assembly resolution 39/46 of 10 December 1984

Article 3 provides that "no state party shall expel, return or extradite a person to another state when there are substantial grounds for believing that they would be in danger of being subjected to torture".

Additional human rights instruments may promote regional cooperation and enhance human rights protection at a regional level. For instance, the **Arab Charter on Human Rights**, adopted by the sixteenth Arab Summit on May 23, 2004, includes articles on refugees and their rights¹². Article 26 states:

1- Every person legally present in the territory of a state party to this charter has freedom of movement and choice of residence in any part from that region within the limits of the legislation in force. 2- it is not permissible for any state party to deport any person who does not have its nationality and who is legally present on its territory, except in accordance with a decision issued following the law, and after enabling him to present his case to the competent authority, unless national security reasons necessitate otherwise, and in all cases, collective expulsion is prohibited.

Furthermore, the Council of Foreign Ministers of the Organization of Islamic Cooperation (OIC) adopted the **Cairo Declaration on Human Rights in Islam** on August 5, 1990¹³. Its articles are in line with the basic principles of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights as well as the 1951 Refugee Convention. In 2012, the OIC issued the **Ashgabat Declaration**, which indicates that the Member States continue to fulfil their firm commitment to provide protection to refugees, taking into account their national capabilities and local laws. The Declaration also acknowledges the importance of the 1951 Convention and its Additional Protocol¹⁴.

2.1.2. European Legal Framework on Refugee Protection

The **Dublin Regulation** aims to reduce refugees moving between one state and another, without there being any certainty about who will be the competent state for examining their asylum application (Favilli, 2018). Through the Regulation (EU) No 604/2013, known as Dublin Regulation III, the criteria and mechanisms for determining the responsible Member State are established, still in force today. Despite periodic revisions, the main rules of Dublin Regulation III have remained substantially unchanged, although the aim of the regulation is different today: it is no longer that of ensuring that there is at least one competent state to examine applications for protection but, rather, that there is just one. The main objective has become to reduce, if not to eliminate, the possibility of applicants for international protection choosing the state where the application is to be submitted and, thus, their movement, so-called secondary movements within the EU (Ibid.). Thus, the Dublin Regulation not only determines the competent Member State for examining an application for international protection, but also the state in which the person is meant to stay for a long period. Recently, the proposed reform of the Dublin Regulation¹⁵, tabled by the EC on 4 May 2016, entrusts Member States located at the external borders with the responsibility to filter out persons coming from a "first country of asylum", a "safe third country" or a "safe country of origin", and assess their security risks, before triggering the mechanism allocating responsibility across the EU.

The **Common European Asylum System** (CEAS) was developed by the EU in 1999 as a common asylum policy frame. It constitutes a framework of agreed rules which establish common procedures for international protection. It aims to ensure the fair and humane

entry into force 26 June 1987, in accordance with article 27

<https://www.ohchr.org/en/professionalinterest/pages/cat.aspx>

¹² Arab Charter on Human Rights, 2004,

http://www.eods.eu/library/LAS_Arab%20Charter%20on%20Human%20Rights_2004_EN.pdf

¹³ Organization of the Islamic Conference (OIC), *Cairo Declaration on Human Rights in Islam*, 5 August 1990, available at: <https://www.refworld.org/docid/3ae6b3822c.html>

¹⁴ Ashgabat Declaration of the International Ministerial Conference of the Organization of Islamic Cooperation on Refugees in The Muslim World, 12 May 2012, available at: <https://www.refworld.org/docid/595c95ba4.html>

¹⁵ European Commission, Proposal for a [Dublin IV Regulation], COM (2016) 270, 4 May 2016, Article 3(3).

treatment of applicants for international protection, to harmonize asylum systems in the EU and reduce the differences between Member States on the basis of binding legislation, as well as to strengthen practical cooperation between national asylum administrations and the external dimension of asylum. To facilitate the application of the European asylum system at the national level, the European Asylum Support Office (EASO) was also created (Ibid., 2018).

The **Qualification Directive**¹⁶ of 2011 amended Council Directive 2004/83/EC of 29 April 2004 on minimum standards for the qualification and status of third-country nationals or stateless persons as refugees or as persons who otherwise need international protection and the content of the protection granted. It establishes common grounds for granting international protection and foresees a series of rights for its beneficiaries (residence permits, travel documents, access to employment and education, social welfare and healthcare).

The **Asylum Procedures Directive**¹⁷ establishes common standards of safeguards and guarantees for a fair and efficient asylum procedure. **The revised Asylum Procedures Directive** aims at fairer, quicker and better-quality asylum decisions. Asylum seekers with special needs will receive the necessary support to explain their claim and, in particular, there will be greater protection of unaccompanied minors and victims of torture. This directive sets common procedures for granting and withdrawing international protection.

The **Temporary Protection Directive**¹⁸ 20/07/2001 - Council Directive 2001/55/EC of 20 July 2001 sets minimum standards for giving **temporary protection** in the event of a mass influx of displaced persons and measures promoting a balance of efforts between Member States in receiving such persons and bearing the consequences thereof.

Last but not least, the Council of Europe Convention for the Protection of Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms (**European Convention on Human Rights-ECHR**) does not provide the right to asylum. However, a number of articles may constitute barriers to removing an asylum seeker from the territory of a signatory party. Article 3 enshrines the prohibition of torture or inhuman or degrading treatment or punishment; in other words, the principle of non-refoulement. In addition, the expulsion of persons denied asylum may also raise issues under Article 2 (right to life), Article 5 (right to liberty and security of the person), Article 6 (right to a fair trial), Article 8 (right to respect for family and private life), Article 4 of Protocol No. 4 (collective expulsion of aliens) and Article 13 (right to an effective remedy)¹⁹.

2.1.3. The Incorporation of the International and European Legal Framework in RESPOND Countries

All RESPOND countries examined in this report²⁰, **except Iraq and Lebanon**, have signed the 1951 **Geneva Convention** and its additional protocols, although **Turkey** has retained a geographic limitation to its ratification. More specifically, Turkey recognizes the Convention's refugee status only for those fleeing as a consequence of "events occurring in Europe".

The countries which have not ratified the 1951 Geneva Convention are bound by **other international or regional agreements and treaties** which refer to human and refugee rights. More specifically, **Iraq** has signed the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, the International Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Racial Discrimination (14/1/1970), the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (25/1/1971), the International

¹⁶ Directive 2011/95/EU of 13 December 2011 on standards for the qualification of third-country nationals or stateless persons as beneficiaries of international protection, for a uniform status for refugees or for persons eligible for subsidiary protection, and for the content of the protection granted. Ireland did not participate in Directive 2004/83/EC and is not bound by the recast Directive.

¹⁷ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32013L0032&from=en>

¹⁸ Council Directive 2001/55/EC of 20 July 2001 on minimum standards for giving temporary protection in the event of a mass influx of displaced persons and on measures promoting a balance of efforts between Member States in receiving such persons and bearing the consequences thereof.

¹⁹ https://www.echr.coe.int/Documents/COURTalks_Asyl_Talk_ENG.PDF

²⁰ Austria, Germany, Greece, Iraq, Italy, Lebanon, Poland, Sweden, Turkey, and United Kingdom.

Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (25/1/1971), the Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women (13/8/1986), the Convention on the Rights of the Child (15/6/1994), the Optional Protocol to the Convention on the Rights of the Child on the involvement of children in armed conflict (24/6/2008), the Convention against Torture and Other Cruel, Inhuman or Degrading Treatment or Punishment (7/7/2011) and the Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (20/3/2013). Iraq has also ratified the Arab Charter on Human Rights and is a member of the OIC that issued the Ashgabat Declaration (Warda and Almaffraji, 2020). **Lebanon** has signed the 1948 Universal Declaration of Human Rights and ratified in 1972 the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights as well as the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights. Lebanon is also bound by the provisions of the Convention Against Torture and Other Cruel, Inhuman or Degrading Treatment or Punishment, ratified in 2000, as well as its optional Protocol, ratified later on in 2008 (Rahme, 2020).

Furthermore, **all EU RESPOND countries** are bound by the EU *acquis* aimed at the creation of a **CEAS**, except **the UK**. The UK has adapted its system to some of the instruments of CEAS, which aimed to define minimum EU-wide standards for asylum qualification, reception, and procedures. However, making use of its right to opt-out of its provisions, the UK has implemented the first round of the CEAS directives but not the second. Furthermore, in light of Brexit on 31 January 2020 and the following transition period, many uncertainties appear for the country in terms of the CEAS.

Additionally, **most RESPOND countries** have incorporated the **European Convention on Human Rights** and its principle of protection against torture or inhuman or degrading treatments (art. 3 ECHR) into their legal framework. The principle of asylum is explicitly entrenched, to different degrees, only in the constitutions of **Italy, Germany, Poland, and Iraq**. The detailed table of the Legal Framework in RESPOND Countries is provided with the WP1 comparative report (Pannia et al., 2018, p. 22).

3. Comparative Findings from the National Reports

3.1. Policy Responses and Important Changes since 2011

The RESPOND Project focuses on the 2011-2018 time period. As the field works in the consortium countries were completed in 2019 and country reports on protection were published at the first quarter of 2020, this part of the report extends until 2020. Within this period, 2015-16 appears as the critical juncture, when major legal and institutional changes started to occur in many of the RESPOND countries as a response to the so-called European Refugee Crisis.

Drawing from reports of ten countries, it is possible to summarise the main patterns in the international protection regime as follows: Since 2015-16, many countries have introduced **more centralised asylum systems and more restrictive policies to decrease the number of entries and asylum applications and increase the number of deportations and returns**. There has been an increase in **anti-immigrant narratives and negative representations of refugee arrivals**, even in some of the most welcoming countries such as Sweden, which has been known to have a relatively open migration and integration policy based on equal rights. With the exception of Turkey, all reports mention a **perception and usage of “crisis” or “state of emergency”** (e.g. Germany, Greece, Lebanon, Italy and Poland). **Restricted access to national/federal territory** and, thus, to the asylum procedure is the case in many countries such as Poland, Lebanon, Turkey, Greece and Austria, where new physical and procedural barriers have been introduced. Almost all countries tended to **downgrade the rights of applicants and beneficiaries of protection**. In general, all newly introduced amendments or new regulations bring **new restrictions or limitations to existing standards of rights**. The rule of law is seen as a hindrance and obstacle. Secondary law has become more restrictive and some new provisions and practices have clashed with constitutionally provided individual rights or international human rights. **Temporary Protection measures** have become more relevant through the extension of their coverage. Its usage limits the possibility for residence permits and family reunification, such as observed in Sweden, Italy and Germany. As a non-EU country, Turkey adopted a temporary protection scheme to shape its response to Syrian mass migration.

From 2015 onwards, almost all **countries face pressure and the lack of administrative capacity to process the increasing number of applications**. In response, **accelerated procedures, fast-track-procedures and increased rejections, along with long waiting periods for the applicants, have become common patterns**. For EU members, this leads to the different implementation within the national territories, while the deficiencies of the CEAS have become more visible. Therefore, the existing practices in the countries under consideration **range from generous/welcoming/humanitarian approaches to the so-called minimum EU-level standards or even lower**, with highly securitized approaches. The **Hotspot** approach has led to rights violations rather than solutions, and **pushbacks** at the borders have become normalised. The updating of the list of third safe countries has resulted in the justification of deportations and returns and blurred the line between forced and voluntary returns. Bilateral or EU-level readmission agreements and administrative arrangements have intensified since 2011 and even more so since 2015. In all countries, civil society movements act as “safety valves” and criticize the ongoing issues.

The aforementioned general patterns take a different legal, institutional, policy and practice form in each country. The following paragraphs underline the most important policy developments at the country level.

In **Austria**, the national asylum institution was introduced as the first instance authority in 2014, and the previously decentralised and fragmented structure became more centralized (Josipovic and Reeger, 2019, p. 17). As echoing the previously mentioned commonalities, admissibility and fast-track procedures became common in the Austrian asylum regime.

Similarly, the concepts of 'safe country of origin' and 'third safe country' were mainly used for the justification of returns according to the Dublin Procedure. A unilateral quota was imposed on the annual admission of persons to the asylum procedure in 2016 to avoid the increase in application numbers (Ibid., p. 19). However, it has only been legally coded as a possibility if certain criteria (certain number of annual asylum applications, border controls effective) are fulfilled and if an according ordinance is passed. The quota has never become effective, as asylum applications steeply declined after 2015. Aligned with yet another common tendency, Austria began to implement the EU Qualification Directive at the minimum level and adopted more restrictive national measures, such as the launching of further restrictions on family reunifications (Ibid., p. 20). The possibility to apply for the revision of decisions before the Administrative High Court is a positive development during the given period. There have been critical voices, in particular by NGOs, against deportation and return policies targeting Afghan migrants in particular (Ibid., p. 17). The centralisation of the system has also been heavily criticized by non-state actors, who point out that the body deciding on individual cases might at the same time be providing legal advice and address that the number of errors in first-instance decisions is extremely high.

Germany's asylum regime has mobilised the application of the concepts of 'safe third country' or 'safe country of origin', accelerated asylum procedures and introduced a separate social welfare regime for asylum seekers, in addition to reinforcing border controls (Hänsel et al., 2020, p. 13). Up to 2014, Germany displayed a more generous response and applied an extended interpretation of the EU *acquis*, such as the Qualification Directive or the implementation of the subsidiary protection status in 2013. However, the steady rise in application numbers led to restrictions (Ibid., 15). To address the issue of potential source countries, the list of safe countries of origin was extended (2014), and several amendments allowing for a more restrictive and effective implementation of accelerated procedures (in 2015 by the Act on the Acceleration of Asylum and even further, in 2016 by the Asylum Package II) were introduced; a ban of entry from safe countries of origin (in 2015 by the Act to Redefine the Right to Stay and the Termination of Residence) was adopted; and deportation and return practices were supported and widely implemented (in 2019, by the Migration Package).

Poland, as other countries, updated its list of 'safe countries of origin' and 'safe third countries' and changed the appeal body in asylum procedures in 2017 (Pachocka and Sobczak-Szelc, 2020, p. 32). In the same year, it established the Migration Crisis Response Mechanism that aims at providing support to EU countries experiencing the highest influx of asylum seekers, addressing root causes in regions of origin and improvement the exchange of information between different countries and institutions (Ibid., p. 33). In 2019, it started to work on a revised proposal for amending the Law on Protection, including the introduction of a border procedure and a further updating of the list of safe countries of origin and safe third countries (Ibid.).

In **Sweden**, too, there have been major shifts in the Swedish Protection System since 2015. Compared to other RESPOND countries in the EU, Sweden has been known to have relatively open migration and integration policies based on equal rights; however, after 2015 there have been efforts to reduce the number of asylum seekers and refugees, in particular with the 2016 Temporary Act (Shakra and Szalanska, 2020, p. 9). The Temporary Act refers to the Act where the Swedish government presented restrictive measures as an attempt to reduce the number of asylum seekers coming to Sweden, which passed in 2016 (Ibid.). Furthermore, Sweden adopted the minimum level under EU and international law regarding asylum and family-migration issues (Ibid.). The report states that the two poles regarding asylum policies became more visible in 2019 and the far right seems to have attained its best results by supporting a restrictive approach towards refugee protection. Even immigration-friendly parties such as the Red-Green Coalition have steered more towards the Social Democrats, contradicting "Swedish exceptionalism" by imposing restrictions during 2015, such as the introduction of border controls or the exclusive granting of temporary protection (Ibid.).

Greece has undergone significant developments in its national asylum procedures. An Asylum Service and a First Reception Service were established (Law 3907/2011) in parallel to the Directive 2008/115/EC of the EU in 2011 (Leivaditi et. al., 2020, p. 15). The Syrian civil war

and similar conditions in other countries led to a high number of entries and asylum applications in Greece. Following the closure of the so-called Western Balkans Corridor and the 2016 EU-Turkey Statement, Greece adopted a national law (Law 4375/2016) that introduced a considerable number of changes in the legal framework, first reception and asylum procedures and the management of refugee flows, leading to a greater involvement of the European Asylum Support Office (EASO) and the European Border and Coast Guard Agency (Frontex) (Ibid.). New regulations such as 'exceptional', 'fast-track border' and 'accelerated' procedures were subsequently introduced. Also, similar to Austria and Germany, the country applied the concept of 'safe third country', the centralisation of the application and registration process and a high number of detentions and returns. After the EU-Turkey Statement and the geographical restriction on the five North-eastern Aegean islands due to the Hotspot approach, asylum applications increased significantly in the country. Additionally, a wide range of conservative measures on refugee issues have been announced such as future plans for a stricter securitization of the Greek borders, the conversion of camps to "closed centres", etc (Ibid., p. 16).

Italy reorganized its national asylum system according to the EU Directives (2013/33/EU and 2013/32/EU) in 2015. In 2017, the appeal system was updated, and one level of appeal within the international protection system was removed and a specialized court division was introduced (Ibrido and Terlizzi, 2019, p.20). In line with the common tendency among EU members to limit rights, the controversial so-called "Salvini Decree Law No. 113/2018" turned into Law No. 132/2018 and abolished the humanitarian protection regime in 2018. Also, new regulations have broadened the range of criminal offenses which justify the revocation of international protection and introduce measures to reduce new arrivals and contain irregular immigration (Ibid.).

The UK displays a hostile approach, imposing restrictions on immigration and asylum since 2010. Its **international protection regime has been driven by** practical and ideological pressures, along with the growth of external migration, domestic political conflict and legal challenges (Foley, 2020, p. 14). International protection has also been affected by austerity policies which had an impact on refugees and asylum seekers, in particular regarding access to services. The UK's response to Syrian mass migration prioritizes externalization through humanitarian relief and geopolitical interventions in the country of origin rather than the adoption of resettlement programmes. As of 2014, the UK has been working on new programmes and amendments regarding vulnerabilities, in particular unaccompanied minors. Unlike the other EU countries studied in this project, the UK resisted Europe-wide relocation programmes, claiming that they encourage Syrian refugees to make dangerous journeys to Europe. Despite negative developments regarding refugee protection, the temporary suspension in 2018 of the Detained Fast Track can be seen as a positive step towards a rights-based approach. However, a new asylum processing system for those already in detention was immediately put in place (Ibid.). At this stage, due to the unstable policy environment created in the aftermath of "Brexit" (the UK left the EU on 31 January 2020, after the publication of the UK report) it is unclear how the transition period might affect refugee protection in the country.

Apart from the EU countries, three non-European countries of the RESPOND Project (Turkey, Lebanon and Iraq) have become important hosting countries. In 2011, **Turkey** first responded to Syrian mass migration with an open-door policy, while a major transformation of the national asylum system was already underway. Turkey's national law on migration and asylum came into force with significant institutional changes in 2013. As a response to the mass arrival of Syrian refugees since 2011, Turkey applied temporary protection and legalized it with the Temporary Protection Regulation (TPR) adopted in 2014 (Gökalp Aras and Şahin Mencütek, p. 17). As other countries, it favoured a centralized protection regime. Even the role of the UNHCR, due to the geographical limitation of the 1951 Convention, was limited in 2018. On 10 September 2018, the parallel Refugee Status Determination (RSD) procedure (also registration) conducted by UNHCR and Turkey came to an end, and the entire procedure of RSD was placed under the national migration and asylum authority. The country has derogated from the principle of non-refoulement with the claim of protecting public order and security

(Ibid., p. 19). The deportation provisions were also amended with the Emergency Decree of October 2016 and then consolidated (by Law No 7070) on 1 February 2018, reflecting the wide-range securitization taking place in the aftermath of the 2016 attempted coup d'état (Ibid.). Despite a flexible approach of provincial authorities towards the internal mobility of Syrians, this approach changed in 2019 to strengthen internal controls (Ibid., 20). In the same year, also following cross-border military operations, the emphasis on the return of Syrians became more visible in the country. The EU-Turkey Readmission Agreement was suspended in 2019, while the EU-Turkey Statement (2016) appears to still be in force, with significant implications for international protection.

Lebanon has long been a host country for forced migrants. Until 2014, it adopted a “laissez faire” approach towards Syrian mass migration (Rahme, 2020, p. 13). However, in line with the majority of the RESPOND countries, Lebanon too started to adopt stricter policies to halt increasing numbers. New restrictive policies were introduced, violating the open-door policy dictated by bilateral agreements between Lebanon and Syria and introducing new visa categories (Ibid.). The report highlights the limited possibilities of complying with the current entry and renewal requirements, the concurrent deprivation of fundamental rights, the lack of legal redress and exposure to different kinds of exploitation as causes for concern regarding the developments in the post-2011 period (Ibid, p.27). As Lebanon is not party of Convention, but hosting the largest number of refugees per capita, the UNHCR had to play a central role in responding Syrian mass migration by referring its international protection mandate. The UNHCR have carried out functions of registering and provision of humanitarian assistance to of refugees. However, the Lebanese state’s policy goal of decreasing the number of Syrians in the country since 2015 through limiting to access territory and encouraging returns influenced the work of UNHCR, in practice lack of holding any legal status by Syrians and precarity (Janmyr 2016, 2018; Sahin-Mencutek 2018).

Iraq is not a signatory party to the 1951 Convention; however, the country is a member of the Organization of Islamic Cooperation (OIC), which adopted the Ashgabat Declaration (2012). The latter can be seen as an important response after 2011, for the signatories – including Iraq – expressed their deep concern about the condition of refugees in the world, especially the fact that most are hosted by OIC member states; the declaration also recognizes the importance of the Convention (Warda and Almajraji, 2020, p. 12). Although the Convention (1951) remains unsigned, the League of Arab States, of which Iraq is a member, also signed a memorandum of understanding with the UNHCR in October 2016, to respond to the needs of refugees in the Arab region and facilitate the arrival of humanitarian assistance and humanitarian response in emergency cases (Ibid., p. 13). UNHCR Iraq closely cooperated, both with the Central Iraqi Government and the Kurdistan Region of Iraq to management of refugees, including support to the pertinent ministries, provision of humanitarian assistance and caring of camp residents who are given asylum certificates (Yassen 2019).

Drawing from the national reports, the following table provides a summary of commonalities after 2011 and in particular 2015.

Table 1 Policies, Mechanisms and Instruments in Refugee Protection since 2011

POLICY	LEVEL	MECHANISMS	INSTRUMENTS
To reduce the number of asylum seekers reaching the territory	National/International/ EU level	Deterring	Border measures (security walls, fences etc. (Turkey, Greece), Usage of force at borders (Poland); Border procedures (short lodging times) (Italy); Restrictive visas (Lebanon); Supranational actors (FRONTEX)
		Returning (at the borders)	Push backs by the frontline states (Poland, Greece, Turkey, Italy)
To reduce number of people applying for asylum	National/ EU Level	Deterring through complexification	Creating complex labelling and legal statuses; Bureaucratic hurdles; Incomprehensive asylum procedures;
		Shifting/Returning	Generally: Implementing admissibility criteria, readmission (safe country of origin, safe third country updated lists) Particularly: detained fast track (UK), transit zones/hotspot approach (Greece; Italy); fast-track border procedure (Greece); airport procedure (Germany); immediate procedure (Italy); Updated safe regions (in particular Syria) (Sweden), Incentives for voluntary returns or forced returns in voluntary return's clothing (Sweden, Turkey)
To prevent asylum shopping (moving of asylum seekers from one country to another)	National	Deterring	Dublin Regulation, first country of asylum, safe country of asylum
	EU level	Cooperation (Harmonization of policies and procedures)	EASO
To distinguish desirable and undesirable migrants/refugees	National/International/ EU Level	Pre-selecting nationalities, different procedures for different nationalities	Bilateral/administrative agreements (Greece, Germany, Italy), registration and RSD process, vulnerability
To accelerate asylum assessments	National	Massification	Mass accommodation (Germany)
		Pre-selecting on recognition rates	Fast track (Germany); Sweden
		Discursive measures	'deserving protection', 'vulnerability' (all)
To prevent permanent stay of refugees	National	Limiting/downgrading rights	Limiting family reunifications, shortening residence permit durations, no freedom of movement, limiting access to basic social benefits
		Return policies	
		Extending temporary measures	Subsidiary protection, Temporary protection status
To share responsibility/burden	EU Level	Policy sharing: Common policy making and Harmonisations	The EU Acquis related to refugee protection, EASO Qualification Directives (2011), Asylum Directive (2013)
	EU Level	Refugee sharing	Quotas, resettlement, relocation scheme
	EU and non-EU	Financial sharing	Aid packages, bilateral agreements (EU-Turkey, EU-Lebanon; UNHCR involvement)
	Global/ UN	Burden sharing, collective response to mass migration	The Global Compact on Refugees (2018)

Source: Authors' own elaboration on country reports

3.2. Macro-Level Analysis: Legal and Institutional Framework

3.2.1. Definitions and Forms of Protection in RESPOND Countries

3.2.1.1. International Protection (Refugee Status and Subsidiary Protection)

International protection, a predominantly legal concept entailing important legal entitlements for individuals and obligations for states, is underpinned by complex definitions under international law. The stricter definition of international protection refers to refugee status and subsidiary protection statuses granted by the Geneva Convention of 1951 and EU Law as well as temporary protection (Ibrido and Terlizzi, 2019, p.11). These three statuses are known as EU-harmonized protection statuses as they are coordinated by the Qualification and Temporary Protection Directives (EMN, 2019, p.1).

The European Union has a two-tier protection regime (ECRE, 2016). The 2004 Qualification Directive, harmonizing recognition standards across Member States; and its 2011 recast, which extends beyond the remit of the Refugee Convention by setting out two forms of protection available under EU law: the refugee status, for persons qualifying as refugees under the Convention definition, and subsidiary protection, for those who do not meet the criteria for refugeehood but face serious harm due to certain human rights violations in their country of origin. Through this dual form of protection, the EU creates a complementary category of protected persons, legally and normatively distinct from refugees (AIDA, 2016b). This fact has been criticized for breaking away from EU commitment to provide a uniform asylum status throughout the EU, on one hand, and from other regional approaches that have extended the refugee definition, on the other (AIDA, 2016b).

It has also been argued that this two-tier approach to protection is based on the false assumption that subsidiary protection status addresses shorter-term protection needs compared to the refugee status (Ibid.). Additionally, extensive reforms across several Member States have lowered the level of rights conferred upon subsidiary protection holders compared to refugee status holders, often as far as EU law would allow (Ibid.). As such, different determination can be found across MSs as to who needs international protection, what form of protection is needed and what rights should be attached thereto; furthermore, significant differences exist in the treatment of refugees and subsidiary protection beneficiaries, creating severe inequalities at multiple levels which impact on the lives of beneficiaries (Ibid.).

The term “asylum seeker” refers to an individual who is seeking international protection. In countries with individualized procedures, an asylum seeker is someone whose claim has not been finally decided on by the country in which he or she has submitted it. Not every asylum seeker will ultimately be recognized as a refugee, but every recognized refugee is initially an asylum seeker (IOM, 2019, p. 12).

Refugee Status

The core of international protection concerns those who have refugee status under the 1951 Geneva Convention and the Qualification Directive which reformulated article 1 of the Convention: “someone who is unable or unwilling to return to their country of origin owing to a well-founded fear of being persecuted for reasons of race, religion, nationality, membership of a particular social group, or political opinion” (UNHCR n.d, 2011, p. 3). The 1969 Organization of African Union Convention expanded the definition by including those “fleeing events seriously disturbing the public order” (OAU, 1969). Similarly, the 1984 Cartagena Declaration embraced a wider refugee definition by covering those fleeing generalized violence, foreign

aggression, internal conflicts, massive violation of human rights or other circumstances which have seriously disturbed public order' in Latin America, Mexico, and Panama (Cartagena Declaration, 1984).

The EU embraced the concept of refugee as defined by the 1951 Refugee Convention. The refugee status was included in the Qualification Directive of 2004/83/EC of the 29th of April 2004 and its recast of 2011, Qualification Directive 2011/95/EU. The Directive defines "standards for the qualification of third-country nationals or stateless persons as beneficiaries of international protection, for a uniform status for refugees or persons eligible for subsidiary protection and for the content of the protection granted (recast) (Council Directive 2011/95/EU). In this way, the Qualification Directive sets out criteria for applicants to qualify for refugee status or subsidiary protection and foresees a series of rights for its beneficiaries (residence permits, travel documents, access to employment and education, social welfare and healthcare). Member states transposed the Qualification Directive by integrating it into their national law between 2013 and 2016 by adopting presidential decrees (e.g. **Greece**, no. 141/21-10-2013), legislative decrees (e.g. **Italy**, no. 142/2015) or by extending their asylum law (e.g. **Germany**).

Some MSs embrace the need to protect against persecution perpetrated by state bodies, while others consider the inability of a state to ensure protection regardless of the source, public or private, of the persecution, to be enough. Article 6 clearly states that the perpetrators of the persecution (or serious harm for the purposes of subsidiary protection) may be, in addition to the state, "political parties or organizations controlling the state or a substantial part of its territory", as well as non-state entities if it can be demonstrated that the state or other entities who control the territory, including international organizations, are unable or unwilling to provide adequate protection (Favilli, 2018).

In identifying acts of persecution and reasons for persecution, the Directive has substantially reproduced the provisions of the Geneva Convention with some slight variations. Over the years, some states, spurred on by UNHCR guidelines, have interpreted these provisions in their broadest sense to ensure protection against persecution on the grounds of gender, sexual orientation and age, in particular through the broad interpretation of the concept of "social group". Thus, article 9 qualifies as persecution "acts specifically directed against one gender or against children". In addition, article 10 expressly provides that "social group" could mean a group founded on the common characteristic of sexual orientation. It also states that gender-related aspects might be considered, "although they do not constitute in themselves a presumption of the applicability of this article" (Ibid.).

In countries under consideration, the overview of the refugee statutes is as following:

In **Germany**, refugee protection based on the 1951 Refugee Convention is the most frequently applied for protection status. Its content is broader than the notion of individual political asylum laid down by the German Constitution, and also applies to persecution by non-state actors and for gender-specific reasons (Hänsel et al., 2020).

In **Austria**, asylum is granted to persons who, for well-founded fear of being persecuted, are outside their country of origin and cannot claim protection there. While political opinions represent the most common reason for persecution, other aspects such as belonging to a religious minority or changing inner convictions (conversion), which cannot be freely expressed, might present a well-founded reason of persecution. Additionally, subjective post-flight reasons for asylum in general (but also objective ones) are acknowledged, such as the example of the "social group" of women with a "western orientation" (Josipovic and Reeger, 2019).

As regards **Sweden**, the right to refugee status does not depend on whether the fear of persecution comes from the state or if the state, other parties or organizations controlling the territory fail to provide effective and not temporary protection to that person (Shakra et al., 2018).

In **Poland**, according to article 13 of the Law on Protection, to obtain refugee status, the foreigner must experience a justified fear of persecution in the country of origin due to race, religion, nationality or political beliefs or belonging to a particular social group, and must be unable or unwilling to benefit from the protection provided by the country of origin. The nature of the persecution must constitute a serious threat to human rights (Pachocka and Sobczak-Szelc, 2020).

In **Greece**, refugee protection is based on the 1951 Geneva Convention and on EU legislation on the CEAS. Refugee status is granted to a third-country national or a stateless person who meets the criteria established by Presidential Decree 141/2013. (see Petracou et al. 2018, p. 47; Leivaditi et al., 2020, p. 21).

In **Italy**, there are three different dimensions of the concept of protection: the constitutional dimension, the international and supranational dimension and the domestic legislative dimension (Ibrido and Terlizzi, 2019, p. 9). The international and supranational dimension is linked to the Geneva Convention of 1951, as well as to EU Law (inter alia, Art. 18 of the Charter of Fundamental Rights and Directive 2004/83/EC) (Ibid., 18).

In the **UK**, the refugee status is determined by applying Article 1A (2) of the Geneva Convention (1951), interpreted according to the EU Qualification Directive (Foley, 2020).

Turkey, having the geographical limitation clause, grants refugee status only to people originating from Europe, as a result of events occurring in European countries (The Law on Foreigners and International Protection/ LFIP, Article 61.1). For persons not originating from European Countries, Turkey grants the so-called conditional refugee status (Gökalp Aras and Şahin Mencütek, 2020).

The Rights of the Beneficiaries of Refugee Status

The recast Qualification Directive sets minimum rules on the duration of residence permits for refugee status which require permits of at least three years. Additionally, beneficiaries of refugee status should receive travel documents as well as enjoy the right to access to the labour market and to move freely across the national territory.

The refugee status in **Germany** provides the same rights as the asylum status: a three-year residence permit, the possibility of a settlement permit after three or five years if other preconditions are met, as well as unrestricted access to the labour market and the entitlement to privileged family reunification (Hänsel et al., 2020). The Integration Act of 31 July 2016 that came into force on 6 August 2016 contains, among other things, restrictions on freedom of movement and residence requirements for recognized refugees (Ibid.). Since then, Germany requires refugees to take up their place of residence within the federal state in which their asylum procedure has been conducted. The obligation to live in a certain place remains in force for three years, but it can be lifted for certain reasons (e.g. for family-related reasons or for education and employment purposes) (AIDA, 2016b).

In **Austria**, upon the granting of asylum, recognized refugees receive a Convention Passport which entitles them to residence and entry for three years. Furthermore, they receive a blue identification card for the duration of their initial temporary residence (Josipovic and Reeger, 2019). As of 2016, asylum is granted for a period initially limited to three years. The residence

permit can subsequently be renewed for an indefinite period of validity if there are no conditions that require the initiation of a procedure to withdraw the asylum status (Ibid.). Austria has also considered the possibility of applying residence restrictions to beneficiaries of international protection to prevent a trend of beneficiaries settling in Vienna after obtaining their status (AIDA, 2016b). Another development in the Austrian asylum procedures is that the Basic Welfare Support has been discontinued, and holders of asylum are transferred to the general social aid system; the latter has a Needs-Based Minimum Benefit at its core, which falls entirely under the competence of the federal provinces (Josipovic and Reeger, 2019). However, it should be noted that the Basic Welfare Support is a social service for asylum seekers. The Needs-Based Minimum Benefit (now termed Social Aid) is much higher and applies to beneficiaries of protection. In the case of the latter there have been attempts to cut it but they were overturned by high courts.

In **Poland**, foreigners granted refugee status have access to the labour market on the same basis as Polish citizens; social assistance on equal terms as Polish citizens; individual integration programs; health care financed by the state; housing sponsored by the state; public education (compulsory for children); professional training financed by the state through programs of professional development; family reunification (Pachocka and Sobczak-Szelc, 2020).

In **Greece**, the Constitution guarantees the rights of all person living within the territory with a series of articles such as “respect and protection of the value of the human being” (art. 2); “full protection of their life, honour and liberty irrespective of nationality, race or language and of religious or political beliefs” for all persons living within Greek territory (art. 5, par. 2) and inviolability of personal liberty (art. 5, paragraph 3) (Articles 2,5,7,20) (Leivaditi et al., 2020, p. 17).

In **Italy**, the refugee status ensures a residence permit of five years, renewable if the reason for its issuance persists. The holders of residence permits are entitled to various civil and social rights on equal terms as Italian citizens, in particular access to the national health service and the education system. Moreover, the National System for the Protection for Asylum Seekers and Refugees (SPRAR), offers beneficiaries access to vocational training, language courses and job placement services (Ibrido and Terlizzi, 2019).

Subsidiary Protection

Subsidiary Protection was established according to the Qualification Directive 2011/95/EU and is a form of international protection for persons seeking asylum who do not qualify as refugees. The EC defines it as:

The protection given to a non-EU national or a stateless person who does not qualify as a refugee, but in respect of whom substantial grounds have been shown to believe that the person concerned, if returned to his or her country of origin or, in the case of a stateless person, to his or her country of former habitual residence, would face a real risk of suffering serious harm and who is unable or, owing to such risk, unwilling to avail himself or herself of the protection of that country (EC Glossary, 2020)²¹.

Articles 2 and 3 of the European Convention on Human Rights are used as reference for the granting of subsidiary protection. This means that the asylum applicant has to prove that she or he will be in “real risk of suffering serious harm” from the government or non-governmental

²¹ See Council Directive 2004/83/EC of 29 April 2004 on minimum standards for the qualification and status of third country nationals or stateless persons as refugees or as persons who otherwise need international protection and the content of the protection granted

actors if return to his/her country of origin. The term “serious harm” also includes those situations in which a person has the right to receive protection to prevent the denial of a right recognized in international conventions on refugees other than that of Geneva (Favilli, 2018). Even though MSs are all bound by both the Geneva Convention and the ECHR, there is great divergence in the rights guaranteed to beneficiaries of international protection (Ibid.).

Some countries are more eager to grant subsidiary protection so as to escape granting refugee status and avoid the obligation of family reunification.

In **Germany**, the rights connected to subsidiary protection status are much more limited than those coming with asylum or refugee status. For example, the residence permit is only valid for one year (with the possibility of extension) and a settlement permit is possible to receive after five years provided as well as unrestricted access to the labour market is provided, but not the entitlement to privileged family reunification (Hänsel et al., 2020, p. 22). The asylum applicant has to prove that he/she faces serious harm in their country of origin from the government or non-governmental actors. “Serious harm” is defined as the imposition or enforcement of the death penalty, torture, inhuman or degrading treatment or punishment, or a serious individual threat to the life or integrity of a civilian as a result of arbitrary force within an international or domestic armed conflict (Hänsel et al., 2020). Since 2016, **Germany** grants subsidiary protection to half of the Syrian applicants (Hänsel et al., 2020, p.37).

In **Austria**, subsidiary protection is granted in cases where a person faces torture, inhuman punishment or degrading treatment, if his/her right to life is endangered, or in case of serious danger to life and limb in conflict situations, for example during civil wars (Josipovic and Reeger, 2019). This holds true for all EU countries, as it is provided for by the Directive, thus it is the same for the other RESPOND EU member countries. **Austria** is more likely to grant subsidiary protection to unaccompanied minors with growing chances from 2015 until 2017 (Josipovic and Reeger, 2019, p.44.). However, the report also states that the acceptance rates for asylum status are considerably lower and oscillate around 40 per cent in the years under consideration (Ibid.).

Sweden granted subsidiary protection to the majority of Syrian applicants (Shakra and Szalanska, 2020, p.62). The Swedish interpretation and application of subsidiary status is in line with the EU framework.

In **Poland**, asylum seekers deemed not deserving of refugee status but still seen as facing a real risk of being seriously harmed if they are returned to their country of origin are granted subsidiary protection (article 15 of the Law on Protection). The risks are taken into account when deciding about this form of protection include the possibility of being executed or sentenced to capital punishment, tortured or treated in an inhumane way, or experiencing a serious individual threat to life and health due to international or internal military conflicts in which civilians are attacked in the country of origin (Pachocka and Sobczak-Szelc, 2020).

In **Greece**, the Qualification Directive sets out criteria for applicants to qualify for refugee status or subsidiary protection and foresees a series of rights for its beneficiaries (residence permits, travel documents, access to employment and education, social welfare and healthcare). In Greece, the Qualification Directive was transposed into Greek legislation through Presidential Decree 141/21-10-2013 (Leivaditi et al., 2020, p.17).

In **Italy**, subsidiary protection is a form of protection that can be granted to people seeking protection when they cannot prove a risk of personal persecution but only one of serious physical harm in the country of origin such as torture, death penalty, etc. (Ibrido and Terlizzi, 2019, p. 19).

In the **UK**, the CEAS introduced requirements for subsidiary protection provisions for those people that fail to meet the refugee criteria as defined in the 1951 Refugee Convention. Subsidiary protection provisions of the Qualification Directive have been transposed into UK law and the category of “Humanitarian Protection” replaced the earlier policy of Exceptional Leave to Remain (Foley, 2020).

In **Turkey**, persons who do not fulfil the eligibility criteria for either refugee status or conditional refugee status but who would be subjected to the death penalty or torture in their country of origin if returned, or who would be at “individualized risk of indiscriminate violence” due to situations of war or internal armed conflict, qualify for “subsidiary protection status” under article 63(1) of LFIP (Gökalp Aras and Sahin Mencütek, 2020).

The Rights of the Beneficiaries of Subsidiary Protections

The rights provided by the subsidiary protection status are much more limited than those of the refugee status. 21 out of 28 EU Member States have followed a two-tier approach concerning residence permits – often limited to one year – and grant less security of residence to persons benefitting from subsidiary protection (AIDA, 2016b). As regards travel documents, beneficiaries of subsidiary protection are issued documents of shorter validity, with the exception of some countries (**Austria, Greece, and Italy**). Additionally, there are also differences in accessing the labour market and moving freely across the national territory between the beneficiaries of these statuses.

Germany provides more limited rights to the holders of the subsidiary protection status compared to beneficiaries of the refugee status. The residence permit for beneficiaries of subsidiary protection is only valid for one year (if extended, for two more years in each case) potentially followed by a settlement permit after five years if specific preconditions are met. Unrestricted access to the labour market is provided but not the entitlement to privileged family reunification (Hänsel et al., 2020). Beneficiaries of subsidiary protection must fix their place of residence in a specific municipality within the Federal State (AIDA, 2016b).

In **Austria**, holders of subsidiary protection are entitled to a temporary residence of one year and are issued a Grey Card for Persons Eligible for Subsidiary Protection (Josipovic and Reeger, 2019). The one-year residence permit might receive a two-year extension (Ibid.). In Austria, beneficiaries of subsidiary protection can bring their family members to Austria after three years (while recognized refugees can do so within the first three months upon acquiring a permit) (Ibid.). Additionally, Austria, like Germany, also considered the possibility of applying residence restrictions on beneficiaries of subsidiary protection. The access of beneficiaries of subsidiary protection to social assistance benefits varies compared to those granted to refugees in most federal provinces. Social support under the needs-based minimum benefit system granted to refugees is not available to subsidiary protection holders in Burgenland, Salzburg Styria and, as of April 2016, Lower Austria (AIDA, 2016b).

In **Sweden**, beneficiaries of subsidiary protection get 13 months of residence permit (Shakra et al., 2018). In 2016, new measures were proposed in Sweden, aimed, among other things, at levelling down the rights of beneficiaries of subsidiary protection. These measures were heralded by the Swedish government as a means “to temporarily adjust the asylum regulations to the minimum level in the EU so that more people choose to seek asylum in other EU countries” (Pannia et al., 2018). In Sweden, the holders of refugee status have the right to be reunited with their nuclear family, while those having subsidiary protection status have very limited possibilities for family reunification.

In **Poland**, foreigners granted subsidiary protection have access to the labour market on the same basis as Polish citizens; social assistance on equal terms as Polish citizens; individual

integration programs; health care financed by the state; housing sponsored by the state; public education (compulsory for children); professional training financed by the state, within programs of professional development; family reunion (Pachocka and Sobczak-Szelc, 2020). In **Greece**, the granting of subsidiary protection status used to be almost similar with refugee protection (a new law was passed in November 2019 and has been in effect since 1 January 2020, amended in April 2020). It provided a three-year residence permit, access to education, welfare benefits, health services, the right to apply for work and the right to apply for travel document. However, persons with subsidiary protection did not have the right to family reunification and 7 years of continuous and legal residence were required in order to apply for Greek citizenship.

In **Italy**, the rights connected to the refugee status and to subsidiary protection are similar: a five-year residence permit that can be renewed if the reason for its issuance persists. The residence permit entitles the holder to various civil and social rights on equal terms as Italian citizens, and in particular to access to the National Health Service and the education system (Ibrido and Terlizzi, 2019).

3.2.1.2. Temporary Protection

Directive 2001/55/EC on Temporary Protection was one of the first legal acts adopted by the European Union on asylum, which was not activated by Italy or Greece in 2015-2016. This Directive applies to mass influxes of people, in the case of both spontaneous arrivals and those due to evacuation plans. The cause triggering the exodus process from one's land can be of various kinds (e.g. armed conflict or endemic violence, human rights violations), and may also include environmental disasters (Favilli, 2018). Temporary protection measures are justified as it is believed that the right to asylum is not enough to ensure adequate protection precisely because of the high number of people involved which would not allow for a careful individual assessment. EC's definition explains it as:

A procedure of exceptional character to provide, in the event of a mass influx or imminent mass influx of displaced persons from non-EU countries who are unable to return to their country of origin, immediate and temporary protection to such persons, in particular if there is also a risk that the asylum system will be unable to process this influx without adverse effects for its efficient operation, in the interests of the persons concerned and other persons requesting protection (EC, 2020).

The security granted by temporary protection is, therefore, collective and does not require the individual to prove they are in personal danger (Favilli, 2018). Under Temporary Protection "assistance and protection against refoulement have been extended on a group basis, without either a determination of prima facie refugee status for the group or individual status determinations for members of the group" (UNHCR, 2019). Subsidiary Protection differs from Temporary Protection as the former is supposed to be granted following an individual status determination (EMN, 2019). Temporary protection, if circumstances so require, can be extended by six months after six months, and up to a total of three years, but may also be prematurely revoked if the situation in the country of origin improves, a case in which the displaced persons must be repatriated (Favilli, 2018). The temporary residence permit in EU member states is granted based on the Temporary protection directive or based on the Act No. 221/2003 Coll., on the Temporary Protection of Foreigners, as amended.)

In **Turkey**, LFIP defines temporary protection as the situation concerning foreigners who arrived in Turkey as a result of forced migration²². The TPR was issued on 22 October 2014 and is a complementary form of protection used in situations where individual processing for

²² Article 7 of TPR provides: "(1) Temporary protection shall be granted to foreigners who were forced to leave their countries and are unable to return to the countries they left and who arrived at or crossed our borders in masses to seek urgent and temporary protection and whose international protection requests cannot be taken under individual assessment. (...)"

international protection eligibility is deemed impractical. Persons who have fled to Turkey from Syria are granted this status. However, Syrians arriving in Turkey not directly from Syria but from a third country cannot benefit from the temporary protection status. These persons are allowed to apply for international protection under LFIP even if their family members in Turkey already benefit from temporary protection. Persons under temporary protection cannot be subject to administrative detention, but in some cases, they can be temporarily or permanently banned from residing outside a Temporary Accommodation Centre²³. TPR designates access to certain services for temporary protection beneficiaries such as health, education, access to the labour market, social assistance and interpretation services²⁴. Temporary protection in Turkey can last indefinitely or be terminated based on a governmental decision; therefore, a situation of uncertainty is created for Syrians under this type of protection (Gökalp Aras and Şahin Mencütek, 2020).

The increase in temporary protection forms in European and non-European countries has negatively affected real minimum standards and is not considered a positive development in the international refugee regime. For example, in 2016, **Sweden** introduced the Act Temporarily Restricting the Possibility to Obtain Residence Permits in Sweden, referred to as the Temporary Law. It aims to reduce the number of asylum seekers by only issuing temporary residence permits and restricting family reunification (Shakra and Szalanska, 2020). The Temporary Act would have expired on 19 July 2019. However, the Swedish government, re-elected in 2018, submitted a bill to extend the already existing Temporary Act for another temporary period until 19 July 2021 (Ibid.).

3.2.1.3. Other Forms of National Protection

Apart from the EU-harmonized protection instruments, namely Refugee Status, Subsidiary Protection, and Temporary Protection, MSs may create their own practices and forms of national (or non-harmonized) protection, such as national forms of protection under the umbrella of “humanitarian reasons”, for persons who do not qualify for international protection but whose removal may not be affected for legal or practical reasons. However, these national protection statuses are under the discretionary power of national governments. After 2015, these mechanisms have steered towards more temporary and restrictive contents.

The principle of asylum is present in the Constitutions of **Italy, Poland, Germany and Iraq**. In **Germany**, the right to apply for asylum is part of the German Constitution. It applies for people persecuted on political grounds because of their race, nationality, political opinion, fundamental religious conviction or membership of a particular social group, including those with shared characteristics, such as a specific sexual orientation (Hänsel et al., 2020). The asylum status can only be applied on the basis of state persecution (except for quasi-state persecution), excluding any form of emergency situation. In 22 May 1993 the text changed, maintaining the right of asylum but adding drastic restrictions and allowing, for example, the returns of people from safe third countries by abolishing the right to asylum in terms of quantitative significance, thus maintaining the number of asylum seekers receiving protection based on the respective Law low (Ibid.). In terms of rights, it provides beneficiaries with a residence permit for three years, unrestricted access to the labour market, privileged family reunification and a possible settlement permit after three or five years if other preconditions are met (Ibid.).

In **Germany**, beyond the international forms of protection and the asylum status emerging from the Constitution, there is also the **Ban on Deportation** and the **Toleration of Stay**, based on § 60a of the Residence Act (*AufenthG*). The National Ban on Deportation is the weakest form of protection that can be granted in the country, according to which the person is not deported if their return is considered a breach of the ECHR or if a concrete danger to life, limb or liberty

²³ TPR, Article 35.

²⁴ TPR, Articles 26-31

exists in that country (Hänsel et al., 2020). A person with a national Ban on Deportation receives a residence permit for at least one year, with the possibility to repeatedly extend the document; after five years, if other preconditions are met, a settlement permit might be granted. Employment is possible pending permission from the immigration authority (Ibid.). As regards Tolerated Stay, the person is actually requested to leave the country but cannot currently be deported; this does not constitute a residence permit. Such are the cases of serious illness, separation of families, absence of travel documents or if deportation is impossible due to the situation in the country of origin. Additionally, anyone receiving an education is granted what is known as “education tolerance” (*Ausbildungsduldung*). The latter expires with the departure of the foreigner, who is not entitled to return to the Federal Republic of Germany (Hänsel et al., 2020).

In **Poland**, asylum is understood as a legal tool for providing a national form of protection, granted if the applicant requires protection and if doing so is in the best interest of the country (leaving the exact interpretation to decision-makers) (Law on Protection). For years, asylum was granted in very few cases or not at all; in 2014 the Polish authorities began to grant asylum more often to Ukrainian nationals fleeing the military conflict in Western Ukraine (Pachocka and Sobczak-Szelc, 2020). Also, in **Poland**, two special permits are stipulated in the Law on Foreigners, allowing a foreigner to stay in Poland under specific circumstances: **a permit for stay due to humanitarian reasons** and **a permit for tolerated stay**. These permits are not mentioned as a form of protection in the Law on Protection, but they are rooted in a previous national form of protection and are, therefore, perceived as national forms of protection (Pachocka and Sobczak-Szelc, 2020). They are issued by the Border Guard as part of the procedure for issuing return orders because, since 2014, the Border Guard must check whether a person who is to be ordered to leave should be granted protection (Ibid.). The grounds for granting this kind of protection include situations in which a person’s return would infringe either on their human rights and/or their children’s rights, when return is impossible due to technical reasons, or situations in which returning to a given country of origin are such that granting this type of protection is merited (experience threats to their lives, torture, etc.) (Ibid.). Holders of the permit for stay due to humanitarian reasons have access to social assistance that covers shelter, food, necessary clothing and financial benefits. The permit is not issued if the foreigner has committed a serious crime in Poland or another country or if he or she constitutes a threat to state security or public order. In general, both permits offer reduced access to social assistance (Ibid.).

In **Italy**, according to Art. 10, par. 3 of the Italian Constitution, “A foreigner who, in his/her home country, is denied the effective exercise of the democratic freedoms guaranteed by the Italian Constitution shall be entitled to the right of asylum under the conditions established by law” (Ibrido and Terlizzi, 2019, p.17). In addition, in **Italy, Decree-Law no. 113/2018 abolished humanitarian protection in 2018, but the** domestic legislation provides special protection in exceptional circumstances. After the amendment of the Consolidated Act by Decree-Law no. 113/2018, art. 20 of the Consolidated Act, four specific forms of temporary protection were confirmed and three further forms of temporary protection were established. The four specific reasons for temporary permit to stay are for social protection reasons, victims of domestic violence, special cases of labour exploitation and special protection purposes. The additional three are temporary permits to stay for medical care, for victims of natural disasters and to reward acts of civic valour (Ibrido and Terlizzi, 2019, p.21)

The second paragraph of Article (21) of the Constitution of the **Republic of Iraq** states: “The right to political asylum in Iraq is regulated by law and it is not permissible to extradite a political refugee to a foreign entity or forcibly return him to the country from which they fled”. In addition, the third paragraph of the same article provides: “Political asylum is not granted to those accused of international or terrorist crimes, or whoever harms Iraq” (Warda and Almafraji, 2020). As such, the Iraqi Constitution upholds the right to grant asylum and has a Memorandum of Understanding with UNHCR.

In **Austria**, **humanitarian protection** can be granted if there are neither grounds for refugee status nor for subsidiary protection, and the BFA examines whether a “**residence title** for reasons of Art 8 ECHR” is to be granted (Josipovic and Reeger, 2019). This applies to cases where a return decision is permanently inadmissible for reasons of private and family life, duration and legality of the stay, actual existence of family life, worthiness of the protection of private life, degree of integration and ties to the home country (Ibid., 2019). The humanitarian title entails the same rights as subsidiary protection. Additionally, a “**Residence Permit in Cases Requiring Special Consideration**” can be issued for persons residing in Austria for five years, of which three years have been spent under a regular status (Ibid.). Furthermore, a “**Special Protection Residence Permit**” may be granted to victims of human trafficking, cross-border prostitution or violence (Ibid.).

In **Sweden**, asylum seekers who do not meet the conditions of the refugee definition or subsidiary protection can be granted a **residence permit in some extraordinary personal situations** such as if the asylum seeker is outside the country of nationality or of habitual residency in case of a stateless person; or if the asylum seeker risks being subjected to human trafficking, environmental disaster or very serious health issues (Shakra et al., 2018).

In the **UK**, people can apply not to be returned to their country of origin with a human right claim under ECHR, notably on the grounds of Article 3 (prohibition on torture and inhuman or degrading treatment) or Article 8 (right to respect for family life and private life). These claims can form part of an asylum claim but can also be lodged separately. The UK has also introduced specific resettlement policies in response to major humanitarian issues such as the Syrian civil war. First in 2014, and to a greater extent in 2015, the government established the Syrian Vulnerable Person Resettlement Scheme (VPRS) as a pathway for Syrians to resettle in the UK. Later, the Vulnerable Children’s Resettlement Scheme (VCRS) was introduced specifically for the resettlement of refugee children. The so-called Dubs Amendment to the Immigration Act 2016 binds the UK to accept the relocation of unaccompanied children from Europe to the UK, with priority given to those at risk of abuse and exploitation (Foley, 2020).

3.2.1.4. Protection in Turkey, Iraq and Lebanon

On a legislative level, in 2013 **Turkey** put into force a comprehensive law regulating international protection, the LFIP (Law No.6458 effective as of 11 April 2013). The Implementation Regulation (IR) of LFIP provides guidelines both for international protection and migration-related issues. Nevertheless, due to the geographical limitation, there was a gap in Turkish asylum law concerning individuals who do not fall within the scope of the Refugee Convention. This gap was filled by the entry into force of the TPR on 22 October 2014, which was issued on the basis of Article 91 of LFIP. Consequently, Turkey’s asylum legislation presents a dual structure, composed of two main pillars: on the one hand, the “international protection” pillar, which includes the refugee status, the conditional refugee status and the subsidiary protection status and, on the other, the “temporary protection” pillar. Non-European nationalities are given only conditional refugee status or subsidiary protection. Temporary protection can be terminated with a governmental decision; it thus creates significant uncertainty for Syrians under this type of protection. Therefore, international and temporary protection in Turkey provides more limited protection compared to the actual refugee status, which is the situation for four million refugees and asylum seekers in Turkey (Gökalp Aras and Şahin Mencütek, 2020).

Even though some countries are not signatories of the 1951 Convention, they may recognize the right of asylum by referring to the principle of non-refoulement as in the example of Iraq and Lebanon. The relevant procedures are included in the domestic legislation, mainly to the Constitution or Residency - Foreigners Law.

Iraq has not legislated a comprehensive legal framework on humanitarian asylum. A draft law has been submitted by the permanent committee for refugee affairs linked to the Iraqi Ministry of the Interior since 2016. The Iraqi cabinet has referred this project to the Iraqi Parliament, which has not legalized it yet²⁵. Despite the absence of a comprehensive legal framework for refugee protection, Iraq addresses international protection within the framework of its existing laws, treaties, agreements, declarations and international human rights instruments, which have already been mentioned above. Law No. 51 of 1971 on political asylum, which is currently in force, regulates the lives of asylum seekers in Iraq. However, it does not include provisions on humanitarian asylum, neither does it refer to the types of temporary or permanent protection. The Ministry of Immigration and Displacement has adopted Law No.21 of 2009 in order to organize and improve the conditions of Internally Displaced Persons (IDPs) and refugees in Iraq. The two aforementioned legislative texts, as well as the decisions and orders of the Permanent Committee for Refugees constitute the national legislative framework regarding refugee protection. Article 2 of Law 21/2009 specifies that refugees in Iraq are the ones who

... resorted to it as a result of being persecuted because of race, religion, nationality, belonging to a certain social group or political opinions, or as a result of exposure to public violence or events that seriously disturb public security or threaten their lives or their physical safety or liberties and those who have taken refuge in accordance with international law and agreements to which Iraq is a party

With regards to Palestinian refugees, Law No.21/2009 defines Palestinian refugees as the Palestinians "*who were forced to leave their homeland since 1948 and resided legally in Iraq and were accepted as refugees*". However, the issuance of the Foreigners' Residence Law No. 76 of 2017 revokes the privileges included in the decisions of the Saddam Hussein regime, which granted Palestinian refugees the right to live, own property, work, access education, etc (such as Resolution 202 that gives Palestinian refugees all the rights of the Iraqi citizen). The abrogation of Resolution No. 202 was a setback in the protection of Palestinian refugees in Iraq. The new Residence Law for foreigners No. 76 of 2017 has withdrawn the rights granted previously to them and deprived them of benefits such as food ration and retirement, negatively affecting the humanitarian situation of children Palestinian refugees in Iraq. On the other hand, Syrian refugees, as defined in articles (2) and (3) of the Political Refugee Law, are considered as "displaced across borders". Iraq does not treat Syrians residing in its territory as refugees or asylum seekers, but it considers them as guests according to the directives of the National Security Agents Council and the Iraqi Ministry of Immigration. This approach aims to avoid any possibility of them resettling in Iraq or being granted Iraqi citizenship in the future (Warda and Almafraji, 2020).

Lebanon also lacks a comprehensive legal framework on refugee protection. The domestic legislation governing the status of foreign nationals on Lebanese territory is the 1962 Law Regulating the Entry and Stay of Foreigners in Lebanon and their Exit from the Country. According to its article 26, "any foreign national who is the subject of a prosecution or a conviction by an authority that is not Lebanese for a political crime or whose life or freedom is threatened, also for political reasons, may request political asylum in Lebanon". Article 26 contains a definition of the term "political refugee" while the scope of Article 31 of the same law, which enshrines the principle of non-refoulement and includes only political refugees. As a result, the Lebanese legal framework fails to provide protection to individuals seeking refuge on the basis of other (than political) grounds. Furthermore, according to Lebanese law, the illegal entry, residency and exit of foreigners are penalized, subjecting refugees and migrants alike to criminal incarceration and administrative detention. Due to the absence of a national

²⁵ The draft law prepared by the Ministry of Immigration and Displaced and the Ministry of Interior represented by the Permanent Committee for Refugee Affairs aims to include all cases of both humanitarian and political asylum due to persecution and threats based on race, religion or nationality or social affiliation in line with the provisions of the Constitution of Iraq, international agreements and the enforcing laws (Warda and Almafraji, 2020).

refugee law, a Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) was signed by the General Directorate of General Security (GSO) and UNHCR in September 2003. The MoU explicitly recognizes the right to asylum for individuals with a well-grounded fear of returning to their country. The responsibilities of both UNHCR and the Lebanese government were clearly stated and acknowledged regarding the inherent rights of asylum seekers, the Refugee Status Determination (RSD) and the seeking out of durable solutions. Under the MoU, UNHCR is tasked by the GSO with the issuance of temporary circulation permits, normally valid up to three months, allowing UNHCR to perform Refugee Status Determination (RSD). The circulation permit may be extended for a period of six to nine months by GSO. However, these legal status deliberations are not formally recognized by the Lebanese authorities, and as a result, a formal legal status is not granted to refugees. The UNHCR/GSO MoU was not tailored to address the mass influx of Syrian refugees in 2011, who had entered lawfully following the open border policy constituted by bilateral agreements between Syria and Lebanon. In the case of the Syrian crisis, UNHCR did not formally declare a *prima facie* status nor did it establish a Temporary Protection regime for Syrian refugees. Instead, it appeared to apply a *de facto prima facie*.²⁶ Syrian refugees were unable to regularize and legalize their stay. In 2015, the protection space for asylum seekers and refugees was highly compromised. The Lebanese government requested UNHCR to suspend registrations and to deregister those who had returned to Syria (e.g. to seek medical aid in Syria, which is inaccessible in Lebanon, or to vote). New visa categories were introduced to regulate Syrian entry into Lebanon. A 'humanitarian exception' was introduced²⁷. New residency rules and regulations brought about a significant change for Syrian presence in Lebanon (Rahme, 2020).

3.2.2 The Proliferation of Asylum Procedures and the Multiple Categorizations of the Applicants

Through the recast EU Asylum Procedures Directive of 2011, multiple asylum procedures were established, resulting in the fragmentation of asylum procedures depending on the location of the applicant or the presumed content of his/her application (AIDA, 2016a). The Directive provides the following types of procedures:

- A regular asylum procedure to examine protection needs
- A "prioritised procedure" to examine the protection needs of the vulnerable or manifestly well-founded cases as part of the regular procedure
- An "admissibility procedure" which does not examine protection needs, for asylum seekers who may be the responsibility of another country or have lodged repetitive claims
- An "accelerated procedure" to examine the protection needs of ostensibly unfounded or security-related cases
- A "Dublin procedure" which does not determine either protection needs or admissibility, for asylum seekers whose claims may fall under the responsibility of another EU Member State; and
- A "border procedure" to speedily conduct admissibility or examine the merits under an accelerated procedure at borders or in transit zones (AIDA, 2016a).

3.2.2.1. Access to the Procedure and Registration

International protection can be sought by an individual at any point or place in a country's territory, territorial waters or borders, whether by expressly requesting asylum or by implying a

²⁶ Prima facie status is used during mass displacements, as it legalizes the status of a group of refugees fleeing under the same circumstances, also granting international protection in accordance with the 1951 Refugee Convention; this is how it differs from the temporary protection regime.

²⁷ Unaccompanied and/or separated children with a parent already registered in Lebanon, persons living with disabilities with a relative already registered in Lebanon, persons with urgent medical needs for whom treatment in Syria is unavailable and persons who will be resettled in third countries.

need for protection. The registration of a protection claims, however, entails an elaborate administrative process, whereby authorities record the person's intention to seek protection together with his or her personal details and other relevant information. This process takes place before certain authorities, within specified deadlines and often in specified locations. In most cases, it also results in the production of official documentation to certify the individual's status (AIDA, 2018a). The EU asylum *acquis* introduces a range of legal concepts relevant to the registration of applications, such as "making", "registering" and "lodging" a claim (article 6 of the recast Asylum Procedures Directive), without however detailing how these notions are to be understood in practice.

Article 6 of the recast Asylum Procedures Directive requires Member States to register an asylum application within three working days if the application is made to the authority competent under national law for such registration, or no later than six working days if it is made to other authorities who are likely to receive asylum applications but are not competent to register them, such as for instance at the border or in detention. **The time limit for registration** can be extended to ten working days in case of large numbers of third-country nationals applying for asylum simultaneously (AIDA, 2017c). A person who has made an asylum application must have an effective opportunity to lodge the asylum application as soon as possible. Member States may require that asylum applications be lodged "in person and/or at a designated place". According to Article 6(4) of the recast Asylum Procedures Directive, an asylum application is deemed to have been lodged once a form submitted by the applicant, or where provided for in national law, an official report, has reached the competent authorities of the Member State. As regards **the place of registration**, EU law does not require Member States to designate a place where asylum applications can be "registered", although it enables them to specify a designated location where they can be "lodged". To that end, most European countries have taken the necessary steps to ensure that registration of asylum applications made within the territory can be conducted in different parts of their territory. Where the applicant does not lodge his or her asylum application, Member States may consider the asylum application as implicitly withdrawn or abandoned and either discontinue the examination of the asylum application or reject the application in case it is considered as unfounded on the basis of an adequate examination of its substance (AIDA Comparator, 2017).

The interview is one of the most crucial parts of the asylum procedure. The applicant should be provided with all the necessary information regarding the procedure. If the applicant is not able to communicate with the interviewer due to a language barrier, an interpreter must be available. A lawyer representing the applicant can also attend the interview. The interview is confidential and can be audio recorded. After the interview, the decision whether to grant the applicant refugee status, subsidiary protection status or reject the application is provided (Petracou et al., 2018, p. 32). For several RESPOND European countries (e.g. **Sweden** and **Poland**), the formal introduction of an asylum application entails a single procedural step: after a person has expressed the wish to seek international protection, his or her claim is formalized and its examination by the asylum authority can begin. Other countries (e.g. **Germany, Italy, Greece, and Turkey**) construe "registration" and "lodging" as discrete stages with different legal effects in the procedure (AIDA, 2018a).

In **Germany**, the border authority or the police shall take the foreigner's photograph and fingerprints for identification measures and have the obligation to refer the person requesting asylum to the competent or nearest reception centre for the purpose of registration. Every applicant over the age of fourteen must be submitted to procedures establishing his or her identity and provide fingerprints. As part of the application process, information such as the country of nationality, number of people, sex and family ties of the asylum seeker will be recorded. The reception centres and arrival centres are run by the federal states, and various processes such as registration, identity checks, interview, and decision-making are streamlined in the same facility (Chemin et al., 2018).

In **Austria**, upon an application for asylum the police record the personal data, take a photo and fingerprints and conduct a brief initial interview. After a first inquiry with an interpreter is recorded within a maximum of 48 hours in police custody, the documents, including a report of the inquiry, are submitted to the Federal Office for Immigration and Asylum (BFA). Only the prognosis decision about the likeliness of Austria's responsibility for the respective case marks the formal starting point of any asylum procedure (Josipovic and Reeger, 2019). Consequently, persons are transferred to a Distribution Centre or invited to present themselves at one of the two Initial Reception Centres in Traiskirchen (Eastern Austria) and Thalham (Western Austria) (Josipovic and Reeger, 2019).

In the case of **Sweden**, the asylum procedure starts when the asylum seekers arrive at the reception of the Migration Agency centre and fill in a registration form, giving a short registration interview. Since 2018, asylum applications can only be made at the Swedish Migration Agency (SMA) centres in Stockholm, Gothenburg or Malmö and, therefore, asylum seekers cannot seek asylum in any other place such as airports, ports or police stations, as is the case in the other EU member states (Shakra and Szalanska, 2020). During the registration interview, the asylum seekers answer a few open questions regarding, for example, why they left the country of origin and cannot or will not return there and how they arrived in Sweden (Shakra et al., 2018). Later on, the Migration Agency will assign a migration caseworker who will review and prepare the asylum application for the investigation interview and check the applicability of the Dublin Regulation. The Swedish Aliens Act requires the asylum seekers be photographed and their fingerprints taken regardless if the application is related to asylum or employment. The Migration Agency will use the asylum seekers' fingerprints to investigate if the asylum seeker has sought asylum somewhere else within the Schengen zone, thus activating the Dublin Regulation (Ibid.).

In **Poland** applications for international protection are submitted either at the border or within the national territory, at one of the Border Guard (BG) units, and applicants get a temporary confirmation of their identity and the status of an applicant for international protection (Pachocka and Sobczak-Szelc, 2020). The Border Guard is responsible only for receiving applications and providing asylum seekers with necessary medical aid and information on further steps. Confirming the identity of an applicant is the task of the Border Guard that receives the application. The procedure includes checking a person's identity documents, and documents authorizing them to cross the border and stay on the territory of Poland, checking whether the applicant has these documents, taking photos and fingerprints. The BG is responsible for guaranteeing the presence of an interpreter (if needed) at the moment of submitting an application. Only vulnerable groups are transported to reception centres by the BG or with the use of transport organized by the BG (Ibid.).

In **Greece**, asylum applications are submitted to the Asylum Service which is also competent for applying the Dublin Procedure, with most requests and transfers concerning family reunification in other Member States. Applications are lodged in 18 different locations, notably Lesvos, Attica, Thessaloniki and Samos (AIDA, 2018a).

In **Italy**, asylum requests can be lodged at the border or within the national territory before the Border Police and the Immigration Office or the Police (*Questure*²⁸) which are the competent authorities respectively (AIDA, 2019). Applications must be lodged within 8 working days at the borders (AIDA Comparator, 2017). The responsible authorities for the examination of applications for international protection are the Territorial Commissions, which are the independent administrative bodies across Italian territory. Each Territorial Commission includes representatives of the Prefectures, State Police, Municipalities and a member appointed by the United Nations High Commissioner for Human Rights. The orientation and

²⁸ The *Questure* are police authorities that deal mainly with public safety and security, as well as perform some administrative functions

coordination of the currently existing 20 Territorial Commissions is ensured through the National Commission, which also organizes the training and updating of Territorial Commission members. The National Commission is composed of representatives of the Ministry of the Interior, the Ministry of Foreign Affairs, the Presidency of the Council of Ministers and UNCHR (Ibrido and Terlizzi, 2019, p.23).

In the **UK**, in order to apply for international protection, applicants must go to the Asylum Intake Unit in Croydon, London, or, if detained, they may apply at the detention centre. The first step is a screening interview with an immigration officer, where the asylum claim is registered, and the officer decides if the person will be detained or admitted temporarily. The outcome of the screening interview determines which of the following procedures will be followed: regular procedure, accelerated procedure or safe third country procedure (Foley, 2020).

In **Turkey**, the Directorate-General for Migration Management (DGMM) is the agency responsible for the registering and further processing of all applications for international and temporary protection. According to LFIP, foreigners must apply to the Provincial Directorate of Migration Management (PDMM) offices in any of the 81 provinces upon their entry to Turkey. The PDMM offices are also formally in charge of registering temporary protection beneficiaries. After pre-registration, the applicants should appear before the PDMM office in 30 days to obtain their Temporary Protection Identification Card. International protection applicants need to present their request in person at the assigned PDMM. Applications can also be made during administrative detention and at the border, before law enforcement agencies within the territory or at border gates (Gökalp Aras and Şahin Mencütek, 2020).

3.2.2.2. Regular Procedure and Prioritized Procedure

The Regular Procedure is the basic asylum procedure where the asylum application is examined in substance. This takes place when no other form of procedure, from the ones mentioned below, applies. In this procedure, the personal hearing/interview constitutes a crucial step. The interviewer aims at understanding the individual reasons for flight, and interviewees are requested to explain their reasons for fleeing, their personal history and any persecution in their country of origin in a plausible way and in full detail.

According to the recast Asylum Procedures Directive, a “**prioritized procedure**” could also take place as part of the Regular Procedure. As explained in the Preamble to the recast Asylum Procedures Directive, prioritized procedures entail a more rapid examination of claims “without derogating from normally applicable procedural time limits, principles and guarantees” (AIDA, 2017b). Member States are encouraged to favourably prioritize applications from persons with manifestly well-founded claims or vulnerabilities warranting special procedural guarantees (AIDA, 2017b). As such, **vulnerability** plays a crucial role in the **examination of the asylum application**, as many EU countries, such as **Greece, Italy** and **Poland** provide that asylum applications by persons with special needs are to be examined by way of priority (AIDA, 2017a). Additionally, in **Italy**, the law states that the Territorial Commission for International Protection must schedule the applicant’s interview “in the first available seat” when that applicant is deemed vulnerable (AIDA, 2017a). Conversely, **Austria** and **Germany** do not foresee prioritization of the processing of claims by vulnerable groups. In **Austria**, special provisions exist especially for unaccompanied minors (whose numbers are high in comparison to other EU countries) concerning the admissibility and the substantive procedures. Unaccompanied minors are legally represented first by a legal advisor and, in the substantive procedure, by the legal staff of the respective provincial children and youth aid authorities in some provinces; other provinces choose to deploy representatives of specialized organizations (Josipovic and Reeger, 2019). In **Turkey**, the prioritized examination applies to persons with special needs who shall be “given priority with respect to all rights and proceedings” regarding their application for international protection (Gökalp Aras and Şahin Mencütek, 2020).

Article 31 of the recast Asylum Procedures Directive determines **time limits for deciding on an asylum application at first instance**. Article 31(2) requires the Member States to conclude the procedure as soon as possible. Furthermore, according to article 31(3) the procedure must be completed within 6 months of lodging the application (AIDA, 2017c). In general, time limits for the examination of asylum applications at first instance vary from one country to another, and between different procedures in the same country (AIDA, 2017b). The six-month time limit can be extended by nine more months in cases where:

- Complex issues of fact and/or law are involved
- A large number of third-country nationals or stateless persons simultaneously apply for international protection
- The delay can clearly be attributed to the failure of the applicant to comply with his or her obligations under Article 13 of the recast Asylum Procedures Directive

In exceptional circumstances, the time limit can be extended by another three months when necessary for ensuring an adequate and complete examination of the application for international protection. In general, an overall deadline of 21 months should not be exceeded by Member States (AIDA, 2017c).

Table 2. General maximum duration of regular procedure (days)	
Austria	180
Germany	-
Greece	180
Italy	33
Poland	180
Sweden	-
Turkey	180
UK	-

Source: AIDA. (2017c). AIDA Comparator – Asylum Procedure.²⁹

3.2.2.3. Admissibility Procedure

The recast Asylum Procedures Directive (2013) allows Member States not to examine an asylum application when they are not responsible for that claim under the Dublin Regulation or when the claim is deemed inadmissible. Inadmissibility may only be ordered on five exhaustive grounds defined by the Directive, where the applicant:

- has been granted international protection by another Member State
- comes from a “first country of asylum”
- comes from a “safe third country”³⁰
- makes a subsequent application with no new elements
- is a dependant of an applicant and makes a separate claim without justification (AIDA, 2016a).

Table 3. Grounds for Inadmissibility Per Country					
Countries	Grounds for inadmissibility: Article 33(2) recast Asylum Procedures Directive				
	Protection in another EU MS	First country of asylum	Safe third country	Subsequent application	Application by dependant
Austria	√	x	√	√	x
Germany	√	√	√	√	x

²⁹ <http://www.asylumineurope.org/comparator/asylum-procedure> [Accessed 17 May 2020]

³⁰ Safe third country is a country of transit of an applicant which is considered as capable of offering him or her adequate protection against persecution or serious harm. The concept is defined in Directive 2013/32/EU and is used as a ground for declaring asylum applications inadmissible.

Greece	√	√	√	√	√
Italy	x	√	x	√	x
Poland	√	√	x	√	√
Sweden	x	x	x	x	x
Turkey	-	√	√	√	√
UK	√	√	√	x	x

Source: AIDA. (2017c). AIDA Comparator – Asylum Procedure.³¹

Except **Italy** and **Sweden**, all EU RESPOND countries plus **Turkey**³² have incorporated the admissibility procedure into their national asylum systems, although with divergences in its transposition and practical application. For instance, **Poland**, **Turkey** and **Greece** have transposed the inadmissibility ground connected to the dependant application. The admissibility procedure based on the concept of the “first country of asylum” is reflected in the national legislation of **Germany**, **Greece**, **Poland** and **Turkey**. In this case, the asylum claim is deemed inadmissible – and consequently not examined according to its merit – when the asylum applicant has been granted refugee status in a third country or when he or she could “enjoy sufficient protection” (Pannia et al., 2018). In **Turkey**, the admissibility procedure is regulated by Article 72(1) of the LFIP and applies, inter alia, in cases of subsequent applications or the application of the “first country of asylum” and “safe third country” concepts.

Among RESPOND countries, the most recurrent ground for inadmissibility is the one related to “safe third country”, applied in the asylum systems of **Austria**, **Greece**, **Germany**, **Turkey** and the **UK** (Ibid.). However, in practice, the concept has been extensively applied only in some of these countries. In **Greece**, the concrete application of the notion of a “safe third country” played a formidable role within the implementation of the EU-Turkey Statement. Asylum applicants entering Greece after 18 March 2016 saw their applications dismissed as inadmissible and were returned to Turkey, which was considered a “safe third country” under the application of art. 38 of the recast APD (Leivaditi et al., 2020). On appeal, these inadmissibility decisions were deemed incompatible with the asylum *acquis*, as the majority of Appeals Committees found Turkey not to qualify as a “safe third country” (AIDA, 2016a).

In the **UK**, through the third country procedure, the officer of the screening interview may conclude that applicants have passed through a safe third country on their way to the UK and their case is referred to the Home Office Third Country Unit. They may be detained, subject to transfer to another EU country under the Dublin Regulation or to the country they had passed through *en route*. As with “clearly unfounded” cases, there is no right to appeal within the asylum system and the only recourse is judicial review.

Notably, inadmissibility decisions can be issued also in relation to another EU Member State within the framework of the Dublin III Regulation, when national institutions ascertain that another EU country is responsible for examining the asylum. In these cases, the admissibility procedure involves the compression of fundamental legal guarantees for asylum applicants. In **Austria** when asylum seekers do not cooperate on their return to the EU country deemed responsible for their applications under Dublin III Regulations, welfare measures, such as cash allowances, are reduced or withdrawn (Pannia et al., 2018).

3.2.2.4. Accelerated Procedure

The 2005 Asylum Procedures Directive and its 2013 recast make provisions for the possibility of applying special procedures to deal with specific caseloads which may warrant swifter decisions. The recast Asylum Procedures Directive states that “in well-defined circumstances

³¹ <http://www.asylumineurope.org/comparator/asylum-procedure> [Accessed 17 May 2020]

³² However, Turkey does not use the concept in practice (AIDA, 2016a, p. 17).

where an application is likely to be unfounded or where there are serious national security or public order concerns, Member States should be able to accelerate the examination procedure, in particular by introducing shorter, but reasonable, time limits for certain procedural steps, without prejudice to an adequate and complete examination being carried out and to the applicant's effective access to basic principles and guarantees provided for in this Directive". The concept of "safe country of origin" (the country whose nationals may be presumed not to be in need of international protection), defined in Directive 2013/32/EU, is grounds for channelling an asylum application towards an accelerated procedure.

Accelerated procedures differ from regular procedural rules, as well as from prioritised procedures "in particular by introducing shorter, but reasonable, time limits for certain procedural steps". Accelerated procedures under EU law involve appeals subject to shorter time limits and which often have no (automatic) suspensive effect over removal decisions, thereby exposing asylum seekers to the risk of deportation before their appeal is decided (AIDA, 2017b). Unfounded or manifestly unfounded applications can be accelerated under a less protective procedural regime on the assumption that they will most likely be rejected (Ibid.). Although the recast APD does not define the 'manifestly unfounded claim', art. 31(8) lays down the grounds upon which Member States may provide an accelerated procedure (Pannia et al., 2018).

Article 31(8) of the Directive identifies ten grounds for the application of the accelerated procedure, namely when the applicant:

- has only raised issues not relevant to refugee or subsidiary protection status
- comes from a "safe country of origin"
- has misled the authorities by presenting false documents or withholding relevant information relating to identity and nationality which could adversely affect the decision
- has likely, in bad faith, destroyed or disposed of identity or travel documents
- has made inconsistent, contradictory, improbable or insufficient representations which make his or her claim unconvincing
- has filed an admissible subsequent application
- entered or stayed irregularly in the territory and, without good reason, did not present him or herself to the authorities to file an application as soon as possible
- is making an application to delay or frustrate the enforcement of a return decision
- is a danger to national security or has been expelled for reasons of public security and public order
- refuses to be fingerprinted (AIDA Comparator, 2017).

All RESPOND countries, except **Iraq and Lebanon**, apply accelerated procedures. In **Sweden**, the legislative framework does not contain an explicit reference to the "accelerated procedure". However, a fast-track procedure is provided in cases of manifestly unfounded claims and when the applicant's country of origin has a recognition rate below 20% (AIDA, 2017b). High divergences are observed concerning various aspects of accelerated procedures, such as the grounds on which the procedure is triggered, the time frame according to which the procedure should be conducted and the determining authorities. Apart from **Turkey, Italy and Poland**, all RESPOND countries applying an accelerated procedure incorporate a notion of "safe country of origin" in their domestic legislation (Pannia et al., 2018). Based on this concept, the asylum applications of foreigners coming from a specific list of countries are presumed to be manifestly unfounded unless applicants prove otherwise.

In **Germany**, since March 2016, an accelerated procedure has been introduced as part of Asylum Package II (§ 30a AsylG). This procedure is carried out in branch offices of the Federal Office for Migration and Refugees (BAMF) within the special reception centres. The procedure was implemented for two years at two BAMF sites – Manching/Ingolstadt and Bamberg, both

in Bavaria – where special reception centres were prescribed by law for this procedure. According to Section 30a (2) of the AsylG, an accelerated procedure is supposed to last only seven days (Hänsel et al., 2020). In Germany, accelerated procedure is implemented, for example, for asylum seekers coming from a country that is considered a safe country of origin (currently the EU member states and Albania, Bosnia-Herzegovina, Kosovo, Montenegro, North Macedonia, Serbia, Ghana, Senegal), or as a sanction if asylum seekers are accused of having deliberately provided false information about their identity. Applications by asylum seekers coming from safe countries of origin are generally considered ‘manifestly unfounded’ unless the individual in question can present evidence proving his or her individual persecution (Hänsel et al., 2020). 20

In **Greece**, Law 4375/2016, art. 51(6) provides that an application may be registered and examined by way of priority for persons who: a) belong to vulnerable groups or are in need of special procedural guarantees, b) apply from detention, at the border or from a Reception and Identification Centre, c) are likely to fall within the Dublin Procedure, d) have cases reasonably believed to be well-founded, e) have cases which may be considered as manifestly unfounded, f) represent a threat to national security or public order or g) file a Subsequent Application (AIDA, 2019a, pp. 43-44).

In **Italy**, Law n. 132/2018 has increased the cases of accelerated procedure for deciding an asylum claim. Article 28-bis of the Procedure Decree, as amended by Decree Law 113/2018, implemented by L 132/2018, provides for different accelerated procedures that foresee different time limits – from 5 to 18 days – following the immediate transmission of the file from the *Questura* to the Territorial Commission, depending on the applicable ground (AIDA, 2019, p.60). The accelerated procedure applies to the following cases: 1. The applicant comes from a safe country of origin; the applicant makes a Subsequent Application without presenting new elements; 2. The application is made by a person detained in a Pre-removal Detention Centre (CPR) or in a Hotspot or First Reception Centre; the asylum application is made at the border and 3. The application is deemed manifestly unfounded (Ibid., p. 61)

In the **UK**, the accelerated procedure applies if a case is judged as “clearly unfounded”. Although this judgment may be based on individual circumstances, the most common reason is that the applicant comes from a country that has been designated by law as “safe”. The consequence of this status is that appeals are “non-suspensive”. It should be noted that Detained Fast Track (DFT), which involved detaining with a view to deporting in cases where the Home Office considered that the case could be closed quickly, was suspended in July 2015 (Foley, 2020).

In **Turkey**, in the accelerated procedure the personal interview must take place within 3 days from the registration, and the decision must be issued within 5 days from the personal interview (LFIP, Article 79.2). The very limited time frame within which decisions must currently be taken by the responsible authorities (5 days from the personal interview) raises concerns about the quality of the RSD process (Gökalp Aras and Sahin Mencütek, 2020).

Different approaches vis-à-vis the exemption of **vulnerable groups** from the accelerated procedure have been incorporated in the legal framework of MSs. Persons identified as requiring special procedural guarantees are always channelled towards the regular procedure in the example of **Greece**. Vulnerable persons are not exempt from the accelerated procedure in **Germany, Italy, Poland** and **Sweden** (AIDA, 2017a). It should be noted that, when transposing the Asylum Procedures Directive, **Sweden** saw no use of transposing Article 24 on applicants in need of special procedural guarantees (AIDA, 2017a). As regards unaccompanied children, the recast Asylum Procedures Directive does not set out a coherent approach for the adaptation of the accelerated procedure to their needs. It allows Member States to apply accelerated procedures only where one of the following three circumstances

arises: the child comes from a safe country of origin, makes an admissible subsequent application or represents a threat to public order or national security (AIDA, 2017a).

3.2.2.5. Border Procedure and Other Types

According to the recast Asylum Procedures Directive (2013), grounds listed in art. 31(8) for the accelerated procedure also apply to procedures conducted at the border or in transit zones.

In **Germany**, the airport procedure, regulated in section 18a of the Asylum Act, applies to asylum applicants who enter the country by air without valid documents, applicants who apply for asylum in a transit area and those who come from a “safe country of origin”. Applicants are held in the transit zone and are subject to accelerated examination of their asylum claim without them being considered to have entered German territory (Hänsel et al., 2020). The fast-tracking is based on the principle of pre-selecting asylum seekers depending on recognition rates (‘perspective to stay’ with a protection rate of over 50% – where this is the decision rate by the BAMF before the appeal process) in order to swiftly carry out the procedure (Hänsel et al., 2020). Additionally, the law foresees no exemption from the border procedure for vulnerable groups or unaccompanied children; however, in practice, unaccompanied children have been channelled out of the airport procedure (AIDA, 2017a). The procedure features a very short time frame (the applicant’s interview must take place 2 days after the application, while in case of rejection, an interim measure is required within 3 days), which raises concerns about the quality of the assessment and the access of applicants to effective remedy.

In **Greece**, there are the two following types of border procedures: The normal border procedure which applies to asylum seekers arriving in airports or transit zones, and a special procedure, known as the Fast-Track Border Procedure which was introduced by Law No. 4375/2016 and is closely linked to the EU-Turkey statement implementation. This procedure applies to all asylum seekers arriving after 20 March 2016 who lodged their applications in Lesbos, Chios, Samos, Leros and Kos, where Hotspots have been established (Leivaditi et al., 2020). Vulnerable people and applicants for family reunification are exempted from this procedure and must follow the regular procedure. Until August 2017, requests by vulnerable persons and applicants for family reunification were referred to a Regional Asylum Office (RAO) on the mainland and, as a result, the geographical restriction was lifted for their cases. Since then and due to conditions of overcrowding in mainland RAOs, the guidelines of the Asylum Service have changed, and applications regarding the regular procedure (such as those of vulnerable persons and applicants for family reunification) are also examined on the islands. Based on the relevant law, the geographical restriction is lifted only for those who have a positive decision to their application and for some cases of vulnerable applicants only after Ministerial Decisions regarding the decongestion of the islands. Under the Fast-Track Border Procedure, inter alia, interviews may also be conducted by EASO staff, while applicants face very limited deadlines. The concept of “safe third country” has been applied for the first time for applicants belonging to nationalities with a recognition rate of over 25%, including Syrians (Ibid.).

In **Austria**, as of 2015, the federal government also provides details on legal cases of accelerated procedures that are referred to as “fast track procedures”. In general, these are enforced when a person’s application is “evidently unfounded”, meaning the applicant has arrived from or crossed through a safe third country, has tried to hide his/her identity or does not state reasons of persecution. These cases need to be ruled upon within a maximum of five months and negative decisions do not have a suspensory effect (Josipovic and Reeger, 2019). In **Poland**, in 2017, a proposal for amending the Law on Protection was announced and followed by its revised version in 2019, aimed at introducing a border procedure and lists of safe countries and safe third countries (Pachocka and Sobczak-Szelc, 2020). According to the draft law, which also incorporates the concept of “safe country of origin” and “safe third country”, asylum applicants may be detained pending the RSD procedure. Many concerns

have been raised by NGOs against the proposal, which also reduces essential procedural safeguards, such as the right to appeal against a negative decision (Pannia et al., 2018).

In **Italy**, following the 2018 reform, Decree Law 113/2018 introduced the border procedure, applicable at border areas and in transit zones which foresees a 9-day examination of asylum applications and concerns applicants apprehended after evading or attempting to evade border controls and persons coming from a safe country of origin. The Minister of the Interior is responsible for determining the specific areas where this procedure applies (Aida, 2019, p.60). In addition to the Border Procedure and the different types of Accelerated Procedures, Decree Law 113/2018 has also amended the Procedure Decree to introduce an “**immediate procedure**” (*procedimento immediato*), applicable where the applicant is subject to investigation for crimes which may trigger exclusion from international protection and grounds for detention in a CPR apply, including a non-definitive judgment (AIDA, 2019, p. 63).

In **Turkey**, the PDMM shall be promptly notified of applications made at the border, although the LFIP does not provide any specification in this regard. Applications made after the border crossing are subject to the regular procedure and the general rules laid down by LFIP. In relation to applications made in the transit area of an airport or if a person is rejected at the border, the competent PDMM will be notified by the border authorities and will undertake their examination (Gökalp Aras and Sahin Mencütek, 2020).

3.2.2.6. Appeal, second-instance procedures, and legal assistance

Article 46 of the recast Asylum Procedures Directive requires Member States to ensure that asylum seekers have the right to an effective remedy before a court or tribunal against any decision taken on their application for international protection, including inadmissibility decisions and decisions taken at the borders. An effective remedy is furthermore defined as providing for a full and *ex nunc* examination of both facts and points of law at least in appeals procedures before a court or tribunal at first instance (AIDA Comparator, 2017). The Directive does not impose specific time limits for lodging appeals but requires MSs to provide reasonable time limits and other necessary rules for the applicant to exercise the right to an effective remedy.

Asylum seekers must have access to an appeal with automatic suspensive effect over the execution return proceedings pending the outcome of the remedy under Article 46(5) of the Directive. In certain cases, including cases that have been decided in accelerated procedures or border procedures and inadmissibility decisions, a system may be applied whereby a court or tribunal shall have the power to rule whether or not the applicant may remain on the territory either upon the applicant’s request or *ex officio*. This may only be applied in procedures at the border, provided that the applicant has the necessary interpretation, legal assistance and at least one week to prepare and submit the appeal, and the court or tribunal in such case has the competence to examine the negative decision of the determining authority in terms of fact and law (AIDA Comparator, 2017). In most countries, the appeals, whether judicial or administrative, have automatic suspensive effect. However, in some countries there is no suspensive effect when an application is rejected as “manifestly unfounded” (such as in **Germany**) or certified as “clearly unfounded” (such as in the **UK**).

Expecting asylum seekers to navigate complex procedures shortly after arriving in a new country without appropriate assistance is liable to create incomprehensible asylum procedures (AIDA, 2017b). The provision of legal and procedural information free of charge in procedures at first instance is foreseen in Article 19 of the recast Asylum Procedures Directive. Article 20 ensures free legal assistance and representation in appeals procedures. Article 20(3) specifies that a Member State can opt not to offer free legal assistance and representation in appeal procedures where it considers that the appeal has no tangible prospect of success. Article 21 provides some more details on the conditions for the provision of legal and procedural

information free of charge and free legal assistance and representation. It states that the provision of legal and procedural information can be done by non-governmental organizations or by professionals from government authorities or specialized services of the State. Furthermore, it offers Member States the possibility to limit the provision of legal assistance only to those who lack sufficient resources and/or by legal advisers or other counsellors specifically designated by national law to assist and represent applicants (AIDA Comparator, 2017).

There is no access to state-funded legal advice and/or representation during the first instance procedure in, **Germany, Greece, Italy, and Turkey**. In **Greece**, free legal aid is officially provided to applicants only in appeal procedures before the Appeals Authority, as indicated by Law 4375/2016. In **Sweden**, access to legal advice and/or representation is fully accessible in practice. In **Austria, Poland** and the **UK**, legal advice is provided during the first instance, whereas in **Sweden** both legal advice and representation are provided (AIDA Comparator, 2017). Among RESPOND countries, state-funded access to legal advice and/or representation during the appeal stage is fully guaranteed in **Austria and Sweden**. In **Poland** this only covers legal advice. In **Turkey**, a greater number of bar associations have become involved in legal assistance in international and temporary protection cases, although coverage varies from one region to another (AIDA Comparator, 2017). In **Germany**, asylum seekers can apply for legal aid to pay for a lawyer during the appeal stage. The granting of legal aid is dependent on how the court rates the chances of success (AIDA Comparator, 2017). In 2017, in **Italy**, problems persisted in Milan and Trieste, where a strict merits test was applied by the Bar Councils, and almost all requests for legal assistance were rejected. In **Poland**, legal aid was only introduced in 2015, but in 2017 it was only used in 415 out of 2785 appeal proceedings (AIDA Comparator, 2017). In **Greece**, a new state-run legal aid scheme in appeals procedures was introduced in September 2017, although its capacity is fairly limited (Leivaditi et al., 2020).

More specifically, in **Germany**, rejections of the asylum application based on inadmissibility or a substantial rejection of the asylum claim can be appealed before the courts. The first appeal is examined before the Administrative Court (*Verwaltungsgericht*), the second before the High Administrative Court (*Oberverwaltungsgericht* or *Verwaltungsgerichtshof*) and the final appeal before the Federal Administrative Court (*Bundesverwaltungsgericht*). In case of a simple rejection, an appeal to the Administrative Court has to be submitted within two weeks. If an asylum application is rejected as manifestly unfounded or dismissed as inadmissible, the time frame to submit an appeal is only one week – and the appeal does not have a suspensive effect (Hansel et al., 2019). One of the most frequent reasons for this formal decision is the rejection of the asylum claim on admissibility grounds (Hänsel et al., 2020).

In **Austria**, the person applying for international protection has an appeal period of seven days. This refers to a negative decision in admissibility procedure (Dublin). Generally, there is a two weeks appeal period upon negative decision in the substantive procedure. He/she can turn to the Federal Administrative Court, which must reach a decision within seven days of accepting the case. If the person does not cooperate on his/her return to his/her respective Member State, Basic Welfare Support is reduced by withdrawing, for example, pocket money or schooling and clothing allowances, which are otherwise part of the social benefits (Josipovic and Reeger, 2019). In Austria, persons can generally obtain free legal advice in the appeal proceedings. This includes support and advice in filing the complaint, as well as a clarification of perspectives. Legal advisers may also represent asylum seekers in the proceedings. In Austria, procedural assistance for asylum seekers is provided by two NGOs. An appeal against decisions of the BFA generally has a suspensory effect, which means that in these cases the complainant may remain in Austria until the decision of the Federal Administrative Court (BVwG). In contrast, the complaint in “Dublin proceedings” has no suspensory effect and may only be granted in special cases (Ibid.).

In **Sweden**, the appeal process for decisions of rejection by the Swedish Migration Agency (SMA) regarding migration and asylum cases consists of two instances. The first appeal can be made at the Migration Courts at the County Administrative Courts in Stockholm, Gothenburg, Malmö or Luleå. However, the last and final appeal of the Migration Courts' decisions can only be made to the Migration Court of Appeal at the Supreme Administrative Courts in Stockholm (Shakra and Szalanska, 2020). This court's decision is final and cannot be appealed again. However, the right to appeal in the final instance is not automatically guaranteed to all applicants; most applications require the so-called leave to appeal. This leave to appeal is a permission to review the case granted by the Migration Court of Appeal. There are two grounds for the Migration Court of Appeal to grant this initial permission or leave to appeals. In chapter 54, paragraph 10 of the Swedish code of judicial procedure states that the first ground is if the case is of importance for the guidance of the application of the law. Or, alternatively and in more seldom cases, due to exceptional reasons such as the relief of substantive defects, for example a grave procedural error, or when a decision reached by the court of appeal is obviously the result of a gross oversight or gross mistake (Shakra and Szalanska, 2020).

In **Greece**, an appeal must be lodged within 30 days in the regular procedure, 15 days in the accelerated procedure – in case of an inadmissibility decision or where the applicant is detained – and 5 days in the border procedure and Fast-Track Border Procedure. The appeal has automatic suspensive effect. The procedure before the Appeals Committee shall be generally in writing, and the examination of the appeals shall be performed based on the elements from the case file, without the presence of the appellant. During the examination procedure of the appeal, the Committee shall examine both the legality of the act under appeal and the merits of the case and shall accept or reject the appeal and issue a relevant decision (Petracou et al., 2018, p. 33). A further reform in March 2017 foresees the involvement of rapporteurs appointed by EASO to assist the Appeals Committees in the examination of appeals (AIDA, 2019a, p. 26) (Leivaditi et al., 2020). An application for annulment may be filed before the Administrative Court of Appeals against a negative second instance decision within 60 days from the notification. No automatic suspensive effect is provided (Aida, 2018, p. 26). A twofold procedural framework remained in place by the end of 2018 for the examination of appeals against negative decisions. Appeals submitted after 21 July 2016, when the new Independent Appeals Committees under the Appeals Authority began its operation, are examined by said Committees. Appeals against decisions on applications lodged before 7 June 2013, i.e. before the operation of the Asylum Service, are examined by the so-called "Backlog Committees" under PD 114/2010. Moreover, appeals submitted until 21 July 2016 against decisions rejecting applications for international protection lodged after 7 June 2013 are also examined by the "Backlog Committees" (AIDA, 2018, p. 47)

In **Italy**, according to the Procedure Decree, asylum seekers can appeal against a decision made by the Territorial Committee within 30 days before the competent Civil Court. The appeal can lead to the issuance of a residence permit for special protection instead of granting international protection. This is also the case for the border procedure. The time limit for appealing against a negative decision rejecting the application, so as to obtain subsidiary protection instead of the refugee status or request the border procedure, is 30 days; as for the accelerated procedure, the time limit depends on the type of accelerated procedure applied by the Territorial Commission. "If Safe Country of Origin is applied as a self-standing ground for applying the accelerated procedure, the applicant would have 30 days to lodge an appeal. If, however, the accelerated procedure is applied on the basis of a manifestly unfounded application, which includes safe country of origin grounds, the applicant would only have 15 days to appeal (AIDA, 2019, p. 63). In the border procedure, the appeal is not automatically suspensive. The cases of the accelerated procedure where the appeal does not have an automatic suspensive effect are the following: applications by persons detained in a CPR or Hotspot or First Reception Centre; Manifestly unfounded applications; Applications subject to the border Procedure and applications made after apprehension for irregular entry with the

sole purpose of frustrating issuance or execution of removal order. Appeals against decisions rejecting the application as manifestly unfounded also lack automatic suspensive effect. Decree Law 13/2017 has also removed the possibility of onward appeal before the Court of Appeal if the first appeal has been dismissed, within 30 days of the notification of the decision. A decision of the Civil Court can only be challenged by a final appeal before the Court of Cassation within 30 days (Ibid).

In 2017, acts removing one appeal stage from the international protection procedure were approved in **Germany** (Act to Enforce the Obligation to Leave the Country) and **Italy** (Law Decree No. 13/2017, art. 6(13) (Pannia et al., 2018). The automatic suspensive effect over a first instance negative decision was also eliminated. Moreover, in some RESPOND countries, the introduction of a so-called 'leapfrog appeal' was accompanied by further limitations of applicants' rights and legal guarantees. A *de facto* restriction of applicants' rights during the appeal process can be also observed in **Poland**, where a negative decision causes the automatic withdrawal of social benefits. Due to the tendency of the Appeal Courts to refuse suspensions, asylum seekers appealing a first instance negative decision often remain without any support (Pannia et al., 2018).

In the **UK**, claimants initially appeal to the First Tier Tribunal (Immigration and Asylum Chamber), part of the unified tribunal structure of the Ministry of Justice. Appeals on points of law can be made before the Upper Tribunal with permission from either the First Tier or the Upper Tribunal. Points of law could include the First Tier making a mistake on a point of asylum law, failing to follow a binding decision of a higher court or failing to take into account important evidence. Those applicants who are rejected through the standard procedure can appeal through the judicial system. Since asylum issues are reserved to Westminster (England and Wales legal system), all tribunals are administered centrally through HM Courts and Tribunal Service, which has two tiers: The First-Tier Tribunal and the Upper Tier Tribunal. Appeals against Home Office decisions are heard initially in the First-Tier Tribunal (Immigration and Asylum Chamber). Appeals against First-Tier decisions are referred, with permission, to the Upper Tribunal. If this appeal is also rejected, the applicant may have recourse to a higher court: The Court of Appeal in England and Wales, the Court of Appeal in Northern Ireland, and the Court of Session in Scotland (Foley, 2020).

In **Turkey**, the LFIP provides two separate remedies against negative decisions issued in the regular procedure: "administrative appeal remedy" and "judicial appeal remedy". Applicants who are issued negative decisions may benefit from the administrative appeal through the International Protection Evaluation Commissions (IPEC) within ten days or they may directly submit a judicial appeal within 30 days from the notification of the decision before the competent Administrative Court. Applicants also have the opportunity to continue appealing before the District Administrative Court within 30 days. The decisions of the administrative courts are final, and they cannot be appealed before the District Administrative Courts. During this process, applicants may have access to legal aid. Throughout the appeal procedure, applicants have the right to remain on Turkish territory, except in some cases related with public safety or health or membership in a terrorist or criminal organization. In this context, in October 2016 the Emergency Decree was put into force. The Decree justifies the deportation decision as one that "*may be taken at any time during the international protection proceedings*" against an applicant for reasons of: (i) leadership, membership or support of a terrorist organization or a benefit-oriented criminal group; (ii) threat to public order or public health; or (iii) relation to terrorist organizations defined by international institutions and organizations. Removal decisions may be appealed before the Administrative Court within 15 days from their notification. With regard to temporary protection applicants, TPR itself does not have a dedicated provision listing specific remedies for persons facing negative decisions. Therefore, all acts and actions of competent authorities within the scope of TPR are subject to general rules derived from Turkish administrative law, unless there is a dedicated specific remedy provided by the LFIP itself. During the procedure, the applicant has the right to be represented

by a lawyer and to benefit from state-funded legal aid, like international protection applicants (Gökalp Aras and Şahin Mencütek, 2020, p.29).

Not all countries have laid down specific time limits to be followed by second-instance decision-making authorities and wide discrepancies in the duration of appeal procedures do exist, from 3 days in the fast-track border procedure in **Greece** to 3 months in the accelerated procedure in **Austria** (AIDA, 2017b). Non-compliance with those time frames by the appeal authorities does not entail any consequences. In addition, some countries apply different appeal modalities in the accelerated procedure compared to the regular procedure (AIDA, 2017b).

3.2.3. Vulnerability and Refugee Protection

People belonging to vulnerable groups require special care and protection. Thus, vulnerability assessment procedure is critical and is supposed to be carried out during first registration. On the other hand, the concept of ‘vulnerability’ has increasingly played a central role in legitimizing the approach of countries and IOs (UNHCR’s resettlement scheme) to limiting international protection to reduced numbers of asylum seekers. However, this priority should be considered against a backdrop of established institutional barriers to certain groups. The vulnerability assessment process determines who has the right to asylum (e.g. Greece, UK), relocation (current practices of EU countries regarding unaccompanied children in the Greek islands) or resettlement programs of UNHCR (Lebanon, Turkey, Iraq). As the representative of one NGO from Greece stated: “at this point, we speak of the right to vulnerability instead of the right to asylum” (Leivaditi et. al., 2020, p. 35)

In some European countries, **vulnerability** plays a significant role in the registration of the asylum application. For example, in **Greece**, vulnerable groups and persons in need of special procedural guarantees are guaranteed priority in the registration of their claims. In practice, applicants belonging to vulnerable groups may be able to bypass the requirement of a Skype pre-registration appointment prior to obtaining an appointment with the Asylum Service for registration, as they can be directly referred to the Asylum Service for a registration appointment. Such referrals are made by the Reception and Identification Service (RIS), as well as NGOs closely cooperating with the Asylum Service (AIDA, 2017a).

In **Greece**, the accelerated procedure requires giving priority to vulnerable persons in registration and examination. After completing procedures with Frontex and the police, refugees are first subject to the short interview by EASO, then a vulnerability screening by the Centre for Disease Control and Prevention (known by its Greek acronym KEELPNO) and, secondly, registration with EASO. The vulnerability assessment involves an assessment by a medical specialist and, if needed, by a psychologist to ensure that vulnerable people – such as pregnant women, unaccompanied children, people with disabilities and victims of torture or sexual violence – are identified. In practice, KEELPNO’s lack of adequate number of trained staff caused significant delays in vulnerability assessments, which sometimes in turn delayed the interviews (Leivaditi et. al., 2020, p. 35). Following the EU-Turkey Statement in 2016, the vulnerability assessment in the islands determines which of the two asylum procedures will be followed. People identified as vulnerable (as well as applicants for family unification) enter the regular asylum procedure in Greece, as opposed to the fast-track border procedure which aims at sending people back to Turkey; this means they are exempted from this procedure. Additionally, in certain cases – usually the most vulnerable – the geographical restriction might be lifted and some might be transferred to apartments in the mainland. In practice, in May 2017, Syrian applicants exempted due to vulnerability had their restriction lifted immediately, while non-Syrian applicants exempted due to vulnerability did not have their restriction lifted until they underwent the personal interview. This change in administrative practice as regards the lifting of the geographical restriction of vulnerable non-Syrian applicants has further exacerbated overcrowding on the islands. In the mainland, according to informants such as lawyers, it is up to the discretion of each caseworker of the Asylum Service to decide if the

process should be interrupted and the asylum seeker referred to an agency such as an NGO which is competent to certify vulnerability (known as provision of vulnerability certification as a valid proof); the certificate is recognized by the Asylum Service as complementary to all other documents in the application folder. (Ibid., p. 38). The vulnerability certification is also needed to benefit from the free legal aid or mental rehabilitation services that are often provided by NGOs (Ibid.). The Greek state recently established KEA (Social Solidarity Income) as a financial assistance to the most vulnerable groups (among Greeks, immigrants and refugees); however, to apply, one must submit a wide range of documents, such as a Tax Registration Number (AFM), a Social Security Number (AMKA), a bank account, a copy of an electronic lease agreement and other papers that are not always easily obtained by recognized refugees (Ibid., pp. 54-55).

In terms of vulnerabilities, the **Austria** report speaks of high rates of unaccompanied minors, estimated at 8.6% for 2011 and 2016 (Josipovic and Reeger, 2019, p. 44). As in the other countries, age determination is a problematic dimension which requires physical, dental and radiological screenings. NGOs heavily criticize the methods applied for age assessment as lacking reliability (Ibid.). Also, a micro-level interviewee stated that the evaluation process leads to different results than those claimed (Ibid.).

Germany follows a 'clearing procedure' conducted by especially trained social workers to identify special needs and vulnerabilities among asylum applicants. Certain groups with special vulnerabilities, such as pregnant women or refugees in the resettlement programme or other federal humanitarian programmes, are first registered and accommodated in special arrival centres, where no deportations are executed (Hänsel et al., 2020, p. 43).

In **Poland**, Article 68(1) of Law on Protection provides for vulnerable groups among applicants for international protection (such as minors, pregnant women, single parents) and for what they might need (single room, nursing care, special needs of disabled persons) (Pachocka and Sobczak-Szelc, 2020, p. 66). During asylum interviews, psychologists must be present, along with the officials from the Office for Foreigners, to assess potential vulnerability (Ibid., p. 49). Concerning vulnerability, as emphasized by one meso-level actor from the social organization sector, 'all vulnerable groups are thrown into one bag. They are not offered some kind of individual solution depending on a specific need they have' (Ibid., p. 66). Among the identified vulnerable groups, the largest one is people who have been subjected to physical and/or psychological violence (Ibid., p. 68). Problems include the identification mechanism of vulnerabilities, limited psychological support and accommodation for people within camp-like, closed centres (Ibid., p. 70). One of the main problems raised by NGOs is the detention of asylum seekers, including vulnerable groups such as victims of torture or children. Accordingly, most migration-related pending cases against Poland in the ECtHR are linked to the detention of children and other vulnerable people (Ibid., p. 65). The Dublin Procedure also constitutes another significant problem. As is the case in other countries participating in the Dublin system, the Polish authorities might not possess the necessary knowledge on a given person's situation in the context of their vulnerability because, as the report stressed, the Dublin system does not require sharing this kind of information between the national authorities of involved countries. At this point, the report reminds that "vulnerability is mentioned, per se, only once in the Dublin Regulation, in the context of children, not in any article but in the preamble (Ibid., p. 47).

In **Iraq**, although there is respect for vulnerable groups, particularly during registration, there is no legislation regulating the vulnerability assessment and the provision of special services, especially to children, women, pregnant women and the elderly (Warda and Almaffrajiet, 2020, p. 37). It is reported that children who live outside the camps need psychological and social support services, as well as Iraqi children who are internally displaced. The education of refugee children and children with disabilities has also been affected by the economic and financial situation of the Kurdistan region since 2018, where teachers have not received their salaries for a while (Ibid., p. 17).

Lebanon introduced a ‘humanitarian exception’ in 2014, during the restriction of its law on border control, by launching new visa types for Syrians entering Lebanon. Humanitarian exception refers to “unaccompanied and/or separated children with a parent already registered in Lebanon, persons living with disabilities with a relative already registered in Lebanon, persons with urgent medical needs for whom treatment in Syria is unavailable, and persons who will be resettled in third countries.” This assessment is conducted by the General Security Office during border crossing (Rahme, 2020, p. 14). For asylum seekers within Lebanon, the vulnerability assessments are usually conducted by the UNHCR; those belonging to vulnerable groups are included in the resettlement program lists. However, there are suspicions regarding the credibility of UNHCR assessments (Ibid., p. 27). As for Syrian refugees, NGOs have the leading role in child protection, along with other service areas such as health, education, shelter and others (Ibid. p. 15). Furthermore, a different gender dimension comes into play in Lebanon. While lack of residency has greatly restricted the mobility of male refugees, the General Security Office has been more lenient towards female refugees lacking official papers (Ibid., p. 22).

In Turkey, based on the fieldwork, the most common vulnerability categories appear to be people with disabilities, (individuals displaying mental and psychological illnesses, chronic diseases and physical injuries); children (unaccompanied children, child workers), women and girls (subject to early marriage, gender-based violence, in particular rape, sexual harassment), victims of torture in general and elderly refugees, members of the LGBTI community and minorities. Economic vulnerability is also taken into account by involved actors. Persons belonging to lesbian, gay, bisexual, transgender and intersex populations are not defined within the national law regarding protection. In the case of Turkey, the determination of vulnerability is important not only to access to services but also to benefit from limited resettlement opportunities. Those considered vulnerable are included in the resettlement priority lists that are prepared by DGMM and shared with UNHCR. UNHCR carries out the process of resettlement in third safe countries, both for those under international protection and Syrian refugees. At the border, mainly IOM, UNHCR and their implementing partner NGOs are allowed to determine or help law enforcement actors to determine vulnerabilities. These actors are able to serve on the basis of protocols signed with pertinent state authorities. Differences are observed in the implementation of vulnerability criteria among Syrians and non-Syrians. When asked about the problems they face, most respondents spoke of the ‘determination of vulnerabilities’ as well as of the difficulties in the nature of vulnerabilities. Other common problems include the lack of coordination among related actors, the lack of capacity (in terms of in-service training and knowledge, financial problems and human resources) and disparities between the legal framework and its implementation. According to the meso-level interviews, vulnerabilities are not determined properly, and state agencies do not have adequate statistics and information to be able to follow up on cases. Indeed, the situation was relatively better in terms of vulnerabilities for those under international protection given that, until 10 September 2018, the first registration used to be conducted by the UNHCR and ASAM; they were able to both determine and follow up on cases and activate the relevant actors. The determination of vulnerabilities and unaccompanied cases has since become more challenging due to the lack of capacity and coordination among the actors involved.

3.2.4. The Hotspot Approach

Part of the European Commission's European Agenda on Migration, the Hotspot approach is generally described as providing “operational solutions for emergency situations” through a single location to swiftly process asylum applications, enforce return decisions and prosecute smuggling organizations through a platform of cooperation among EASO, Frontex, Europol and Eurojust. Even though there is no precise definition of the Hotspot approach, it is clear that it became a fundamental feature of relocation procedures conducted by Italy and Greece until September 2017 in the framework of Council Decisions 2015/1523 and 2015/1601 of 14

and 22 September 2015 respectively. Hotspots managed by the competent authority have not required new reception facilities, operating instead from already existing ones (AIDA, 2019, p. 27).

Hotspots are relevant to certain border locations in **Italy** and **Greece**. The Hotspot approach implemented in **Greece** and **Italy** rests on the assumption that national authorities and assisting EU agencies present in border locations are able to quickly and accurately separate those who are in need of international protection from those who ought to be returned. First presented as part of the European Agenda on Migration, the Hotspot approach was meant to assist frontline member states facing exceptional migratory pressure at the EU's external border. Hotspots constitute a geographical space consisting of initial reception facilities. At the same time, Hotspots are also identified as an approach whereby the European Asylum Support Office, Frontex and Europol would "work on the ground with frontline Member States to swiftly identify, register and fingerprint incoming migrants" (Pannia et al., 2018).

In **Greece**, The Greek reception system established by Law 3907/2011 was transformed in April 2015 by what the EU Commission established as the "Hotspot Approach". In particular, the Hotspot approach was first introduced in the European Agenda on Migration as an initial response to the exceptional flows and is implemented in Greece through the legal framework governing the reception and identification procedure under Law 4375/2016. According to Law 4375/2016, newly arrived persons on the Greek islands should be directly transferred to a Reception and Identification Centre, where they are subject to a three-day "restriction of freedom of movement within the premises of the centre" that can be further extended for a maximum of 25 days if reception and identification procedures have not been completed (Leivaditi et al., 2020). Five Hotspots operate under the legal form of Reception and Identification Centres (RICs) in Greece, in the main islands of reception: Lesbos, Chios, Samos, Kos and Leros. In the beginning, Hotspots in Greece operated as open facilities to register, screen and assist arriving migrants and asylum seekers before their swift transfer to the mainland.

In **Italy**, by the end of 2018, four Hotspots were operating in Apulia (Taranto) and Sicily (Lampedusa, Pozzallo, and Messina), down from five in 2017. The Hotspots of Lampedusa and Pozzallo have reopened following temporary closure in 2018 – only partial closure in the case of Lampedusa (AIDA, 2019, p.27).

3.3. Meso-Level Analysis: Practices, Experiences and Perceptions on Asylum Procedures

In the light of country reports on 'refugee protection' of the RESPOND Project, this section of the report reflects the implementation dimension of the legal framework drawing from the experiences and perceptions of meso-level actors such as IGOs, (I)NGOs or state actors that take place within implementation.

3.3.1. Access to Asylum: First Registration, Admissibility Procedure and Dublin Regulation

In all countries, identification for international protection takes place after a person has already entered the country. The asylum procedures in each country display similarities and differences as overviewed already in Section 3.2.3.1 Access to the Procedures and Registration.

In the RESPOND EU members, procedures follow similar general stages: Firstly, the application of admissibility procedure, whereby countries decide whether another EU country

is responsible for the asylum procedure according to the Dublin Regulation III (604/2013). The national process starts only when applications are considered admissible, that is, if a person is unable to find protection in another safe third country or if no other EU member state is responsible for the examination. The admissibility assessment is generally conducted by a Dublin Unit of the MS. If the case is considered admissible, the second stage, which is the examination of the refugee status procedure, begins. It is based on individual interviews (a personal hearing, and possibly interrogation and investigations) and decides on whether the asylum seeker is to be granted protection status or a residence permit. If the refugee status criteria are not found applicable, the possibility of refoulement is examined. If a return would violate the non-refoulement procedure, a subsidiary or other protection status (humanitarian protection or tolerance to stay) may be issued; otherwise, a return decision is taken. If the application is rejected on the ground of inadmissibility, residence may be terminated. The third stage takes place in the case of a negative decision and consists of an appeal against the decision.

The challenges emerging during the application and registration procedures mentioned in the country reports further illustrate the multiplicity of actors, the complexity of procedures, the sophistication of technologies and practices beyond legislations. For example, registering in EU MSs involves the cross-checking of applicants in the European Dactyloscopy (EURODAC) database, the Visa Information System (VIS), the Schengen Information System II (SIS), or in national fingerprint databases for asylum applications elsewhere as well as for criminal records.

Unlike other countries, **Germany** has more decisive practices within the limits and beyond EURODAC (Hänsel, 2020, p. 29-30). It uses assistive technology for identity checks during interviews with asylum applicants that provides the decision-maker further and detailed information about the applicant (Ibid., p. 19) for the first registration. Similarly, authorities in **Austria** are able to inspect geo-data from asylum seeker' digital devices in case of doubts with regard to their identity, their country of origin or their travelling route (Josipovic and Reeger, 2019, p.22).

According to meso-level actors, access to asylum is a difficult process, linked to problems in first registrations and the implementation of several procedures discussed in the Macro Level Analysis Section. For instance, in **Greece**, newly arrived individuals seeking international protection can register at Evros Region, North-eastern Aegean Sea or South-eastern Aegean Sea. However, particularly in the North-eastern Aegean islands (following the EU-Turkey Statement), the numbers of refugees have been increasing; such is the case of Moria Hotspot in Lesbos, which is a RIC, where refugees remain for a long period of time and conditions are described as utterly inhumane (Leivaditi et al., 2020, p. 28-30). According to the Greece report, before the EU-Turkey Statement newly arrived persons arrested at the Greek borders were invited to leave the country within a month without being given the chance to access asylum. However, with the adoption of a new legislation (Law 4375/2016) and following the EU-Turkey Statement, although access to asylum became possible, the conditions at the "pre-registration centres (new arrival tents, quarantine)" have changed. Also, regarding the first registration, participants in meso- and micro-level interviews speak mostly of negative experiences, in particular if new arrivals cannot provide documents for their registration.

In terms of obstacles in implementation, the **Poland** report (Pachocka and Sobczak-Szelc, 2020, p.8) states 2015-16 observed the breakthrough in country's asylum system along with the intense politicization of migration and asylum issues. In particular, eastern border of Poland was highly controlled for impeding the access of asylum seekers. In institutional terms, the Border Guard played a key role in unofficial practices such as pushbacks on the eastern border between Poland and Belarus as well as blocking the asylum applications (Ibid. p. 8, 41).

Regarding the implementation of first registration, the **Sweden** report does not point towards any major problems. Experiences with first registration and the submission of asylum

applications were generally positive for both meso and micro level analyses (Shakra and Szalanska, 2020, p.56). However, during 2015 and 2016, due to the high number of applications and overcrowding, the registration and application procedures have become slower (Ibid.).

Turkey changed its registration procedures radically. Since September 2018, Turkey's migration agency has taken full authority for the RSD procedure by gradually eliminating the parallel procedure carried out with the UNHCR. In principle, international protection applicants gained more flexibility to make the first registration at their point of entrance into Turkey. However, in practice, the **Turkey** report reveals non-standardized practices in registration that have been observable across cities (Gökalp Aras and Şahin Mencütek, 2020). Not only access to rights is challenging for migrants but also, in some cities, even access to asylum, since authorities have temporarily suspended registration for both international (non-Syrians) and temporary protection applicants (Syrians) and are not performing first registrations (Ibid., p.17). This is an important change, and both meso- and micro-level interviews speak of problems linked to registration and to the capacity of the administration and judiciary actors in Turkey (Ibid., p. 45).

As indicated above, **Iraq and Lebanon** are not signatories of the 1951 Convention. In Iraq, the first registration process results in obtaining the (asylum seeker) document, which in turn facilitates the process of obtaining residence and the right of movement, as well as the right to live outside the camps (Ibid., p.26). **Lebanon** has long been relying on the UNHCR to manage the registration, documentation, as well as RSD, in addition to providing assistance (Rahme, 2020, p.15).

In short, in relation to the first registration, both the Dublin procedure and the Hotspot approach appear as the common feature for the EU MSs, despite national procedural differences. On the other hand, the non-EU countries of RESPOND display differences. Due to their close relation with first registration and admissibility procedures in the EU MSs, the implementation of the Dublin Regulation and the Hotspot approach will be mentioned separately. Although Italy and Greece are the most affected countries, this aspect is also of great importance for the other frontline members, which face disproportionate migratory pressures.

3.3.1.1. Implications of admissibility procedures and the Dublin Regulation

The most frequently cited reason to declare an asylum application inadmissible and not proceed with the other stages following first registration is the Dublin III Regulation, which results an unfair share for the frontline countries at the EU borders. Almost all the EU MSs reports, in particular their meso-level analyses, emphasize the need for an alternative process to the Dublin regime, new forms of solidary distribution mechanisms, as well as a stronger harmonization of national asylum procedures within the EU. The Dublin Regulation is criticized by almost all the reports due to its practical deficiencies and its normative premises. Against the background of a heavy burden on southern and frontline Member States, the need for more solidarity in favour of those members and the creation of a durable distribution mechanism were emphasized.

The two frontline countries – **Greece and Italy** – display further problems regarding implementation. Both countries' reports (Leivaditi et. al., 2020; Ibrido and Terlizzi, 2019) speak of the problems created by the Dublin system which create obstacles for international protection in the EU member states due to the fact that the countries at the borders are automatically responsible for processing the application for asylum while there are delays in family reunification. The meso-level expert interviews call for more solidarity among all MSs as well as a fair distribution of responsibilities.

Based on the common EU legal framework and the national legislations, EU members have different criteria for admissibility; however, the most common one is to find out if another country is responsible for carrying out the asylum procedure based on the Dublin Regulation and further international treaties and if the asylum applicant has already been granted protection in another EU member state. Non-EU countries of RESPOND (Turkey, Lebanon and Iraq) have their own admissibility process but not the Dublin procedure.

In terms of implementation and alternatives to the Dublin Regulation, the **Austria** report highlights the problematic aspects of the Regulation and suggests “a bonus system for regions and cities rather than for member states”, which could provide per capita financial support to localities for reception and integration purposes (Josipovic and Reeger, 2019, p. 45).). This report suggests a compulsory allocation quota at the level of Member States appears not to be feasible, at least for the moment, as such a bonus system would represent require a minimum consensus (Ibid.) According to the **Germany** report, among the most significant Dublin-related implications is the negative effect it has on asylum seekers. Because, in practice, rather than avoiding ‘secondary movements’ within Europe, the Dublin Regulation causes asylum seekers to remain in a prolonged and protracted legal limbo for years (Hänsel et al., 2020, p.30, 47). It is also reported that **Germany** has been delaying the transfer of some cases, and therefore the application of the Dublin Regulation, due to the asylum procedure or rights-based problems in component countries such as Italy, Greece (Ibid., p. 27). This shows both the implementation problems regarding the Dublin Regulation but also the different refugee protection capacities among MSs.

In the case of **Greece**, along with existing national criteria, the Dublin Regulation and the EU-Turkey Statement (2016) created “additional administrative steps preceding the substantive examination of asylum applications for the newly arrived persons and they are not allowed to leave the islands before a decision on the admissibility of their cases is taken” (Leivaditi et. al., 2020, p. 45). As in the Hotspot system, the EASO assumes an additional role regarding the Statement and assesses whether applicants should be exempted from the admissibility procedure and transferred out of the Hotspots due to vulnerability reasons. In this regard, the report emphasizes the de facto power of EASO in that it conducts admissibility interviews and makes recommendations (Ibid., p. 46). The meso level interviews of the report mention “the lack of fair hearing and careful consideration of their individual case” by the EASO (p. 47). The report also highlights both the high number of ‘close-ended questions’, which limits the explanations provided by applicants and their chance to clarify inconsistencies in their statements during the EASO admissibility evaluation.

In sum, the Dublin system is highly criticized. The reports of the EU member consortium partners coincide in that there is urgent need for reforms and for finding an alternative to this regime, as well as harmonizing national asylum procedures.

3.3.1.2. Hotspot Approach and Similar Practices (related with first registration process)

The Hotspot approach was developed by the EC in 2015 to support the MSs located at the external EU border. This approach covers registration, identification, fingerprinting and debriefing of asylum seekers, as well as return operations in collaboration with the EASO, Frontex, Europol and Eurojust. In this sub-section we will discuss only registration-related features, where the EASO support teams participate in the asylum applications. Greece and Italy are the first and only two EU members that has been implementing hotspots approach, and the implications thereof are analysed in detail in their country reports.

The **Italy** report defines the system as “prolonged and generalized legal uncertainty concerning the protection of refugees” (Ibrido and Terlizzi, 2019, p.32). Hotspot centres are the places

where the registration starts and, with the cooperation of the EASO, the national authorities in a way classify migrants. The report states that migrants are “classified as asylum seekers or economic migrants based on a summary assessment and in the absence of cultural mediators [...], preventing them from regular access to the asylum procedure” (Ibid., p. 32). In the light of the meso- and micro-level interviews, the report emphasizes the violations of the fundamental rights of asylum seekers and beneficiaries of international protection, who experience poor living conditions in the Hotspots and a lack of support and clear information about the asylum procedure at the point of arrival (Hotspots) (Ibid., p. 35).

The **Greece** report provides significant insider knowledge about the implementation of the Hotspot system drawing from the 34 semi-structured interviews and meso-level interviews conducted with refugees living in Moria Hotspot, as well as a focus-group interview of the University of Aegean research team. The introduction of the Hotspot system results in a considerable increase of asylum applications due to the geographical restriction on the five North-eastern Aegean islands. The provision of operational support under the Hotspot approach covers registration and identification procedures, the response of the EU in the face of the exceptional flows. However, the EU-Turkey Statement resulted in the significant increase of the population living in Moria Hotspot (Leivaditi et. al., 2020). Moria Hotspot turned into not only a RIC, where the first registration of refugees takes place, but also a place where refugees remain for a long time (Ibid., p. 29). The report documents the problems in the first registration process, the serious concerns about reception, living conditions and serious human rights violations in Moria (Ibid.). The waiting period between one’s arrival at Moria Hotspot and registration by EASO is reported as problematic due to the unstandardized procedures (Ibid, p. 34). While some people can register upon their arrival, many others cannot. The report mentions the persistence of systematic failures in the conduct of interviews by EASO officials too (Ibid., p. 46-47).

In general, all the consortium countries of RESPOND have reception and identification centres under different names. After first registration, applicants can be required to stay in designated places such as Distribution Centres, Initial Receptions Centres as in **Austria**, Reception and Identification Centres in **Greece**, AnKer centres in **Germany** and temporary accommodation centres for Syrians and satellite cities of applicants of international and temporary protection as in **Turkey**. Some of those centres serve as the places where international protection applicants enter their first stage of asylum procedure, such as in **Austria**, or they can be only spaces of residence such as accommodation centres for temporary protection holders and ‘satellite cities’ for international protection applicants in **Turkey**. In general, these accommodation centres aim at centralizing the asylum process as much as possible in one location with the main purpose of accelerating asylum procedures and categorizing different groups of applicants. However, as is the case for the majority of RESPOND countries, in particular the meso- and micro-level interviews pointed out that there is an effort to concentrate asylum seekers in a mass, half-closed accommodation centre for the duration of their stay. It has been criticized by refugee right organisations as an intimidation strategy which discourages people and urges them to return voluntarily, or leads to deportation through administrative decisions. In terms of assessing claims, mass accommodation centres are believed to have a negative effect on the individual’s chances in the asylum procedure, due to a lack of information, independent counselling and support networks (Ibid., Hänsel et al., 2020, p. 56). Thus, this new tendency can be seen as an ad hoc measure, in a similar way as Hotspots. In **Turkey**, unlike international protection beneficiaries, Syrians who are under temporary protection can reside at temporary accommodation centres to temporarily or permanently avoid homelessness. Although Syrians cannot be officially detained for irregular border-crossing, they are taken to temporary shelters to be registered (but they are free to leave the camp after); in some cases, our meso-level respondents described applicants being taken to cross-border camps inside Syria, which also is a clear violation of the non-refoulement principle. (Gökalp Aras and Şahin Mencütek, 2020, p. 32).

In general, the Hotspot approach and the similar centralized, camp-like registration and identification centres are criticized by the meso and micro level actors of the RESPOND partner countries mainly because of the inadequate information concerning asylum rights, the detention of newly arrived without access to asylum and return of potential asylum seekers.

3.3.2. Provision of Information on Asylum Procedures: Legal Assistance, Translation, and Consultation Services

Applications for international protection are complex processes. Applicants are supposed to receive all necessary information regarding the asylum procedure. In many countries, applicants for international protection, including applicants for temporary protection, have the right to be represented and assisted by a lawyer. Free access to legal aid is critical in order to receive support and be referred to a competent actor. To overcome language barriers, translators/interpreters are supposed to be present in the interviews of asylum authorities with applicants. The stories of applicants are crucial in the assessment of asylum applications and are interpreted by the third-sides/interpreters. Vulnerability assessment is done based on asylum applicants' statements. Legal aid and interpretation support are partly codified in law and regulations. They are often provided together. In addition to legal aid, asylum seekers also require other support services such as medical and psychosocial assistance.

However, despite their rights on paper, the RESPOND country reports show that, in practice, legal aid and other types of assistance are not easily accessible to all individual asylum seekers. Applicants have to navigate through the complex asylum system on their own, without sufficient information and language proficiency. Most country reports speak of difficulties in accessing asylum due to the lack of legal aid and information, as well as of problems in the detention/removal centres and in appeal processes.

One of the major differences between countries is the presence or lack of systematic and structured legal assistance opportunities. In some countries (Austria, Sweden, Germany etc.), such assistance is provided by non-state actors or registered non-state or semi-state institutions/actors. In other countries (Turkey, Lebanon, Iraq), this is not structured and based on ad-hoc initiatives or asylum seekers' own network. In **Austria**, asylum seekers have the right to demand a legal adviser to attend to normal proceedings or represent the person at the hearing before the Administrative Court. In 2019, **Austria** adopted a law to install a federal agency that will replace non-profit NGOs and private firms and take over activities concerning asylum-seeker accommodation and legal consultation (Josipovic and Reeger, 2019, p. 16). Although well-structured legal assistance is provided, the body deciding on individual cases could be the one providing legal advice for the revision of erroneous first-instance decisions (Ibid., p. 20). Both the expert interviews and also the secondary sources point out the growing concerns among NGOs in relation to the communization of asylum seekers' legal aid services and a potential lack of independence (Ibid., p. 46). In addition, the lack of time for obtaining legal consultation before the first interview at the police was mentioned (Ibid., p. 32).

In **Germany**, "consultation concerning the asylum procedure is provided by two agencies, both funded by the Ministry of Social Affairs. Both offer independent counselling in groups and on an individual basis and provide translators where necessary" (Hänsel et al., 2020, p.42). Counselling is also pictured as problematic in AnKer centres. The BAMF informs asylum seekers only in group discussions about the asylum procedure and return possibilities. The report states that "procedural guarantees such as independent, timely and individual legal counselling are not implemented sufficiently, and may negatively affect the quality of the asylum procedure and increase the danger of erroneous rejection in cases where asylum protection should in fact be guaranteed" (Ibid., p.57). Also, the report underlines that after the introduction of the centre-based and closed system, applicants faced the risk of isolation and violation of their right to independent consultation and legal assistance due to the limited in-

house consultation facilities in those centres' (Ibid.). Similar to **Austria**, the **Germany** report also stresses the importance of independent legal counselling and support structures.

In **Greece**, in parallel to the Asylum Procedures Directive, Law 4375/2016 (Art. 41) provides for the right of asylum-seekers to be informed on the procedure to be followed, their rights and obligations in a language they understand (Leivaditi et. al., 2020, p. 49).). However, although free legal assistance is needed for the entire asylum procedure, it is officially provided to applicants only in appeal procedures. The report highlights serious lacks in the provision of information regarding the asylum procedures and the rights of asylum seekers, of legal aid and of legal representation, in particular in the North-eastern Aegean islands.

Although interpretation is an important part of legal assistance, it appears to be one of the most significant problems in **Greece**. The report states that access to information is difficult due to the complexity of the procedure and the constantly changing legislation and practice, as well as bureaucratic hurdles (Ibid., p.48). It shows that, in the absence of legal assistance, NGOs or other networks undertake this supportive role. Specifically, in the islands, interpreting services and legal support as well as free legal assistance at the appeals stage is provided by NGOs. The meso-level interviews in the **Greece** report highlight the negative implications of the funding cutback in the entire legal aid program implemented by the NGOs. Legal aid to detainees in removal centres is one of most challenging issues at the implementation level, although lawyers from different NGOs, the UNHCR and the IOM occasionally visit some pre-removal centres.

Similar to Greece, **Turkey's** law on asylum envisions a state-funded Legal Aid Scheme for judicial appeals of the international protection procedure (Gökalp Aras and Şahin Mencütek, 2020, p. 29). However, in practice, access to legal assistance seems very limited. The Legal Aid Centre of the Bar Association assigns lawyers for refugees in cases of appeal to deportation decisions, decisions of administrative detention and individual applications to the Constitutional Court (Ibid., p. 43). However, in practice, access to legal aid by applicants is quite challenging, as requests for legal aid are not smoothly transferred to the branches of the Bar Associations (Ibid., p. 43). The fieldwork reveals the problems in assessing asylum and legal assistance, in particular at the removal centres for persons under administrative detention. For detainees, it is not easy to have legal representatives and access to information, in particular information regarding asylum (Ibid., p. 43). Also, those without ID cards (including those under temporary protection) cannot easily benefit from legal aid, because the lack of ID creates problems in getting notary authorization (Ibid., p. 49). Even if the paperwork (permissions) is sorted out, the access of the lawyer to the person under detention has become more difficult (Ibid., p. 54). Furthermore, it is often observed that Syrians are not aware of their rights. In sum, the report claims that legal assistance is not provided in a systematic way or is not always accessible for all asylum seekers.

In **Greece and Turkey**, NGOs appear as the main supplier of free legal aid support and interpreter services. They are the only agencies running the legal aid programmes. They are funded by IOs such as the UNHCR and the EU and INGOs. However, NGOs face legitimacy (permits from host states), capacity and funding problems. Also, as was mentioned earlier for Sweden and the UK, governments have reduced financial support to NGOs providing legal aid, and those cuts in funding create a substantial gap in the legal aid services provided to asylum seekers.

Poland's 2015 Law on Protection also guarantees access to free legal aid for asylum seekers at the appeal stage (Pachocka and Sobczak-Szelc, 2020, p. 33, 53). There are three NGOs entitled to provide such assistance (Ibid.). After a three-year break, only a small number of organizations started to receive funding for projects aimed at improving access to legal advice for persons applying for international protection in 2019 (Ibid., p.38) and providing additional support to foreigners during proceedings (Ibid., p.54).

Compared to other consortium members, **Sweden** provides more structured legal assistance. According to the asylum law in **Sweden**, free legal assistance is provided to asylum seekers throughout the regular procedure, at all appeal levels, and is funded by the state (Shakra and Szalanska, 2020, p.65). The increasing number of asylum applications after 2015 caused problems in accessing quality legal counselling for those in need. (Ibid., p.69). In the field, it is also observed that NGOs are limited in terms of legal support, in particular due to cutbacks in services (Ibid., p. 66). Unlike **Sweden**, in **the UK**, austerity commitments reduced the availability of legal aid services to international protection applicants. (Foley, 2020, p. 14).

In **Iraq**, interviews reveal a lack of legal advice and guidance in the application for asylum or protection. In the case of Syrian refugees, the lack of adequate legal advice to refugees, translation services, the right to object their status and decisions issued against them were highlighted (Warda and Almaffrajiet, 2020, p. 37). Refugees who live in the camps have more access to legal aid and psychological support by humanitarian organizations, while those who lived outside the camps do not receive adequate support and assistance (Ibid., p. 34). Besides humanitarian organizations, families and faith-based organizations play a “substantial role in assisting the displaced, especially the churches in the Christian areas, the Husseiniyas, and the mosques in the areas of Moslem” (Ibid., p. 35). The human capital of existing networks and community support are also essential for refugees in the RESPOND countries.

3.3.3. Procedures During Asylum Proceeding: Interviews, Hearing, Decision-Making

Asylum procedures are highly complex and fragmented procedures at the supranational, international, national and sub-national/local level. We have come across highly fragmented procedures and great differences between RESPOND countries; however, there are also many common features, such as the fact that they have become more restrictive, in line with the EU shared framework through, for example, the Dublin Regulation and admissibility procedures. Since the appeal procedure will be examined separately and the admissibility procedure has already been mentioned, we will focus on the remaining procedures in what follows.

In parallel to other countries, **Austria** started to adopt relatively restrictive procedures at the national level, in particular since 2015, but continued to respect the EU common asylum framework. In this framework, the federal government uses accelerated procedures that are referred to as ‘fast-track procedures’, generally enforced when a person’s application is “evidently unfounded” (Josipovic and Reeger, 2019, p. 23).

Germany is a peculiar case among RESPOND countries in that it displays a great diversity of nation-based procedures. Like Austria, starting from 2015, **Germany** introduced several new procedures, such as the accelerated procedure and different fast-tracking mechanisms, due to “the perceived need to speed up the asylum process [that] arose in the context of the rising number of asylum applications and the overstraining of the national asylum agency” (Hänsel et al., 2020, p. 15). Since 2016, people from safe countries of origin have been generally channelled into the accelerated asylum procedure. This new system also entails some differences regarding nationalities – for example, priority is given to Syrians – which is also reflected at the micro-level analysis (Ibid., p. 33). All in all, these procedures and categories have an impact on asylum seekers and refugees. They create more complexities and, in a way, lead to the clustering and pre-selection of asylum seekers. However, this pre-selecting and clustering of asylum seekers before the procedure has even started has been criticised by NGOs, who speak of an “early separation” (Ibid., p. 55).

Greece has the following procedures: regular procedure, first-instance procedure, regular procedure, accelerated procedure, fast-track border procedure, second-instance procedure /appeal. (Leivaditi et. al., 2020, p. 15-16).

Despite being a non-EU country, **Turkey** also adopts some similar procedures, such as “regular procedure” (with both “prioritised examination” and “fast-track processing”), “admissibility procedure”, “border procedure” and “accelerated procedure” (Gökalp Aras and Şahin Mencütek, 2020, p. 28). As for the regular procedure and its substantive element, the personal interview – also known as hearing – is the process in which asylum seekers have to explain the grounds for their claim before the migration officers or case workers. Interviews/hearings constitute a crucial step within the asylum procedure. The individual’s life or liberty are potentially at stake, as a negative decision may lead to the person’s return to his/her country of origin. The guidelines, directives and rules regarding the interviews of asylum seekers recommend the creation of a relaxed and non-threatening environment for applicants, so that they feel comfortable to disclose relevant and potentially highly personal and sensitive information (Foley, 2020, p. 24). The hearing is supposed to be private. The asylum seeker has the right to bring a legal representative, a lawyer. Decision makers should be trained to act sensitively in hearings with vulnerable people, especially survivors of traumatic experiences such as torture and rape, for talking about such experiences is extremely difficult and painful. (Hänsel et al., 2020, p. 61). The UNHCR may attend the hearings, as it is in charge of monitoring and upholding interview quality (Ibid., p. 18).

The country reports reveal serious problems in the conducting of interviews in practice. In **Greece**, NGO representatives voice concerns that the EASO admissibility interviews do not provide a fair hearing and careful consideration of each applicant’s individual case and need for protection (Leivaditi et. al., 2020, p. 47). A former EASO employee who worked with asylum-seekers at Hotspots on the Greek islands observed that “EASO has violated fundamental standards for asylum interviews and overstepped its competences under European law.” (Ibid., p. 47). The representative of another NGO pointed out the complaints about the way in which the EASO conducts the interviews, both in terms of interpreting and in that too much pressure is put on people” (Ibid., p. 47).

In **Germany**, personal hearings are carried out at arrival centres (Hänsel et al., 2020, p. 41). The country report emphasizes that, from 2015 onwards, the fact that interviewers and decision makers were often trained for this activity in short courses of 2-5 weeks led to poor-quality of hearings and implementations (Ibid., 49). Some of the hearings are carried out like interrogations, intimidating and unsettling asylum seekers. It has been reported that newly-recruited interviewers and decision makers sometimes fail to approach the interview objectively and impartially from the outset and have personal biases such as an aversion to foreigners (Ibid., p. 50). Despite reform efforts and the specific training of staff on how to conduct interviews with vulnerable people, in many hearings this special treatment is not applied (Ibid, p. 61).

Both in **Austria** and **Sweden**, it is reported that problems in hearings lead to multiple complications regarding the quality of first-instance decisions. In **Austria**, there is a widespread sense of incomprehension regarding legal criteria for asylum decisions (Austria report p.8). In **Sweden**, it is generally perceived that many critical issues regarding asylum are “eventually very much up to the individual case worker to decide (Shakra and Szalanska, 2020, p. 40). In **Poland**, as stated by interviewees, there are differences regarding the approach of legal assistance providers between “those who are very committed to their clients’ cases but also those who do not even appear at the hearings of the foreigners” (Pachocka and Sobczak-Szelc, 2020, p. 54).

As revealed by the country reports, even in countries that are highly institutionalized and experienced in terms of refugee policies and are considered destination countries, such as

Germany, Sweden and Austria, one of the most important stages of the RSD procedure is highly problematic.

3.3.4. Experiences with Actors

It is well-known that the interpretation of the law and its implementation are crucial in the operation of the asylum system. Actors in different parts of the system may internalize, challenge or renegotiate rationalizations. Despite legislation, asylum case workers and others involved in the national asylum systems may have a power of discretion (similar to other law enforcement actors) in following procedures and making decisions.

The general observation is that stigma, structural mistrust, hostility and disbelief towards asylum applicants is embedded in the asylum regime and exercised by various actors, from border enforcement to case workers. These may lead to restrictions, arbitrary practices, even intimidation or violence. In **Italy**, “according to several NGOs, the Italian authorities have been making arbitrary distinctions between irregular migrants and asylum/international protection seekers at border crossings, thereby hindering the possibility of submitting protection applications.” (Ibrido and Terlizzi, 2019, p.32). In **Austria** migration experts “criticize the lack of independent border monitoring to control whether persons requesting to lodge an application for asylum are granted access to respective procedures.” (Josipovic and Reeger, 2019, p. 25). In **Poland**, foreigners encountered problems in attempting to submit an application for international protection and pushback practices by the Border Guard at the Polish-Belarusian border-crossing point, as pointed-out by interviews with NGOs (Pachocka and Sobczak-Szelc, 2020, p. 39). According to NGOs, the Border Guards pretend to not hear the calls for protection (Ibid., p.42). In **Lebanon**, there have been widespread instances of class-based discrimination and selection in accessing asylum at the borders, according to meso-level actors such as lawyers (Rahme, 2020, p. 18).

The problems with actors are not only limited to border areas; negative experiences are also mentioned when engaging with actors who assess asylum applicants. Meso level actors also observe these problems. In **Germany**, “structural racism and a structural mistrust built into the bureaucratic and procedural system of the asylum regime in Germany, as well as of personal resentments among employees on various levels” (Hänsel et al., 2020, p. 8). The system is increasingly perceived as highly arbitrary and non-transparent (German report, p.48). In the **UK**, there is “a “culture of disbelief” among case workers and others involved in the asylum system” (Foley, 2020, p. 9). In **Poland**, NGOs believe that a key area negatively affecting the asylum system is the lack of an adequate number of officials possessing skills such as psychological and intercultural sensitivity. Moreover, the existing officials involved in the processing of applications are in a hurry to finalize cases and have a general tendency to issue negative decisions (Pachocka and Sobczak-Szelc, 2020, pp. 61-62). In **Turkey**, the attitudes of actors change from city to city or from person to person, as respondents mention different behaviours. In general, complexity and overcrowding are mentioned as reasons behind misconducts.

3.3.5. Pendulum between Acceleration and Prolongation of Procedures

The work overload occurring since 2015 is an important challenge for countries. Local and national migration agencies conducting first registrations and asylum applications seem incapable of dealing with the large number of asylum seekers. In **Germany**, the increase in the number of applications led to “a near collapse of the reception and procedural systems that had been cut back over previous years, producing in fact a self-made emergency situation” (Hänsel et al., 2020, p.8). **Austria** experienced a work overload within the Immigration Office and the Federal Administrative Court following 2015 (Josipovic and Reeger, 2019, p. 46). **Sweden** was forced to hire a large number of case officers and investigators to assess

applications after 2015-2016, creating concerns about their expertise (Shakra and Szalanska, 2020, p. 9).

The rising number of asylum applications and the overstraining of asylum agencies create the impression that there is a need to speed up the asylum process. There had been large backlogs of asylum applications even before 2015, and applicants had to wait for months or even years to get the final decision. The systematic prolongation of procedures and backlogs are observable at every step of the proceedings. The waiting time to get an appointment for handing in the application was very long for resettlement, family unification, asylum decisions and other processes. The duration of first-instance asylum procedures increased between mid-2015 and mid-2016.

In **Italy**, the waiting time is longer and can last up to two or three years. As one legal expert tellingly states: “the greatest problem [asylum seekers] perceive is the length of time they wait. It might happen that [asylum seekers] apply in 2015, the Territorial Commission schedules a meeting in 2016 and gives them an answer in 2017... this is social exclusion” (Ibrido and Terlizzi, 2019, p. 39). “The long waiting time is connected to the asylum procedure, particularly in combination with a ban on taking up formal employment” (Josipovic and Reeger, 2019, p.8). **Germany** faces similar challenges in the prolongation of asylum decisions. In 2017, the average time to process an asylum application at the BAMF and reach a final decision was 10.7 months (including court cases); in mid-2017 it was 12.6 months. In 2018, the average time until a BAMF decision was reached slightly decreased to 8 months, but the total duration, including appeals, rose to 16.8 months in mid-2018 (Hänsel et al., 2020, p. 47). In **Austria**, statistics showed an average of 16.5 months at the end of 2017. It went down to 2.6 months in 2018. In **Poland**, according to the opinion of the Office for Foreigners’ employees, the average duration of proceedings is less than 6 months; however, there have been longer procedures of even 1.5-2 years, but these were exceptional and quite complicated cases (Pachocka and Sobczak-Szelc, 2020, p.50). Micro-level respondents underlined the long durations of asylum procedures (Ibid., p. 9) In **Sweden**. At the beginning of 2012, the waiting period for a decision was no longer than 3 months and the fastest decisions were issued within 20 days. Those arriving after 2015 had to wait for 10 to 27 months to receive the first-instance decision (Shakra and Szalanska, 2020, p. 60). In **Greece**, the fast-track border procedure aims to accelerate the process, but it does not seem to be serving the acceleration of asylum applications.

The performance of non-EU countries seems to be better regarding registrations and the issuing of residence permits, particularly for Syrians. In **Iraq**, the duration of the procedures is quite short, most procedures for residence and asylum take a few weeks or one to two months, with a few exceptions that have lasted 6 months (Warda and Almaffrajiet, 2020, p. 26). In **Turkey**, the waiting time for Syrians to obtain permits (as temporary protection holders) is short. However, applicants for international protection face a long waiting period from their first registration to their interview.

Both accelerations and prolongations have created multiple problems in the quality of first-instance decisions. It is widely reported that accelerated asylum procedures have had a negative impact on the quality of decisions in **Germany, Sweden** and **Greece**. In **Austria**, “an implementation gap was observable in relation to the quality of first-instance decisions by the Immigration Office, as well as a in the context of rejected asylum seekers and effectively conducted returns” (Josipovic and Reeger, 2019, p.8)

3.3.6. Appeal Procedure

The national reports reveal that the speeding up of applications had an unintended consequence, namely the increase in the rate of appeals following negative decisions. The national report of **Germany** indicates that it reached 76 percent in 2018, increasing the

workload for appeal agencies. The average duration of appeals rose significantly, in parallel to the rise in the number of applications (Hänsel et al., 2020, p. 58). As a result, applicants have to wait up to several years until their cases are processed. The report highlights that refugees found themselves in limbo and were forced to stay in the AnKER centres, with more restrictions on their freedom of movement inside the city or country (Ibid., p. 45).

In **Italy**, the majority of applicants received a negative first-instance decision and submitted an appeal (Ibrido and Terlizzi, 2019, p.39).

In **Austria**, there have been “improved appeal conditions for applicants following the institutional reform of 2014” (Josipovic and Reeger, 2019, p. 9).

Sweden has a highly institutionalized appeal process and specific courts (Shakra and Szalanska, 2020, p.22). The report highlights a high performance.

In the **UK**, the appeal process is quite important because many cases are rejected erroneously at the Home Office stage. The rejected applicants can appeal to the judicial system. The national report reveals that “a significant proportion of those who apply for asylum in the UK face initial rejection, but a sizeable majority appeal and a quarter of those receive their status” (Foley, 2020, p. 9).

In **Greece**, there are serious concerns about the composition of the Independent Appeals Committees after the passing of Law 4375/2016. The report states that it is believed that reforms in the composition of the committees resulted in a sharp increase of negative decisions in the second instance (Leivaditi et. al., 2020, p. 42). Recognition rates at the appeal level are reported as a significantly low percentage of the total in- merit decisions issued in 2018: 91% were negative (Ibid., p. 43). In addition, the implementation shows that second-instance decisions issued by the Independent Appeals Committees for Syrian applicants systematically uphold the first-instance inadmissibility decisions if no vulnerability is identified (Ibid., p. 43)

In **Turkey**, the report emphasized that the state-funded Legal Aid Scheme is available for judicial appeals (Gökalg Aras and Şahin Mencütek, 2020, p. 29). The transition period of RSD from UNHCR to DGMM, the lack of adequate capacity, preparation issues and problems in accessing legal aid have had a negative impact on appeal stages, as mentioned by meso-level respondents (Ibid., p. 47). Although bar associations are reported as quite committed to providing legal assistance to refugees in court cases, it is stated that removal orders/ deportation decisions were frequently issued without proper judicial investigation or appeal processes (Ibid. 54, 79).

In **Lebanon**, one cannot apply for refugee status; accordingly, there are no asylum decisions to appeal. The lack of legal status makes Syrian refugees prone to different types of abuse, such as arbitrary detention, possibly accompanied by physical and psychological torture (Rahme, 2020, p. 25).

3.3.7. Detention

People fleeing persecution and conflict who manage to reach certain country borders may find themselves subjected to consecutive forms of deprivation of liberty. Since the beginning of 2018, there has been an emerging trend in most RESPOND countries. After a person has been released from the waiting zone and has subsequently been held in police custody, he or she is admitted into the territory and issued an obligation to leave, as well as an administrative detention order for the purposes of removal. As discussed previously, this implementation has become quite centralized and, despite the right to apply for asylum from detention centres, many reports stated problems regarding access to asylum.

In **Austria**, following the 2017 Aliens Law Amendment Act passed by the new federal government consisting of a conservative, right-wing coalition, control measures have increased and now include detention practices (Josipovic and Reeger, 2019, p. 20). In **Germany**, although the detention of asylum applicants has been declared unlawful, the country report speaks of difficulties in accessing legal counselling when in detention (Hänsel, Hess and Schurade, 2020, p. 66).

In **Greece**, despite the clear provision within the Constitution (Article 6, par. 1), asylum policies have become quite restrictive since the 2000-2010 decade, and detention practices are common (Leivaditi et. al., 2020, p. 17). The report states that, due to the increasing numbers, “exceptional” or “fast-track” procedures have been used to cover unlawful detention practices, in particular at the RICs (Ibid., p. 15). The EU-Turkey Statement and the following national law (Law 4375/2016) are considered turning points regarding detention. Before, TCNs arrested at the Greek borders were not taken to pre-removal centres for detention and were given notice to leave the country within the period of one month. Detention for removal was considered only if the person was arrested again within that period. However, since the Statement, they are taken to Hotspots and RICs, which have turned into big detention facilities (Ibid., p. 25). The report also mentions a new and problematic pilot project in line with the Joint Action Plan (2015) on the implementation of the EU-Turkey Statement (2016): the “Low-Profile Scheme”, implemented in Lesbos, Kos and partly Leros (Ibid., p. 52). It is described as “a highly systematized and arbitrary practice of detention” and foresees the immediate administrative detention of people of certain nationalities with low recognition rates in the EU upon the completion of their registration and identification procedures (such as people from sub-Saharan countries, Pakistan and Bangladesh, etc.); this condition is upheld until their entire asylum procedure is concluded (Ibid.). The Greek research team also conducted a roundtable meeting, where this scheme was described by the majority of meso-level participants as discriminatory, a kind of “containment policy” that functions as a new norm for Greece and as a pilot project for the entire EU. Based on the meso- and micro-level interviews, although some national and international NGOs, the UNHCR and IOM have been able to pay occasional visits to detention centres (pre-removal centres), the report highlights systematic and serious deficiencies such as lack of access to the asylum system, the detention of children, the issuing of detention orders that lack individual assessments, inadequate conditions of detention and a high risk of deportation among detainees. The report provides empirical data from the pre-removal detention centre established in 2017 inside Moria Hotspot (Ibid., p. 53-54).

Like Greece, **Italy** too has adopted more restrictive policies since the 2000-2010 decade and intensified detention practices. With the adoption of the so called “Bossi-Fini Law”, more restrictive provisions concerning the expulsion and detention of migrants have been implemented (Ibrido and Terlizzi, 2019, p. 20). As the second country implementing the Hotspot and one of Europe’s frontline countries, new arrivals in Italy are also stuck in Hotspot centres for several weeks and are sometimes subjected to de facto detention for long periods (Ibid., p. 32).

Poland’s report reveals the detention of vulnerable groups such as victims of torture or children – which is allowed by the national legislation – and explains the long-standing struggle of NGOs and the relevant cases at the ECtHR, for instance Bistieva and others v. Poland. The report states that most recent cases of detention are related to the Dublin System (Pachocka and Sobczak-Szelc, 2020, p. 65-66).

As for the **UK**, the country report describes detention practices as “a notable feature of the UK system”, and supports this claim with figures showing that roughly half of all applicants face with detention, given that the UK has not ratified EU Returns (Foley, 2020, p. 18). The UK is one of only a few countries in the Council of Europe not to fix an upper time limit on immigration detention; in fact, detention cases have recently increased significantly (Foley, 2020, p. 31). The fieldwork behind the country report shows that it is common for immigrants to remain in

detention for extended periods. The 2001 Detention Centre Rules provide the details on requirements such as freedom of movement and association as much as possible, consistent with maintaining a safe and secure environment, and encourage detainees to make the most productive use of their time. However, the micro- level interviews reveal that criminalization narratives regarding detainees are common. The report emphasizes the formally recognized link between administrative detention and criminality and addresses concerns regarding the increased use of detention centres, which are mainly former prisons. Although families with children are an exception to this rule, narratives surrounding the detention system are normally very explicitly linked to immigration control (Ibid., 32).

In **Turkey**, the national law defines two-fold immigrant detention, which creates differences regarding international and temporary protection. The report states that, in practice, due to the lack of capacity and the exceeding of maximum time limits, detainees are released with the 'invitation' to leave the country. However, they are required to present themselves at the competent security authorities at certain time intervals. Although they have the right to apply for asylum at the removal centres, the meso- and micro-level interviews describes the lack of information and interpretation and problems regarding access to asylum as common. There are many cases of people being refused entry at the border and returned without having their protection needs examined; there are also many non-Syrian respondents who had their applications rejected (Gökalp Aras and Şahin Mencütek, 2020, p. 29). As for Syrians, although they cannot be the subject of administrative detention, there are reported cases of applicants being temporarily or permanently banned from residing outside temporary accommodation centres. When this provision is applied, it is forbidden for beneficiaries to leave the camp, a condition that can be viewed as form of state detention. The fieldwork on which the national report is based reveals that, although they are not officially detained, they are taken to temporary shelter centres and, in some cases according to meso-level respondents, to cross-border camps inside Syria, in what is a clear violation of the non-refoulement principle (Ibid.).

In **Iraq**, at least according to the fieldwork, no Syrian refugees have been detained; however, there are many deportation cases (Warda and Almaffrajiet, 2020, p. 29). In **Lebanon**, the 2014 restrictive October policies have opened the door to practices such as detention, referred to as "arbitrary detention" within the report (Rahme, 2020, p. 22). Although the decision of detention can be challenged before an administrative judge, general judicial authorities rarely scrutinise or evaluate the legality of detention; considering the lack of access to legal counselling, this path is seldom taken (Ibid., p. 25).

3.3.8. Deportation, Return and Readmission

In **Germany**, reports generally highlight a shift from reception to return policies, further enforcing control via an "acceleration of the asylum procedure and an extension of a policy of camp-ization" (Hänsel, Hess and Schurade, 2020,2020, p. 73). The emphasis on the 'deportation gap' or the 'obligation to return' dominated the public debate in 2016. The macro-level analysis of the report shows that accelerated procedures are closely linked to return policies. Accordingly, return is common among asylum seekers from countries of origin considered safe or as a sanction of asylum seekers accused of having deliberately provided false information about their identity (Hänsel, Hess and Schurade, 2020, p. 16). In addition to the Dublin Regulation, **Germany** has bilateral readmission arrangements (administrative arrangements) with **Greece, Italy** and **Spain** since 2018, although the numbers of such returns are reported quite low (Ibid.)

In **Germany**, the organization and execution of deportations and voluntary returns are the responsibility of the federal states. Germany has a special accelerated process, where the asylum applicants are also transferred to the AnKER centres that may facilitate deportation and voluntary returns. In those centres, information regarding voluntary return is provided, often in a more detailed and effective way than the information given on the asylum process (Ibid. p.

57). As a protective barrier against deportation, 'tolerated stay' applies to persons who must leave the country but cannot currently be deported due to serious illness, separation of families or the absence of travel documents, or if the deportation is impossible due to the situation in the country of origin (such are the cases of **Iraq** and **Afghanistan**). The same does not apply for **Austria** (Ibid.). Despite its extranational arrangements and bilateral administrative return arrangements with **Greece** and **Italy**, **Germany** occasionally suspends the implementation of the Dublin Regulation due to the problematic conditions prevailing in the two frontline countries (Ibid., p. 31-32).

As in **Germany**, in **Austria** too there is an increasing attention to returns, and the new regulations result in further restrictions on migration control, including return policies. The **Austria** report highlights the relevance of the interconnected phases, from first-instance decisions to appeals, as well as the communization of legal aid services in return policies (Josipovic and Reeger, 2019, p. 8). However, the report highlights several problems in the implementation stages. The negative impact of the considerable work overload, as well as the communization of legal aid services provided to asylum seekers, prevent a fair and effective execution of return policies. As the meso-level interviews pointed out, the negative decision in the second instance, which requires migrants to leave the country, provides limited time for preparation; other conditions, such as the use of handcuffs, were reported as problematic. In terms of voluntary returns, **Austria** reports a low rate of returns, which are supported by some financial state incentives; the largest group opting for voluntary return is that of Iraqis, followed by Afghans. However, the report also highlights that Afghans have predominantly faced detention and forced return.

The **Sweden** report (Shakra and Szalanska, 2020, p. 10) states that, in 2019, the national asylum authority became one of the first within the EU to review the security situation in Syria and issue a new guideline allowing the return, in some cases, of Syrian asylum applicants to assessed safe parts in Syria. The government has taken several measures to speed up this return and improve its conditions, such as checking workplaces (Ibid., p. 31). In addition, the Swedish government once again increased the number of detention centres, as occurred in many EU countries, to speed up returns and deportations.

As in Austria and Germany, after the EU-Turkey Statement and the introduction of Law 4375/2016, **Greece** too introduced additional procedures to accelerate deportations and returns, such as "exceptional" and "Fast-Track Border" procedures, resulting in detention at RICs (Leivaditi et. al., 2020, p. 15-16). Also, the Hotspot approach and its centres focus on return operations and temporary relocation. Greece has created pre-removal centres within these spaces, in accordance with the provisions of the Returns Directive. Thus, it seems that the general tendency to keep the population of concern under control is to facilitate returns. The report reveals that, in Greece, both the Hotspot approach and the EU-Turkey Statement have had a negative impact on asylum procedures. Before the implantation of the mentioned policies, although long delays were still common, the situation was much better in terms of rights. At least applications were examined individually, and case-based differences were respected. However, the Statement has brought about the involvement of more actors such as EASO, Europol, Eurojust, and the main rationale behind the procedure is to examine whether new arrivals can be sent back to Turkey (Ibid., p. 45-46). In practice, since the Statement, it remains unclear whether someone could be readmitted at the very last moment, as legal actors might proceed to legal remedies a few minutes prior to departure (Ibid., 53).

The **Poland** report mentions that Ukrainians who have received a negative decision on their asylum applications often become beneficiaries of subsidiary protection after the appeal process. Thus, they receive residence permits on humanitarian grounds during the return procedures (Pachocka and Sobczak-Szelc, 2020, p.13). In the context of the Dublin system, Poland has close cooperation with EU Member States; among them, Germany appears as a key partner (Ibid., p. 35).

The **Turkey** report states that there are many cases of violation of the non-refoulement principle for both international and temporary protection. For example, deportation decisions do not mention the country that this person will be deported; this is only revealed at the very last moment, creating problems in the provision of legal assistance. The person to be deported is generally detained in removal centres, where only legal representatives, lawyers and bar association members have access; however, given that this access is also hindered, legal assistance is highly problematic. In addition, many of the meso-level interviews within the report speak of very strict time limitations (Gökalp Aras and Şahin Mencütek, 2020, p. 40). The report also critically refers to the “voluntary returns”, shedding serious doubt regarding their “voluntary” character, and describes many unlawful practices (Ibid., p. 41). Also, the report states that returns have been more visible since the beginning of 2018. In particular, following certain cross-border military operations, even some municipalities in Istanbul began to present “voluntary return” campaigns with incentives such as the covering of expenses (Ibid., p. 42). Many meso-level experts, with the exception of official officers, mention that voluntary returns are not voluntary at all.

The **Lebanon** report (Rahme, 2020) mentions deportations in the case of irregular entries of Syrians to **Lebanon**, as well as an increasing pressure on Syrian refugees to return. This is justified by the Lebanese officials with the claim that refugees are only being sent back to regions of Syria that are safe. Regarding returns, although the UNHCR has stated that it cannot promote or facilitate returns of refugees before it has confirmed safety conditions in Syria, these have been conducted by Lebanon since 2018. The main reasons behind the returns are linked to the harshness of policies and the deteriorating livelihood and security conditions in Lebanon, rather than to the consideration of Syria as a safe country. (Ibid., p. 25-26)

Unlike **Lebanon** and **Turkey**, **Iraq** has not yet called for a mass return of Syrians, and it rarely **executes** detention and deportations. Nevertheless, the micro-level interviews mention deportations of persons in case of multi-level entries and back-and-forth mobilities between Iraq and Syria (Warda and Almaffrajiet, 2020, p. 30). The report also describes nationality-based differences in implementation; for example, Arabs are the ones who are sent back the most, in particular if they do not speak Kurdish (Ibid.). The importance and official emphasis placed on voluntary returns are mentioned, but neither meso-level nor micro-level interviews reveal any forced migration.

3.3.9. Protection of Families and Family Reunification

Family reunification in the country of asylum is often the only way to ensure respect for the right to family life and family unity. Restoring family unity is an important part of international protection. In general, family reunification refers to a special asylum procedure for families. The right to family life is ubiquitous in international and European legal standards and a necessary prerequisite to any meaningful effort towards settlement in a host society. The Family Reunification Directive does not squarely cover refugees and beneficiaries of subsidiary protection alike, as it does not apply to persons “authorized to reside in a Member State on the basis of a subsidiary form of protection in accordance with international obligations, national legislation or the practice of the Member States”. As such, lower protection standards in terms of family reunification target those granted subsidiary protection (AIDA, 2016b).

In the aftermath of increased refugee arrivals in Europe in 2015, the year 2016 was marked by national measures aimed at restricting family reunification for protection beneficiaries. Recent legislative reforms in countries such as **Austria**, **Germany** and **Sweden** have imposed stricter conditions on the enjoyment of family reunification (AIDA, 2016b). Several countries have excluded subsidiary protection beneficiaries from the right to family reunification, such as **Greece**. This is now also the case in **Sweden**, following the entry into force of the temporary law from July 2016 to July 2019, where the exclusion of beneficiaries of subsidiary protection

from family reunification affects only those applying for asylum after 24 November 2015 (AIDA, 2016b). **Germany** has recently excluded subsidiary protection holders from family reunification from March 2016 to March 2018 (AIDA, 2016b). In **Turkey**, beneficiaries of conditional refugee status are excluded from family reunification rights, unlike subsidiary protection beneficiaries, who are granted family reunification rights.

More specifically, in **Germany**, the right to family reunification was restricted in 2016 with the 'New Regulation on the Right to Family Reunification', as part of Asylum Package II, to only refugees with full asylum or refugee status under certain conditions and only for nuclear family members. For refugees with subsidiary protection status the right was suspended until 16 March 2018. As of 1 August 2018, family reunification for nuclear family members of subsidiary protection beneficiaries is limited to 1,000 persons per month for the whole of Germany and presupposes humanitarian grounds (Hänsel et al., 2020). Thus, only those receiving full asylum or refugee status and their nuclear family members were given this right (Hänsel et al., 2020, p. 15, 62). Many interviewees spoke of long procedures, heavy bureaucracy and age limitations for minors, as well as a restriction for subsidiary protection in relation to family reunification (Ibid., pp.63-64). The fieldwork also reveals problems in the performance of the embassies in this respect, leading to a systematic prolongation of procedures and backlog. The number of rejections has been increasing, in particular referring to petitions coming from Greece in Germany (Ibid. p. 64).

In **Austria**, individuals receiving asylum or subsidiary protection may conduct a family reunification process under certain conditions. (Josipovic and Reeger, 2019). A three-month deadline for submitting an application was introduced on 1 June 2016 in Austria, despite concerns expressed by civil society organizations on the difficulties facing family members who want to access an Austrian embassy in person to file an application (AIDA, 2016b). If family members lodge an application for international protection, their cases are jointly examined (but they all receive a separate written decision). Thus, granting protection to one family member automatically leads to protection being granted to the remaining family members. However, the legal term of family remains very narrow, covering the relationship between underage unmarried children and their parents, marital or registered partners, as well as legal representatives of underage children (Josipovic and Reeger, 2019, p. 41). The report also reveals numerous bureaucratic obstacles, challenging deadlines and requirements for family reunification. Along with the meso-level interviews, the report also reflects the refugee's experiences regarding family reunification. A large number of our respondents have entered alone as single males and, due to the difficult bureaucratic problems, they are not planning to bring their families. In the case of women, the report states that most of them have already come with their close family members and, therefore, are not seeking further reunification (Ibid.). Thus, gender-based differences are observed.

As other EU members, **Sweden** too offers more limited possibilities for family reunification since 2015. Recent legal developments provide for the possibility of family reunification for subsidiary protection beneficiaries. The family reunification application must have been lodged from 20 July 2019 until no later than 20 October 2019 (Shakra and Szalanska, 2020). Furthermore, family reunification has been greatly restricted following the Temporary Act, extended with another act for another two years, until 19 July 2021 (Shakra and Szalanska, 2020, p. 9). In line with other EU MSs, the number of granted family reunification and asylum applications has decreased (Ibid. 25). The report characteristically mentions that, out of 61 interviews, only one applicant was able to unite with her 5-year-old son (Ibid., p. 62). The report states that almost all respondents were aware of the family reunification regulations, and most were discouraged to invite any of their family members due to the increasing rate of rejections and the complexity of the requirements (Ibid.).

In **Greece** according to PD 131/2006 transposing the Family Reunification Directive as supplemented by PD 167/2008 and amended by PD 113/2013, only recognized refugees have

the right to apply for reunification with family members who are third-country nationals residing in their home country or in another country outside the EU. "Family members" include: (a) Spouses; (b) Unmarried minor children; (c) Unmarried adult children with serious health problems which render them incapable to support themselves; (d) Parents, where the beneficiary solemnly declares that he or she has been living with them and taking care of them before leaving his or her country of origin and that they no longer have other family members to care for and support them; (e) Unmarried partners with whom the applicant has a stable relationship, which is proven mainly by the existence of a child or previous cohabitation, or any other appropriate means of proof (AIDA, 2019, p.181).

Moreover, after the adoption of Law 4375/2016, the entire framework of the Dublin Regulation and, more specifically, of Family Reunifications has been defined. According to article 60 of Law 4375/2016, vulnerable cases as well as applicants for family reunification are supposedly excluded from the Fast Track Border Procedure (Leivaditi et al., 2020). An applicant for family reunification is supposed to apply within three months of the date on which the asylum demand has been lodged for preferential treatment regarding material conditions such as full Social Security Certificate, tax declaration for adequate annual personal income and certificate for sufficient accommodation (Aida, 2019, p.181). According to Article 23 PD 141/2013, as amended by Article 21 L 4375/2016, family members of the beneficiary of international protection who do not individually qualify for such protection are entitled to a renewable residence permit which must have the same duration as that of the beneficiary (AIDA, 2019, p.183)

In **Italy**, since the entry into force of LD 18/2014, the family reunification procedure governed by Article 29bis TUI, previously issued only for refugees, is applied to both refugees and beneficiaries of subsidiary protection. Beneficiaries can apply as soon as they obtain the electronic Residence Permit – that means several months in some regions – and there is no maximum time limit for applying for family reunification. Contrary to what is provided for other third-country nationals, beneficiaries of international protection do not need to demonstrate the availability of adequate accommodation and a minimum income. They are also exempted from subscribing a health insurance for parents aged 65 and over (AIDA, 2019, p.141) Beneficiaries may apply for reunification with:

- (a) Spouses aged 18 or over with whom they are not legally separated;
- (b) Minor children, including unmarried children of the spouse or born out of wedlock, provided that the other parent has given his or her consent;
- (c) Adult dependent children if, on the basis of objective reasons, they are not able to provide for their health or essential needs due to health condition or complete disability;
- (d) Dependent parents, if they have no other children in the country of origin, or parents over the age of 60 if other children are unable to support them due to serious health reasons (Ibid.).

Where a beneficiary cannot provide official documentary evidence of the family relationship, the necessary documents are issued by the Italian diplomatic or consular representations in his or her country of origin, which makes the necessary checks at the expense of the person concerned. The family relationship can also be proved by other means, including a DNA test or UNHCR involvement. The application cannot be rejected solely for lack of documentation. As for the status and rights of family members, according to the law family members who do not have an individual right to international protection have the same rights recognized to the sponsor. Once in Italy, they get a residence permit for family reasons, regardless whether they have previously resided in the country irregularly present. These provisions do not apply to family members who should be excluded from international protection (Ibid.).

In **Turkey**, the Turkish Red Crescent (*Kızılay*) is the one authorized to conduct family reunification. The **Turkey** report (Gökalp Aras and Şahin Mencütek, 2020, p. 56-57) states that

the programme has a strong training dimension in psychosocial support. The Programme is financed by European Union Civil Protection and Humanitarian Aid Operations. The community centres take requests for missing family members, then channel the request to *Kızılay*, who communicate with Red Cross (Ibid.).

Unlike EU members and **Turkey**, in **Iraq** there are no opportunities for family reunification, and the national law does not provide legal basis for reuniting with the rest of the family, as is the case in Europe (Warda and Almaffrajiet, 2020, p. 29). Thus, to obtain international protection, all family members must enter the country. On the other hand, the micro-level interviews show that transnational networks and ties play an important role in family reunification (Ibid.). Furthermore, there appears to be certain confusion among Syrians in **Iraq** on whether full refugee status or even subsidiary protection is enough for conducting family reunification in **Germany**.

In sum, in harmony with developments following 2015, the country reports once again speak of more restrictive policies, this time regarding family reunification, as well as of an increasing number of rejections in most RESPOND countries.

3.4. Micro-Level: Experiences and Perceptions of Applicants for Protection

Although some reference has already been made in previous sections, under this heading we will refer to the common problems and nation-based differences regarding the micro level. Due to the focus of the country reports (from first application to final decision and the evaluation of refugee protection), micro-level responses are mainly related to the perceptions and experiences of interviewees on the refugee procedure.

The differential treatment of Syrian asylum seekers compared to other nationalities is commonly mentioned by interviewees in the majority of countries. Refugees from Syria appear as a relatively more favoured group, enjoying a high level of acceptance and shorter waiting periods (Josipovic and Reeger, 2019, p. 30; Hänsel et al., 2020, p. 33). In addition, according to the meso-level interviews, applicants from certain nationalities appear as having no chance in the **German** asylum system and are systematically excluded (Ibid., 55). In **Sweden**, the same perception prevails regarding the differentiation between asylum seekers from Syria and other countries (Shakra and Szalanska, 2020, p. 62). On the other hand, the Austria reports reveals that Afghans appears as the most disadvantaged national group among refugees (Josipovic and Reeger, 2019, p. 23), and the similar nation-based discrimination was also mentioned regarding many of the other RESPOND countries such as Sweden and Turkey.

Although **Austria**, **Sweden**, and **Germany** provide relatively structured procedures regarding asylum, most interviewees in RESPOND countries mention **confusion and a lack of orientation in relation to the administrative steps of the asylum procedure**. Most respondents stated they were confused about the steps of their own asylum procedure, and some explicitly referred to their limited understanding upon arrival, as well as to the lack of knowledge regarding their legal statuses.

The negative impact of macro-level restrictions in the post-2015 period is also mentioned by the interviewees at the meso-level. The **increase in the number of arrivals** in 2015 is mentioned as one of the major reasons behind this change, and the enormous **backlog of cases** as the consequence. This fact is also reflected at micro-level interviews, for example, in **Poland**, problems mounted in the submission of applications for international protection, in particular at the border-crossing points were reflected through the experience of asylum applicants (Pachocka and Sobczak-Szelc, 2020, p.9). In some cases, asylum seekers and NGOs had already protested against the lengthy asylum procedures in previous years;

however, as the **Germany** report indicates, the system reached breaking point in the summer of 2015 (Hänsel et al., 2020, p. 45), which leads us to even more **prolonged procedures**. Many interviewees in **Germany** described this long waiting period without receiving information and without understanding the reason for the **delays** as highly frustrating and psychologically demanding (Ibid, p. 47, 49).

The negative impact of the Dublin Procedure is also highlighted by refugees at the micro level; based on the interviews, the outcome of the Procedure is the opposite of its intended objective. It results in prolonged and protracted situations of legal limbo (Ibid., p. 30). In **Sweden**, experiences with the registration and submission of asylum applications were generally positive according to the micro-level interviews, but the majority of the respondents who arrived to **Sweden** in 2014 and 2015 complained about the long and slow processes and the duration of the procedures (Shakra and Szalanska, 2020, p. 56). The experiences of asylum seekers also reflect the incapacity of institutions to deal with such a large number of asylum applications (Ibid.).

As a consequence, **duration of the procedures** varies. However, interviewees in most RESPOND countries spoke negatively of lengthy bureaucratic procedures. The feeling of being in “legal limbo” and the sense of “uncertainty” appear as common points among all interviewed asylum seekers, in particular for some specific nationalities such as Afghans and Iranians (Ibid., p. 31). In **Poland**, the duration of the procedures was also highly criticized (Pachocka and Sobczak-Szelc, 2020, p. 49). The **UK** report also mentions long waiting periods for claims (and appeals) to be processed (Foley, 2020, p. 30). Asylum seekers also perceive processes and decisions as highly **arbitrary and non-transparent**, as they are often not informed and do not understand the reason for the delays. For example, in the case of family reunification, many single male interviewees in **Austria** and **Germany**, expressed their intention to apply but hesitated to do so due to the complex bureaucracy, (Josipovic and Reeger, 2019, p. 42; Hänsel et al., 2020, p. 53, p. 62).

Regarding **legal assistance**, the time for obtaining legal consultation is referred to as significantly limited. The high number of involved actors is mentioned as an aspect that confuses interviewees (Ibid., p. 32). Despite the complexity of the procedures and the high number of actors, it is stated that little information is provided in countries such as **Germany** (Hänsel et al., 2020, p. 46). Likewise, access to information and legal assistance is described as problematic by refugees in **Greece**, and most did not know exactly at which step of the procedure they were and confused the registration by EASO with the Asylum Interview (Leivaditi et. al., 2020, p. 48). Micro-level interviews in Greece reveal that the Hotspot approach, the Dublin Regulation and the number of related actors confuse applicants even more regarding the procedures. As a result, they cannot understand the meaning of the status they have gained or their relevant rights. Most interviewees have not received legal assistance during their asylum process, and the ones who were assisted by a lawyer stated their dissatisfaction from the services provided. As in **Turkey**, some had managed to gather information through their social networks, friends or other refugees who had already gone through the relevant procedures (Ibid., p. 51). The interviewees stated a lack of information even on critical issues, such as **vulnerability assessments**; interviewees were not aware of the diagnosis as it was not provided in a language they can understand (Ibid, p. 37). In **Iraq**, the situation is the same: most refugees also spoke of a lack of legal advice and of guidance in the process of applying for asylum or register for the application (Warda and Almafrajiet, 2020, p. 24). Legal assistance is also a challenge in **Poland**, where interviewees mentioned that, in the absence of legal aid, “some friends and refugees who already lived in Poland” are important information sources (Pachocka and Sobczak-Szelc, 2020, p. 52). Among the Consortium members, **Sweden** seems to perform better in guaranteeing legal assistance at all stages of the application. The majority of the interviewed asylum applicants there stated that they knew about their right to free legal assistance (Shakra and Szalanska, 2020, p.65). However, even there, the fieldwork revealed shortcomings in the quality of the legal counselling

and most interviewees declared unsatisfied; furthermore, the lack of commitment by the assigned lawyer is mentioned frequently by the legal assistance beneficiaries (Ibid., p. 65).

Many interviewed asylum seekers in different countries mentioned that their experience with the entire asylum procedure is marked by heavy bureaucracy and difficulty. **Language barriers and interpretation problems** are common in all countries (Josipovic and Reeger, 2019, p. 32; Hänsel et al., 2020, p. 53). The **Austria** report highlights “difficulties that applicants face in their encounters with interpreters, though beneficiaries in retrospect have a more positive or neutral assessment than asylum seekers” (Josipovic and Reeger, 2019, p. 32). In **Sweden**, there are repeated complaints regarding the bad quality of translation from Swedish to Arabic (Shakra and Szalanska, 2020, p. 57). The vast majority of respondents referred to written information about the asylum procedure, which led us to the assumption that oral information is scarce (Ibid.). Regarding language problems, many respondents stated that communication has always been a problem, but it has improved in the course of time, such as in **Turkey**. In general, in order to proceed with the bureaucratic requirements, interviewees try to find someone who speaks Turkish and Arabic (Gökalp Aras and Şahin Mencütek, 2020, p. 61). Regardless the differences of languages and countries, the language barrier appears as one of the main problems. The **Germany** report also highlights the complaints of interviewees about the poor quality of interpretation, the participation of biased interpreters in interviews, their incorrect translations, including ‘intentional’ mistranslations, and a refusal to interpret by interpreters. In such cases, applicants also encounter difficulties in changing problematic or erroneous translations. All this creates a feeling of distrust among refugees towards the system (Hänsel et al., 2020, p. 53-54).

The experiences of applicants with national asylum systems are not characterized only by the language barrier but also by **poor treatment and discriminative behaviours**. The general attitude is expressed as a “culture of disbelief” (Anderson, 2014 and Souter, 2011 cited in Foley, 2020, p. 23) in the **UK** report and as “structural mistrust” in the **Germany** report (Hänsel et al., 2020, p. 49). This concept of culture of disbelief was also discussed in a UK Parliamentary committee as “the tendency of those evaluating applications to start from the assumption that the applicant is not telling the truth” (Home Affairs Committee, 2013 cited in Foley, 2020, p. 23). In relation to this, the report also mentions that criminalization dominates all detention narratives in micro-level interviews (Ibid., 30). The interview experience leaves actors with a sense of alienation in relation to the asylum system, and case workers assume the role of behaviour analysts, ambiguously balancing between control and protection functions (Ibid., p. 26). In addition, interviewees in Germany speak of underqualified staff and unqualified decisions (Hänsel et al., 2020, p. 49). Also, hiring not qualified employees for the asylum procedures is addressed as one of the reasons behind the errors and prevailing sloppiness. Almost all reports speak of the difficulties facing refugees who want to correct mistakes such as wrong gender, nationality, age, etc. (and politics of Scandalisation - Ibid., p. 51). The rate of applicants who have suffered these mistakes is 12% in **Germany**. **The UK** report states that mistakes, delays, and maladministration are seen as routine elements in the country’s asylum system (Foley, 2020, p. 30). Interviewees testify to problematic behaviours of officers during the asylum application (Foley, 2020, p. 26). Refugees in **Sweden** also experienced problems during interviews. While asked about their interview experience and the attitude of interrogators, the interviewees gave divergent responses. In general, the early arrivals tended to be much more satisfied with their interviews and evaluated the behaviour of interrogators positively, whereas the opinions of the late-comers (those who arrived in Sweden in autumn 2014 and after) are more negative (Shakra and Szalanska, 2020, p. 58).

Severe living conditions and rights violations have been expressed by the interviewees in many RESPOND countries. The Hotspot centres and RICs in **Greece** were also highly criticized by the refugees for their inhumane living conditions, especially regarding the most vulnerable groups such as women, unaccompanied children and victims of torture or sexual violence

(Leivaditi et. al., 2020, p. 31). Those centres are described by the interviewees as overcrowded and characterized by suffocating living conditions (Ibid., p. 33).

In **Lebanon**, the UNHCR undertakes an important role in asylum procedures, since the country is not a part of the 1951 Convention; micro-level interviews highly criticized this role in “registration, aid reception and administration” [as] one-off financial assistance, unresolved complaints submitted by refugees, perceptions of unfair treatment and neglect” (Rahme, 2020, p. 19).

Unlike EU MSs and **Lebanon** and **Iraq**, Syrians are provided temporary protection in **Turkey**, which does not have an RSD procedure. Although this procedure is not as complicated as international protection, the micro-level interviews reveal that most Syrians do not know their legal status or the difference between international and temporary protection. The empirical data shows that, to them, this process amounts to obtaining ID cards (*kimlik*) (Gökalp Aras and Şahin Mencütek, 2020, p. 57). Micro-level findings confirm that some provinces do not accept any new applications for temporary protection. Also, procedures differ from one district to another within the same city, in particular in Istanbul. On the other hand, this duality also causes province-based differences. Travel permits, travel limitations and the obligation to provide signatures are frequently stated as common problems.

There is no doubt that the perceptions and experiences of asylum seekers are influenced by the practices of institutions and actors involving in asylum procedures. Slowness of the entire process, sloppiness of paper works, lack or low quality of assistance provided during applications and hearings are rarely exceptional experiences or coincidences. They constitute to the practice dimension of deterrence and control mechanisms aiming to reduce to the number of asylum seekers in the respective country.

4. Analysis of Findings and Conclusion

This comparative report, as part of the third Work Package of RESPOND (WP3), discussed both the legal framework and the implementation of refugee protection and asylum procedures in RESPOND countries during the 2011-2018 period, by building on ten RESPOND country reports. The main findings of the comparative analysis are presented in this concluding section.

Overall, the recent developments on refugee protection, both at the level of the legal framework and of its implementation, appear to be highly problematic. While this is the case for the period examined by RESPOND, from 2011 to 2018, more recent developments have not changed the aforementioned observation. If protection is not only limited to survival and physical security but is, above all, related to the provision of the full range of rights, including civil, political, economic, social and cultural rights, urgent action is needed from the part of RESPOND countries and the EU in order to address the ongoing challenging situation as it was discussed within the conceptual part of the report. But here we have to limit ourselves with the findings of the country reports. Also, the best practices and policy recommendations were excluded, which will be covered by another deliverable, which is “D.3.4: Report on Refugee Protection Regimes and Best Practices”.

Since 2015-2016, all RESPOND countries have received large numbers of refugees fleeing war and poverty. Generally speaking, policies are based on the categorization of countries as source, transit, reception and destination countries, or safe or not, in a way that ignores specific socio-political conditions. Nevertheless, these characterizations should remain fluid due to a number of reasons. Firstly, the protection regimes at the international, regional and national

level, as well as their significant transformation during the examined period, are able to alter the aforementioned character of the examined countries. In 2015-2016, some countries play the role of transit countries for refugees on their way to Central-Western Europe. With the closure of the Western Balkan Corridor and the EU-Turkey Statement (in the case of Greece), many asylum seekers and recognized beneficiaries of international protection were forced to remain in those countries. Secondly, these categorizations are fluid and ever-changing, due to the dynamic character of refugee flows and depending on different policies as well as on the aspirations and movements of migrants and refugees, who are able to transform and adapt to new circumstances. Moreover, this categorization conceals movements which can occur simultaneously within countries themselves. Therefore, with this report, we avoid such categorization and provided mainly similarities as displaying the differences on the country basis under each heading.

Starting from the two significant commonalities of the normative framework regarding refugee protection, all RESPOND countries have signed the 1951 Convention and its additional protocols, except Lebanon and Iraq. Also, Turkey has a geographic limitation. But, at least in what refers to refugee protection, from definitions to certain common principles such as 'non-refoulement', the Convention provides a common framework. In addition, as EU members, most RESPOND countries are bound by the EU legal framework of the CEAS and institutional collaboration with EASO, FRONTEX and Europol. The common legal framework on matters of refugee protection is constituted by the 'Refugee Qualification Directive' (Directive 2004/83/EC), the 'Asylum Procedure Directive' (Directive 2005/85/EC) and the 'Temporary Protection Directive (Directive 2001/55/EC) – although the latter has not been implemented for Syrian mass migration. Among RESPOND countries, the Brexit has created many uncertainties for the UK as a former EU member. On the other hand, although it is not an EU member, Turkey show significant similarities with the EU *acquis* and it represents a country-case as being between the EU and non-EU RESPOND countries.

Despite the common framework at the international and supranational level, significant differences exist at the regional, national and even sub-national level, regarding both legal procedures and the implementation of refugee protection. Nevertheless, a common tendency observed in all countries is the even more restrictive approach to protection. It starts beyond the borders and continues after the borders have been crossed, penetrating different aspects and stages of the procedures. This becomes visible with the physical measures at the borders (such as security walls) and the pushbacks, and is supported by additional, national-level procedural measures to prevent and restrain access to international protection (Pannia et al., 2018, p. 8).

It has been observed that new procedures and more restrictive measures have been introduced in the majority of RESPOND countries; thus, the existing tendency continued and became even more dynamic and complex. One of the new developments is the Global Compact on Refugees of December 2018. The Compact was affirmed by the member states of the UN General Assembly on 17 December 2018, in the annual resolution on the work of UNHCR. The Compact does not replace the existing international refugee system. It tries to fill in the gaps of the Convention, in particular regarding international cooperation and responsibility sharing (UN, 2018a), for the Convention focuses on the rights and obligations of states and ignores the 'how' question and the role of non-state actors. Although it is not legally binding, it focuses on more equitable and predictable burden- and responsibility-sharing, providing a guideline for the international community.

In general, the main objective of these restrictive policies is to reduce the number of entries and asylum applications. However, this centralization brings more complexity, with additional preventive procedures that make it even more difficult for applicants to understand the procedures and receive legal assistance. The centralization is observed even in what refers to legal assistance and the limitation of non-state actors providing legal aid, despite heavy

criticism in many countries, while many others provide no systematic and structure legal assistance whatsoever. In addition to the decreasing number of applications, there is also a tendency among many member states to downgrade the rights of asylum applicants and beneficiaries of protection. In general, all newly introduced amendments and regulations bring new restrictions and limitations to existing standards of rights. Furthermore, accelerated and fast-track procedures, increased rejections and long waiting periods for applicants have become common patterns. For EU members, this leads to diverging implementations between Member States, and the deficiencies of the CEAS have become more visible.

It became obvious that almost all RESPOND countries **have transformed their legal framework** on refugee protection and asylum procedures during the examined period, usually following the European or International legislation. Nevertheless, many differences have been observed between the legal framework and administrative procedures of RESPOND countries and the broader EU or international ones, indicating the different ways in which each Member State intends to implement the common legislative guidelines and directives. In fact, there is no unified protection system, not even in the EU Member States. What emerges in general is **highly complicated and fragmented** protection regime and asylum system in all RESPOND countries, where centralization and de-centralization, coexist. Almost all RESPOND countries face pressure and a lack of administrative capacity to process the increasing number of applications. The tightening of borders is the main strategy in many countries, in an effort to restrict access to national/federal territory and, thus, to the asylum procedure. Beyond the tightening of borders, the narrowing and slowing down of access to international protection and the introduction of additional national procedural tools with the intention of streamlining the RSD process are also observed in most countries (Pannia et al., 2018, p. 41). Many RESPOND countries have introduced **more restrictive policies** that aim to **reduce the number of asylum seekers reaching their territory, decrease the number of entrances and asylum applications as well as the number of beneficiaries of international protection, and generally prevent or restrain access to international protection** – a purpose further served by their problematic implementation which causes delays in registration and decisions and complicated administrative procedures. Additionally, almost all countries tended to downgrade the rights of applicants and beneficiaries of international protection, as all newly introduced amendments and new regulations impose restrictions or limitations to existing standards of rights. Overall, the legal framework of protection in all RESPOND countries is characterized by hindrances and obstacles. The Table 4 summarizes the general tendencies without making a distinction between EU and non-EU members, mostly highlighting the commonalities to capture the ongoing patterns regarding refugee protection.

These changes in the legal framework have been unfolding in parallel with the increase of **anti-migrant narratives and negative representations** of refugee arrivals, protection and reception. Most reports mention the perceptions and usage of the notion of “crisis” or “state of emergency” (such as Germany, Greece, Lebanon, Italy and Poland) and humanitarian crisis. Furthermore, the acts of solidarity that emerged in the entire European continent – but especially in “border” countries such as Greece and Italy – has decreased during the last years. Another crucial point is the continuous fragmentation of the protection framework. As regards the **different types of protection**, further **fragmentation** emerges due to the existence of more than one basic form of protection (that of refugee status), such as subsidiary international protection, temporary protection, humanitarian protection and a wide range of other national or regional forms of protection. This large proliferation of different forms of protection creates **unequal treatment of persons and discrimination in the protection of rights**. Furthermore, the same observation applies to the asylum procedures. More specifically, different kinds of asylum procedures are adopted by different countries, also resulting in complexity and fragmentation, not only in the institutional framework but also in the **“categorization” of asylum seekers and beneficiaries of protection**. For example, the existence of accelerated procedures, border procedures, fast-track-procedures and admissibility procedures, beyond the “regular” one, contributes to this direction. The concepts of **“safe third country”** (such as

in the case of the EU-Turkey Statement) is also linked to the **multiple categorizations of applicants, to the early distinction of those who “deserve” asylum from others, and to the aim of preventing the permanent stay of refugees.** In this direction, the “third safe country” lists are constantly updated to justify deportations and returns, while the differences between forced and voluntary returns have become vague. This also resulted in the stratified legal statuses and determined rights produced by the different procedures, in addition to traceable nationality-based discriminations, such as in the case of Afghans. The increase in rejections, long waiting periods for applicants, returns as an alternative to refugee protection and bilateral or EU-level readmission agreements or administrative arrangements have become common characteristics of policies.

This fragmentation of the examination of claims into different procedures is based on (and at the same time reproduces) different categorizations of asylum seekers. Through the use of different procedural frameworks and presumptions, the recast Asylum Procedures Directive has enabled Member States to speed up the examination of individual claims. The complex procedures and presumptions against applicants have allowed EU Member States to deflect responsibility for asylum seekers more easily and further away from their territory (AIDA, 2016a). Building on the set of rules and procedures provided by the recast Asylum Procedure Directive, all RESPOND European countries have introduced procedural tools in their domestic asylum system, aimed at determining who is worthy of protection and who is not, without always examining the merits of particular asylum claims (Pannia et al., 2018).

The national reports underline a rapidly changing and not quite consistent national legal framework, as well as of a multiplicity of actors involved in the institutional structure of refugee protection. The situation is even more complex in the case of EU-member RESPOND countries given, among others, the additional admissibility procedures caused by the Dublin Regulation and the role of EASO, especially in the cases of Italy and Greece, who implement the Hotspot system.³³ Briefly, almost all RESPOND countries have undergone a change in legislation with most new regulations being implemented in 2018 and 2019; while not necessarily coherent, the new laws follow an overall restrictive tendency. A common feature in most RESPOND countries is the new actors that take role regarding refugee protection; however, rather than governance more centralized decision-making practices have been observed within the majority of RESPOND countries.

In the same direction, **vulnerability** plays a crucial role, especially in the examination of asylum applications, as many EU countries such as Greece, Italy and Poland provide that asylum applications by persons with special needs are to be examined by way of priority. However, in some countries such as Greece, vulnerability plays a significant (although at times less formal) role in other steps of the asylum procedure, also resulting in the multiple categorizations of applicants for international protection. Another point that should be mentioned is that of vulnerability. The recognized vulnerability justifies priority in receiving protection. However, important disappearances regarding the recognition of vulnerabilities were observable in all the RESPOND countries.

Additionally, some new mechanisms and policies such as the Hotspot approach emerge as crucial aspects in the formulation and implementation of policies **The Hotspot approach still serves as a cornerstone for the protection regime, not only in respective frontline countries (Greece and Italy) but for the whole EU.** However, it seems that this approach neither managed to accomplish the target of an effective cooperation at the EU level nor to provide protection according to EU laws (ECRE, 2016 & AIDA, 2017). Not only do living conditions in Hotspots not provide safe conditions for asylum seekers, they also seem to create new discriminations and violations of rights in accessing in asylum procedure and increase return policies. Instead of supporting Member States faced with disproportionate “migratory

³³ For the detailed comparative table, Pannia et al., 2018, p. 24.

pressure”, the implementation of the Hotspot approach has led to the normalization of inhuman treatments, detention and pushbacks at the borders. At the same time, it creates “buffer zones” for border management and for the protection regime in the entire EU, thus failing to provide even the basic forms of protection to asylum seekers. In this direction, the 2016 EU-Turkey Statement, along with unlawful detention practices (such as in the case of Greece), are highly problematic.

Another clear implementation failure regards the **Dublin III Regulation**, as reflected by the expert and refugee interviews of the majority of country reports. In practice, the Dublin III Regulation causes unfair burden sharing, in particular for the frontline countries at the EU borders, and is criticized for its practical deficiencies and its normative premises. The concept of “first country of asylum”, as the core of the Dublin Regulation, aims to prevent secondary movements within Europe and results in uneven responsibility sharing among Member States. Almost all EU MSs reports emphasize the need for an alternative process to the Dublin Regime, with new forms of solidary distribution and responsibility sharing mechanisms as well as a stronger harmonization of national asylum procedures within the EU.

Among the ten RESPOND countries, seven have signed the Compact, while Austria and Italy abstained, and Poland voted against the Compact. If we are to look into the justification given by these countries, without going into the details of the Compact itself, we shall get a glimpse of the different approaches on refugee protection. The representative of **Austria**, for example, justified not signing of the Compact by stressing the fact that there is no reference to the right to migrate within the Austrian legal order, therefore making no distinction between legal and illegal migration and watering down the difference between the two (UN, 2018b). Also, access to the labour market and the granting of social benefits or health care are considered rights that should be regulated exclusively by Austrian law. Thus, for Austria, there is a risk that the Compact might turn into customary international law and be used as reference for the clarification of legal status in national or international courts (Ibid.). Therefore, this justification reflects the common tendency in RESPOND countries towards centralization and nationalization and the decline of certain rights, as was also observed in the country reports (Josipovic and Reeger, 2019). On the other hand, the abstention of **Italy**, which is one of the frontline countries implementing the Hotspot approach, was officially explained with the need for burden-sharing and parliamentary debate as it follows “Government has deferred a decision on whether to join the Global Compact to a subsequent Parliamentary debate.” (UN, 2018b). As different from those, Poland’s reaction is officially explained as the Compact is against to the national priorities, which are mentioned as security and control over its borders (Ibid.). The representative of Poland highlights that the Global Compact is not the right instrument to manage migration and does not serve the best interests of her country and its people, while its sovereign rights to restrict admission of non-nationals carries utmost importance and it is difficult to implement some standards such as detention standards (Ibid.). In line with Austria’s justification, the Compact’s potential to form a customary law or soft law is seen as a risk. Thus, the Compact one more time showed the complex and fragmented legal milieu in the countries that we have studied (Pannia et al., 2018, p. 22).

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Appendix

Table 4: Patterns by Country

	Dispersion of authority in asylum institutions (registration, application, appeal)	Mode of Relations with EU in asylum /protection issues	Downgrading previously granted rights	Moving to temporary measures	From welcoming to “return turn”	Restricting NGOs - societal actors
Austria	Centralized	Compliance with minimum EU-standards	Asylum for 3 years (2016)		Yes	NGOs
Germany	Centralized	Compliance	*Limiting Family unification *Shortening duration (3 years) of residence permits (2016) *Restrictions over freedom of movement (2016)	Increase in Subsidiary protection to Syrians since 2016	Yes (at the beginning of the mass migration from Syria yes, but by 2014 return)	
Poland	In transition	Decoupling	Extensive rights including working right			
Sweden		Compliance minimum level	*limiting the rights of subsidiary protection holders	Subsidiary protection to Syrians and more Temporary measures 2016	Yes	
Greece	More centralized since 2011	Stronger cooperation of the EU (EASO, Frontex)			Yes	
Italy			*Long term residence (5 years) *Abolishing humanitarian protection status		Yes	
UK	Centralized	Not bound by the EU acquis, decoupling after Brexit			N/A	no
Turkey	More centralized (2013), UNHCR’s role is minimalized since 2018	Harmonizing with EU acquis	*Restrictions over freedom of movement since 2016 *Working rights	X	Highly relevant	
Lebanon	Mixed UNHCR’s role is restricted since 2015	Non-relevant	Restrictions over freedom of movement (curfews)	Non-relevant	Highly relevant	Societal actors
Iraq	Federal UNHCR role is crucial	Non-relevant			No	Societal actors

Source: Authors’ Elaboration on National Reports